

“Baseline Study on the Status of the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem Nexus in Middle Eastern Countries”

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This study was conducted by Dr. Eyad Batarseh, Hussam Faraj, Leen Amereh, Leen Zayadin, Saif Al-Omari, Areen Ghawanmeh, Ahmad Afaneh, Dr. Ziad Ghezawi of Dar Al-Omran, and reviewed by Dr. Mutawakil Obaidat (WDC), Dr. Ammar A. Albalasmeh (WDC), Dr. Maha Al-Zu’bi (IWMI), Dr. Bunyod Holmatov (IWMI), Eng. Eman Hamada (WDC), Eng. Moemen Al Wahshat (WDC), Dr. Mohammed Osama Azzam (WDC) of JUST.

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Final Report - Baseline Study on the Status of the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem Nexus in Middle Eastern Countries

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	1
1 Introduction.....	5
1.1 Background.....	6
1.2 Objectives.....	7
2 National Assessment of WEFE Sectors in the Study Countries.....	8
2.1 Iran.....	8
2.1.1 Country Overview.....	8
2.1.2 WEFE Situation.....	10
2.1.3 National Policies and Legal Framework.....	20
2.1.4 Socio-Economic Situation.....	25
2.1.5 Recommendations.....	26
2.2 Iraq.....	28
2.2.1 Country Overview.....	28
2.2.2 WEFE Situation.....	29
2.2.3 National Policies and Legal Framework.....	43
2.2.4 Socio-Economic Situation.....	47
2.2.5 Recommendations.....	48
2.3 Syria.....	51
2.3.1 Country Overview.....	51
2.3.2 WEFE Situation.....	52
2.3.3 National Policies and Legal Framework.....	61
2.3.4 Socio-Economic Situation.....	66
2.3.5 Recommendations.....	67
2.4 Türkiye.....	69
2.4.1 Country Overview.....	69
2.4.2 WEFE Situation.....	70
2.4.3 National Policies and Legal Framework.....	79
2.4.4 Socio-Economic Situation.....	82
2.4.5 Recommendations.....	83
3 WEFE Nexus successful and unsustainable practices.....	85
3.1 Successful Practices.....	85
3.2 Unsustainable Practices.....	97
4 Policy, Legal Frameworks and Agreements Assessment in the Study Countries.....	100
4.1 Iran.....	100

4.1.1	Assessment of Current Policies and Governance Structures	108
4.1.2	Analysis of Legal Frameworks and Agreements.....	108
4.1.3	Identification of Gaps.....	108
4.1.4	Potential for Cooperation.....	109
4.2	Iraq.....	109
4.2.1	Assessment of Current Policies and Governance Structures	117
4.2.2	Analysis of Legal Frameworks and Agreements.....	118
4.2.3	Identification of Gaps.....	118
4.2.4	Potential for Cooperation.....	118
4.3	Syria	118
4.3.1	Assessment of Current Policies and Governance Structures	128
4.3.2	Analysis of Legal Frameworks and Agreements.....	129
4.3.3	Identification of Gaps.....	129
4.3.4	Potential for Cooperation.....	129
4.4	Türkiye	129
4.4.1	Assessment of Current Policies and Governance Structures	137
4.4.2	Analysis of Legal Frameworks and Agreements.....	138
4.4.3	Identification of Gaps.....	138
4.4.4	Potential for Cooperation.....	138
5	Suggested Transboundary WEFE Projects	139
5.1	Small-Scale WEFE Projects	139
5.2	Medium-Scale WEFE Projects.....	140
6	Conclusions	141
7	Appendices	144
Appendix A : Stakeholder Engagement.....		144
Stakeholder Mapping		144
Stakeholder Views		146
Appendix B : Stakeholder Engagement Form		163

List of Figures

Figure 1 Iran country map (source: Worldometer)	9
Figure 2 The 6 Catchments in Iran (Fanack Water)	10
Figure 3 Water use by sector in Iran (source: Aquastat).....	13
Figure 4 Energy supplied per resource in Iran in 2021 (source: IEA)	15
Figure 5 Energy Consumption by Sector in Iran in 2021 (source: IEA).....	16
Figure 6 Iran's landcover map (Ansari et al. 2023)	20
Figure 7 Iraq country map (source: Worldometer)	29
Figure 8 Precipitation (mm) in Iraq (1923 – 2022) (source: tradingeconomics, (2022))	30
Figure 9 The major groundwater aquifers in Iraq (source: Othman et al. 2022)	31
Figure 10 Groundwater depths in different zones in Iraq.....	32
Figure 11 Energy supply per resource in Iraq (source: IEA).	37
Figure 12 Energy consumption in Iraq per sector in 2021 (source: IEA).....	38
Figure 13 Syria country map (source: Worldometer)	51
Figure 14 Water basins in Syria (Fanack)	53
Figure 15 Water consumption by sector in Syria in 2020	55
Figure 16 Energy consumption per sector in Syria 2021 (source: IEA)	57
Figure 17 Organizational Chart of Ministry of Irrigation in Syria	62
Figure 18 Chart illustrating the organizational structure of the Ministry of Electricity in Syria	64
Figure 19 Türkiye country map (source: Worldometer).....	69
Figure 20 The 25 Catchments of Türkiye (source: Fanack Water).....	71
Figure 21 Water consumption by sector in Türkiye in 2021	72
Figure 22 Energy supply in Türkiye 2021 (source: IEA)	74
Figure 23 Energy consumption per sector in Türkiye 2021 (source: IEA)	75
Figure 24 Key Institutions in Türkiye's Energy Sector	80
Figure 25 As Samra Wastewater Treatment Plant.....	87
Figure 26 The Shahid Abbaspour Dam	88
Figure 27 Rawafed Agriculture Organic Farm	89
Figure 28 GAP Project Locations (source: Ruffin et al., 2021)	90
Figure 29 Jordan Hydroponic Agriculture and Employment Development Project (source: ECO Consult)	91
Figure 30 Mosul Dam	92
Figure 31 Wadi Al Arab Water Supply Project II	93
Figure 32 Al Khobar Desalination Plant (source: ACCOINA)	94
Figure 33 Tabqa Dam (source: Zaman al-Wasl).....	95
Figure 34 Sundrop Farms in Port Augusta (source: Centuria).....	96
Figure 35 Al Baydha Project (source: Strickler, D)	96

List of Tables

Table 1 Water resources in Iran in 2020 (source: AQUASTAT)	10
Table 2 Surface and groundwater resources and the corresponding transboundary countries	12
Table 3 Energy supply per sector in 2021 – Iran (source: IEA)	15
Table 4 Energy consumption per sector in 2021 – Iran (source: IEA)	16
Table 5. Ministries overseeing the water sector in Iran	21
Table 6 Institutions overseeing the energy sector in Iran	22
Table 7 Socio-Economic Indicators - Iran	25
Table 8 Transboundary Aquifers in Iraq	33
Table 9 Small water harvesting dams in the Eastern Valleys in Iraq.	34
Table 10 Small water harvesting dams in the Western Desert in Iraq.	34
Table 11 Energy supply per resource in 2021 – Iraq (source: IEA)	37
Table 12 Energy consumption per sector in 2021 – Iraq (source: IEA)	37
Table 13 Socio-Economic Indicators - Iraq	48
Table 14 Water resources in Syria 2020.	53
Table 15 Energy supply per resource in 2021 – Syria	56
Table 16 Energy consumption per sector in 2021 – Syria (source: IEA)	56
Table 17 Socio-Economic Indicators - Syria	66
Table 18 Water resources in Türkiye 2020	70
Table 19 Energy supply per resource in 2021 – Türkiye	73
Table 20 Energy consumption per sector in 2021 – Türkiye (source: IEA)	74
Table 21 Socio-Economic Indicators - Türkiye	83
Table 22 Successful WEFE NEXUS projects	87
Table 23 Unsustainable practices and lessons learnt.....	98
Table 24 Policies, governance, legal frameworks - Iran	100
Table 25 Policies, governance, legal frameworks - Iraq	109
Table 26 Policies, governance, legal frameworks - Syria	119
Table 27 Policies, governance, legal frameworks - Türkiye	129
Table 28 Stakeholder mapping table.....	145

Executive Summary

This baseline study on the status of Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus in Iran, Iraq, Syria, and Türkiye consisted of a national assessment of each one of the WEFE sectors utilizing a literature review and stakeholder consultations, including the current situation of the sectors highlighting the risks, the national policies and legal frameworks, and the socio-economic situation. This was followed by an overview of examples of successful projects in the study countries and in the region, and instances of unsustainable practices in the study countries. The study also presents an assessment of the current policies and governance structure to identify the gaps and show potential for cooperation. The study finally suggests small and medium scale WEFE projects that can be implemented across the study countries. Main conclusions for each country can be summarized in the following.

Iran has made progress in water-energy Nexus through its Ministry of Energy as it is responsible for both water and energy sectors, which is considered the highest level of Nexus, particularly in projects like hydropower dams, but gaps persist in incorporating the WEFE Nexus in agricultural and environmental sectors. While there is room to enhance integration, current efforts provide a strong foundation to build a more comprehensive nexus strategy that bridges sector-specific outcomes.

Iraq faces challenges in implementing Nexus-based strategies due to the recent political instability, and transboundary water issues, which heavily affect the water and agricultural sectors, in addition to severe ecological impacts including salinization and severe impacts on the Mesopotamian Marshlands. Despite medium to low level awareness of WEFE Nexus approach, several opportunities exist for innovative projects such as solar-powered agriculture and solar desalination, but further integration is required.

Syria exhibits low awareness of the WEFE Nexus, with separate management of sectors and limited synergy in existing policies. Years of conflict have disrupted governance and created significant data gaps, emphasizing the need for comprehensive strategies and collaborative initiatives to address resource management and support recovery. There is a clear need for rebuilding the water, energy, food, and environmental sectors infrastructure and projects which is a good opportunity to integrate the WEFE Nexus approach into this rebuilding efforts.

Türkiye demonstrates strong infrastructure and technological advancement in WEFE sectors, with high awareness of the WEFE Nexus approach but with a lack of consensus of the exact definition of WEFE Nexus and its implementation approach. Integrating advanced solutions like precision agriculture and renewable energy systems within water and agricultural sectors present an opportunity to enhance resource efficiency and sustainable development through a cohesive Nexus framework. Also, Türkiye could benefit from issuing a WEFE Nexus policy document that clearly defines the definition and approach to unify all efforts in the country.

Based on the literature review and input from stakeholders, the baseline study conducted for the WEFE situation of the four countries, the main recommendations for Iran are the following.

In Iran, enhancing systems to monitor pollution and promote efficient water use, particularly in agriculture, would significantly benefit Iran. Adopting modern irrigation techniques and drought-resistant crops can improve resilience. Addressing groundwater overuse through well-planned regulations and artificial recharge techniques is essential, alongside the development of conflict resolution mechanisms to manage water allocation during droughts.

For the energy sector, challenges such as aging infrastructure and sanctions affect Iran's energy security. Investing in renewable energy sources like solar and wind offers a sustainable path forward,

reducing reliance on water-intensive hydropower and fossil fuels. Integrating water needs into energy planning and fostering regional collaboration could help mitigate some of the impacts of sanctions.

In the agricultural sector, strengthening water-use efficiency and modernizing irrigation systems are pivotal for sustaining agriculture. Introducing drought-tolerant crops and increasing the reuse of treated wastewater can enhance resilience against climate challenges. Expanding support for farmers and food assistance programs can address economic pressures, while agricultural policies should aim to balance increased food production with sustainable water management.

For the environmental sector, Iran's ecosystems face pressures from pollution, deforestation, and water shortages. Stricter environmental regulations, habitat restoration efforts, and sustainable water management practices are necessary to safeguard biodiversity and prevent erosion. These actions will help maintain aquatic ecosystems and natural habitats, contributing to long-term environmental health.

For Iraq, the following recommendations are proposed. In the water sector, upgrading Iraq's water infrastructure presents a valuable opportunity to enhance water management. Modernizing irrigation systems, reducing distribution losses, and using treated wastewater instead of freshwater for oil extraction can significantly improve efficiency. Strengthening water-sharing agreements with neighboring countries, including Türkiye, Syria, and Iran, will play a key role in securing water resources. A comprehensive national water strategy focusing on sustainable use, wastewater reuse, and conservation technologies, such as drip irrigation and aquifer recharge, will further enhance resilience.

In the energy sector, modernizing energy infrastructure is a priority to reduce transmission losses and enhance energy security. Expanding renewable energy sources like solar and wind will help diversify Iraq's energy mix and reduce reliance on fossil fuels. Efforts to improve governance, curb electricity theft, and attract foreign investment will strengthen the energy sector. Additionally, regional energy cooperation offers opportunities to mitigate geopolitical risks and promote stability.

For Iraq's food security, the public distribution system (PDS) and agricultural sector can benefit from investments in modern farming practices and irrigation efficiency. Introducing drought-resistant crops and supporting conflict-affected regions with rebuilt agricultural markets will enhance food security. Expanding social safety nets and stabilizing local economies will ensure better access to food for vulnerable populations.

For the environmental sector, protecting Iraq's ecosystems, including the vital Mesopotamian marshlands, should be a national priority. These marshlands not only support biodiversity but also provide natural flood control. Conservation efforts can focus on reducing habitat loss, strengthening enforcement of environmental regulations, and addressing pollution from agricultural and industrial activities. Investments in research can help identify and protect critical ecosystems for long-term sustainability.

For Syria, the following recommendations are proposed. In the water sector, rebuilding and modernizing Syria's water infrastructure offers a crucial opportunity to address water scarcity. Enhancing irrigation systems, promoting rainwater harvesting, and investing in wastewater treatment can significantly reduce water loss and ease the burden on freshwater resources. Developing a comprehensive water management strategy that includes climate adaptation measures and collaboration on shared water resources, such as the Euphrates River, will support long-term water security.

In the energy sector, restoring and upgrading Syria's energy infrastructure, including power plants and transmission networks, is an important step toward reducing outages and improving energy reliability. By addressing energy inefficiencies and diversifying sources with renewable options like solar and wind, Syria can reduce reliance on oil and gas. Regional cooperation and strategies to address geopolitical challenges will further enhance energy stability.

Revitalizing agricultural infrastructure is key to restoring food security in Syria. Providing farmers with modern tools, improved seeds, and advanced techniques can support the recovery of essential crops like wheat and barley. Strengthening food supply chains and expanding assistance programs for conflict-affected populations will ensure better access to food. Promoting climate-resilient farming practices and efficient water management can further boost productivity and resilience in the agricultural sector.

For the environmental sector, Syria can focus on restoring vital ecosystems such as the Al Badia steppe and protecting wetlands around the Euphrates River. Initiatives to replant native vegetation and rehabilitate degraded habitats will help combat soil erosion and support biodiversity. Improving waste management and upgrading water treatment infrastructure, particularly in areas affected by conflict or hosting refugee settlements, will contribute to cleaner and healthier environments.

For Türkiye, the following recommendations are proposed. In the water sector, efficient water use is crucial to meeting Türkiye's growing demands, particularly in agriculture. Modernizing irrigation systems with technologies and increasing investments in wastewater treatment and reuse can significantly conserve water resources. Expanding Integrated Water Resource Management (IWRM) practices and strengthening pollution control measures will further support water quality protection. Public awareness campaigns on water conservation can play a vital role in encouraging sustainable practices.

In the energy sector, diversifying energy sources through investments in renewables such as solar, wind, and geothermal energy presents an excellent opportunity to enhance energy security and reduce dependence on imported fossil fuels. Upgrading energy infrastructure to reduce transmission losses and promoting energy efficiency in industries and households are key steps forward. Strengthening diplomatic ties with energy-exporting countries and developing a liberalized internal energy market can also position Türkiye as a strategic energy hub in the region.

For the food sector, improving storage, transportation, and processing systems can help reduce food loss and waste, boosting food security and export potential. Addressing food affordability through targeted subsidies and price stabilization measures can alleviate the impact of inflation on households. Climate adaptation strategies, such as crop diversification and efficient water use, will help safeguard critical water-intensive crops like wheat and barley, ensuring sustained agricultural production.

In the environmental sector, Türkiye's afforestation and reforestation efforts are commendable and should continue to combat desertification and protect biodiversity. Strengthening conservation initiatives for critical ecosystems, such as the Balkan Mixed Forests and Anatolian steppes, is vital to preserving endemic species. Enhanced regulation of industrial and agricultural activities, alongside the expansion of protected areas, will ensure biodiversity is safeguarded and ecosystem services remain robust.

Based on the literature review and input from stakeholders, the following projects are proposed to be utilized throughout the study countries (Iran, Iraq, Syria, and Türkiye). WEFE Nexus Transboundary means that the projects can be implemented across all the countries.

Small-Scale Projects

1. Smart Irrigation Systems for Small-Scale Farms

This project proposes the implementation of smart irrigation systems for small-scale farms in rural areas. By using sensor technology and automated water management systems, farmers can optimize water usage, reducing wastage and increasing crop yields. The smart irrigation system will monitor soil moisture, weather conditions, and crop water needs, ensuring efficient water delivery with minimal human intervention.

2. Solar-Powered Water Pumps for Remote Agricultural Areas

This project focuses on deploying solar-powered water pumps in remote agricultural areas, replacing diesel-powered pumps or manual irrigation methods that require intensive labor. Solar-powered pumps use renewable energy to provide reliable and affordable irrigation water, particularly in rural areas that are off the grid.

Medium-Scale Projects

1. Establishing a NEXUS Governance Framework and Policy Coordination

This project aims to develop and implement a WEFE (Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem) NEXUS governance framework for each country independently utilizing a unified approach between the BPME countries. The focus will be on creating a coordinated policy mechanism and governance framework that addresses the shared management of water, energy, and agricultural resources while preserving ecosystems in each country. This includes drafting a legal document that defines the WEFE Nexus approach for the country introduces joint policies and KPIs between the sectors in order to make the WEFE Nexus approach more applicable and more sustainable for the country. These governance frameworks can be scaled up to develop a Transboundary WEFE Nexus coordination body that aims to optimize the utilization of shared resources between the BPME countries.

2. Floating Photovoltaic (PV) System for Water Bodies and Agricultural Use

This project proposes the installation of floating photovoltaic (PV) solar energy systems on various water bodies, such as ponds, lakes, and reservoirs. Floating PV panels harness the potential of these water surfaces to generate solar power, reducing the need for land-based installations while helping to conserve water by minimizing evaporation. In agricultural contexts, floating PV systems can provide clean energy for farms, supporting irrigation and other farm operations. The integration of solar power with water management enhances renewable energy generation and contributes to sustainable agricultural practices and water conservation.

Introduction

The Middle East region has long suffered from water scarcity, which has been worsened by the impact of climate change, population increase, and fast rate of industrialization. As a result, the decreasing supply of water has become an urgent matter that threatens both water security as well as environmental sustainability in this region. In addition to water shortage, the Middle East also experiences weak governance as well as a lack of environmental sustainability resulting from over-extraction of available resources, degraded quality of rivers and poor farming practices¹.

Comprehensive measures need to be taken in order to successfully tackle these complex challenges. As a foremost priority, there has to be an improvement in water management practices. The ability of the region to cope with an existing water scarcity can be enhanced by using efficient water distribution systems and integrated water resource management. Equally important is embracing cross-sectoral sustainable practices. This means incorporating technologies that conserve the amount of water used in various sectors such as industry, agriculture and domestic use. Innovative methods, such as drip irrigation or water reclamation could help by considerably reducing the quantity of water consumed and mitigating the stress on limited available resources².

Additionally, awareness must be raised about responsible usage and conservation of water. Education and outreach programs have a significant role in providing information necessary for societies to adopt sustainable lifestyles. Enlightening people about the negative consequences arising from excessive consumption of water and its pollution can create a sense of collective responsibility among them towards its protection in the Middle East region. The implementation of effective policies and regulations to ensure sustainable management of it are equally vital; this encompasses setting up limits for use, enforcing pollution control measures, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices³.

In addition, addressing the causes of water scarcity, such as global warming and population growth, requires a multi-faceted and cooperative approach. Global warming exacerbates water scarcity by altering precipitation patterns and increasing evaporation rates, while population growth intensifies demand for limited water resources. Tackling these challenges involves fostering international discussions and partnerships to promote sustainable development and enhance regional resilience to climate change. By collaborating with other countries and organizations, the region can access the necessary resources, expertise, and financing to implement long-term solutions. These partnerships can support the adoption of innovative technologies, such as water-efficient irrigation systems and advanced desalination methods, as well as policies aimed at managing demand and reducing waste, thereby mitigating the impacts of both climate change and population pressure on water resources.

The Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus strategy focuses on the important connection and interdependencies between the four WEF sectors. This notion focuses on systemic efficiency rather than individual sectoral benefits for the future sustainability of these sectors. What happens in one

¹ Zarei, M. (2020). The water-energy-food nexus: A holistic approach for resource security in Iran, Iraq, and Turkey. *Water-Energy Nexus*, 3, 81–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wen.2020.05.004>

² Yazdanpanah, M., Hayati, D., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., & Zamani, G. H. (2014). Understanding farmers' intention and behavior regarding water conservation in the Middle-East and North Africa: A case study in Iran. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 135, 63–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2014.01.016>

³ EL OUADI, Ihssan & Ouazar, D. & El Youssefi, Lahcen. (2020). A decision support model to improve water resources management in agriculture: evaluation of the drip irrigation efficiency in the Ait Ben Yacoub region, East of Morocco. *E3S Web of Conferences*. 183. 10.1051/e3sconf/202018302006.

sector may have unintended consequences or profound impacts on others, causing ripple effects across the entire WEFE Nexus web⁴.

Consequently, a full grasp of cross-sectoral relationships is essential in augmenting water security, advancing socio-economic development as well as ensuring national and regional stability. Through delving into complex linkages among water, energy, food and ecosystems, the potential for synergy can be increased and tradeoffs/conflict between these sectors is minimized. This means recognizing that the challenges posed by the WEFE Nexus are multi-faceted and seeking solutions considering the multiple factors at play⁴.

Failure to consider possible trade-offs as well as externalities involved with these interconnections could result in a lack of trust and rising tension between sectors at national levels and among countries shared water resources. Such results may eventually hinder collaboration, slow down advancement or even lead to conflicts. Thus, it is important to adopt an all-inclusive approach that recognizes and addresses the multiple challenges and opportunities within the WEFE Nexus framework⁵.

A sustainable future that maintains a balance between the demands of the WEFE sectors can only be achieved through collaboration and conscious decision-making. This also includes the promotion of global stability and wellbeing. Incorporating stakeholder participation across the sectors to gather different perspectives and encourage dialogue can aid in establishing strategies that focus on resource allocation, resilience, and reducing negative effects such as resource depletion, environmental degradation, and social inequities⁵.

Moreover, the WEFE Nexus approach recognizes that many challenges are also intergenerational. Decisions made in the present should not hinder the needs of future generations in any way. This means that long-term thinking, sustainable strategies, and short and long-term perspectives should be created.

The WEFE Nexus strategy represents a coherent framework for dealing with challenges associated with the connections between water, energy, food, and ecosystems. A sustainable future that supports the welfare of current and future generations can be achieved by integrating the relationship between different sectors, focusing on collaboration and using a cohesive approach. The challenges and opportunities concerning the WEFE Nexus can be navigated through conscious decision-making to promote regional stability, cooperation, and efficient resource use.

1.1 Background

The Blue Peace Middle East (BPME) is an initiative focusing on the use of water resources for peace and sustainable development in the region. The WEFE Nexus Program is an initiative implemented by the Islamic Network on Water Resources Development and Management (INWRDAM) WEFE Nexus Hub, which is concentrated towards enhancing water, energy, food security, and environmental resilience. This program allows for the exchange of regional knowledge and implementation of WEFE Nexus projects. The Water Diplomacy Center (WDC) (the Client), with the Steering Committee of WDC, INWRDAM, and BPME Coordination Office representatives, along with relevant stakeholders, plan to undertake a WEFE Baseline Study for Iran, Iraq, Syria, and Türkiye. This

⁴ Pérez, Leonardo. (2023). Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus: A key concept for a more resilient adaptation to the climate crisis. *Natural Resources Conservation and Research*. 6. 2324. [10.24294/nrcr.v6i1.2324](https://doi.org/10.24294/nrcr.v6i1.2324).

⁵ C Canessa, C., Vavvos, A., Triliva, S., Kafkalas, I., Vrachioli, M., & Sauer, J. (2022). Implementing a combined Delphi and Focus Group qualitative methodology in Nexus research designs—The case of the WEFE Nexus in Apokoronas, Crete. *PLoS ONE*, 17(7), e0271443. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0271443>

study is being conducted by Dar Al Omran Infrastructure and Environment (the Consultant) and is planned for completion by 2024. This study aims to identify knowledge gaps and opportunities for strengthening intersectoral linkages.

The findings of the baseline study will serve as a foundation for informed decision-making and strategic planning at both national and cross-border levels. By identifying knowledge gaps and opportunities for strengthening intersectoral linkages, the study will guide policymakers, water management authorities, and development organizations in implementing targeted interventions that promote regional cooperation. At the national level, results will support sectoral integration within each country, while at the regional level, they will facilitate cross-border collaboration and the development of joint projects that align with the BPME's vision of sustainable development and peacebuilding through water resource management.

1.2 Objectives

The WEFE Baseline Study aims to:

- Foster cooperation and coordinated management among the water, energy, food, and ecosystem sectors under the WEFE Nexus concept.
- Ensure sustainable use of interconnected resources for present and future generations.
- Create an overview of the WEFE Nexus in Iran, Iraq, Syria, and Türkiye.
- Systematically assess the current state of these sectors.
- Provide recommendations to enhance regional cooperation and sustainable development in the study countries (Iran, Iraq, Syria, and Türkiye).

National Assessment of WEFE Sectors in the Study Countries

1.3 Iran

1.3.1 Country Overview

Apart from coastal areas in the north and some western regions, the Islamic Republic of Iran (Figure 1) has a predominantly arid to semi-arid climate having hot and dry weather in the summer and very cold winters. With an area of 1.65 million km² and a 2400 km coastline, Iran lies between the Arabian Gulf and the Caspian Sea. Iran has direct national borders with 7 countries: Armenia, Afghanistan, Azerbaijan, Iraq, Pakistan, Turkmenistan, and Türkiye. Iran is considered one of the highest countries in the world with an average elevation of 1300 m above sea level. As of 2022, the population in Iran is about 88.5 million with a 1.24% growth rate⁶. From 13 million in 1956, the population has quintupled over the last 60 years. By 2050, projections indicate that this number will rise to 103 million⁷. Approximately 74.9% of people, primarily in the north and west, reside in urban areas; this number has been rising over the previous fifty years. The cities of Tehran, Mashhad, Tabriz, Esfahan, and Shiraz are the most populous in the nation. The country's arid regions are largely uninhabited.

⁶ MacroTrends. (n.d.). Iran population 1950-2024. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/IRN/iran/population#:~:text=The%20population%20of%20Iran%20in,a%200.73%25%20increase%20from%202020.>

⁷ Statistical Centre of Iran. (2019). Statistical yearbook 2018-2019. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://www.amar.org.ir/english/Iran-Statistical-Yearbook/Statistical-Yearbook-2018-2019>

Figure 1 Iran country map (source: Worldometer⁸)

The average annual temperature in Iran is between 22°C and 26°C. Average annual rainfall is about 240 mm in most of the inland areas and can reach 500-1800 mm in the plains surrounding the Caspian Sea. Iran receives over 70% of its annual rainfall between November and March, with June through August frequently experiencing dry conditions. Rainfall amounts differ from year to year and from season to season. Particularly during the winter, concentrated periods of precipitation can lead to strong storms that cause erosion and floods. There is a tiny region by the Caspian Sea with a completely distinct climate. Rainfall occurs year-round; however, it is at its highest in late summer and early winter⁹.

⁸Worldometer. (n.d.). World map. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from https://www.worldometers.info/world-map/#google_vignette

⁹World Bank. (n.d.). Climate change knowledge portal: Iran (Islamic Rep.). Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/iran-islamic-rep>

1.3.2 WEFE Situation

1. Water

a. Water Resources (Internal and Cross boundary)

Iran has a total renewable water resources of 155,140 million cubic meters per year, as of 2020, equating to 1,570 cubic meters per capita annually. Table 1 below details the water resources in Iran.

Table 1 Water resources in Iran in 2020 (source: AQUASTAT¹⁰)

Water resource	Value (MCM/Year)
Total renewable groundwater	49,300
Total renewable surface water	105,840
Total renewable water resources	155,140
Desalinated water produced	120
Treated municipal wastewater	42% of the 4.61 BCM of municipal wastewater treated annually ¹¹ .

Figure 2 The 6 Catchments in Iran (Fanack Water¹²)

Iran consists of six main hydrological catchments (Figure 2):

- Caspian Sea Catchment (Mazandaran), which covers the northern slopes of Alborz and Zagros.
- The Persian Gulf (Arabian Gulf) and Oman Sea Catchment, which covers south western slopes.

¹⁰ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2020). AQUASTAT country profile – Iran (Islamic Republic of). Retrieved from <https://www.fao.org/aquastat/en/countries-and-basins/country-profiles/country/IRN/index.html>

¹¹ Akbarzadeh, A., Valipour, A., Meshkati, S., & Hamnabard, N. (2023). Municipal Wastewater Treatment in Iran: Current Situation, Barriers and Future Policies. *Journal of Advances in Environmental Health Research*. <https://doi.org/10.34172/jaehr.2023.08>.

¹² Fanack, (2022) Water, Shared water resources in Iran,. Retrieved from <https://water.fanack.com/iran/shared-water-resources-in-iran/>

- Lake Urmia Catchment, which covers slopes of mountains that border Iran and Türkiye.
- The Central Catchment, which covers all of central Iran.
- The Eastern Border Catchment, which covers slopes bordering Afghanistan.
- The Sarakhs Catchment, which borders Pakistan.

The Helmand River basin (which is part of the Eastern Border Catchment) serves as a vital water resource for both Iran and Afghanistan. Originating in the mountains of Afghanistan, the river runs approximately 1,100 kilometers before reaching Hamun Lake in Iran. The basin supports a large portion of agricultural production, and provides water for drinking, domestic use, livestock, wildlife, and industry. Spanning an area of around 400,000 square kilometers, the basin is 81.4% located in Afghanistan, 3.6% in Pakistan, and 15% in Iran¹³. As one of the few permanent rivers in the region, the Helmand River plays a crucial role in sustaining water needs for Iran and Afghanistan.

In 2017, Iran's internal renewable water resources were estimated at 128.5 billion cubic meters (BCM), including 8.5 BCM sourced from transboundary resources¹⁴. Afghanistan contributes surface water to Iran through the Helmand River at a rate of 6.7 km³ per year. At the border with Azerbaijan, the Aras River provides an estimated flow of 4.63 km³ per year. The total estimated surface run-off to the sea and neighboring countries is about 55.9 km³ per year. Of this, approximately 7.5 km³ per year flows towards Azerbaijan via the Aras River, and 10 km³ per year flows towards Iraq through the Tigris River tributaries. Additionally, the Karun River flows into Iraq at a rate of about 24.7 km³ per year; however, since this occurs just before it empties into the sea, it is not considered a direct inflow into Iraq¹⁵. Table 2 illustrates the surface and transboundary groundwater resources.

Regarding municipal wastewater, only about 42% of Iran's 4.61 BCB of wastewater is collected and treated. Iran's municipal wastewater treatment is primarily (more than 60%) handled by the traditional activated sludge process. It is estimated to reuse roughly 55% of treated municipal effluent, with the agricultural sector receiving particular attention. In terms of electricity consumption, the treatment of municipal wastewater uses 0.1% (241 million kWh/y) of the nation's total electricity consumption¹⁶.

Iran faces groundwater depletion, with a cumulative deficit of 130 billion cubic meters due to overextraction and recurring droughts, exemplified by declining water levels and quality in regions like the Isfahan-Borkhar aquifer¹⁷. Desalination, producing 120 million cubic meters annually, offers a solution, especially in southern regions, where solar and wind energy potential can power sustainable desalination plants, reducing environmental impact¹⁸. Groundwater pumping

¹³ Goes, B., Howarth, S., Wardlaw, R., Hancock, I., & Parajuli, U. (2016). Integrated water resources management in an insecure river basin: a case study of Helmand River Basin, Afghanistan. *International Journal of Water Resources Development*, 32, 25 - 3. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07900627.2015.1012661>.

¹⁴ Fanack, (2022) Water, Shared water resources in Iran,. Retrieved from <https://water.fanack.com/iran/shared-water-resources-in-iran/>

¹⁵ AQUASTAT, 2008. Country Fact Sheet: Iran. FAO's global information system on water and agriculture. Available at www.fao.org/nr/water/aquastat/countries_regions/irn/index.stm.

¹⁶ Akbarzadeh, Abbas & Valipour, Alireza & Meshkati, Seyed & Hamnabard, Nazanin. (2023). Municipal Wastewater Treatment in Iran: Current Situation, Barriers and Future Policies. *Journal of Advances in Environmental Health Research*. 11. 60-71. [10.34172/jaehr.2023.08](https://doi.org/10.34172/jaehr.2023.08).

¹⁷ Samani, S. (2021). Analyzing the Groundwater Resources Sustainability Management plan in Iran through Comparative Studies. *Groundwater for Sustainable Development*, 12, 100521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GSD.2020.100521>.

¹⁸ Gorjian, S., & Ghobadian, B. (2015). Solar desalination: A sustainable solution to water crisis in Iran. *Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 48, 571-584. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2015.04.009>.

contributes 3.6% of Iran's carbon emissions, underscoring the need for renewable energy integration in water management systems to address the pressure of both water and energy use¹⁹.

Table 2 Surface and groundwater resources and the corresponding transboundary countries²⁰

	Water Resource	Shared Countries
Surface Water Resources	Aras	Türkiye, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran
	Sari Su and Ghare Su	Türkiye, Iran
	Nihling	Pakistan, Iran
	Helmand	Afghanistan, Iran
	Harirud , Atark and Northern Khorasan	Turkmenistan, Iran
Groundwater Aquifers	Leninak-Shiraks Aquifer	Azerbaijan, Armenia, Iran, Türkiye
	Nakhichevan/Larijan and Djebail Aquifer	Azerbaijan, Armenia, Iran
	Lenkoran/Astara	Azerbaijan, Iran
	Taurus-Zagros	Iran, Iraq, Türkiye
	Sarakhs	Turkmenistan, Iran
	AghDarband	Afghanistan, Iran
	Janat Abad-Saleh Abad	Afghanistan, Turkmenistan, Iran
	Fariman-Torbatjam	Afghanistan, Iran
	Taybad	Afghanistan, Iran
	Karet	Afghanistan, Iran

b. Water Use by sector.

The demand for water in Iran comes from three sectors: agricultural, domestic (urban) and industrial. Water use in the agricultural sector is substantially subsidised by the government (accounting for more than 90% of the water use), resulting in much lower prices than the actual cost of provision. These subsidies manifest through mechanisms such as reduced tariffs and subsidized energy for water extraction and irrigation. In the agricultural sector, water is extremely inexpensive, often nearly free, which diminishes incentives for conservation and efficient usage. Surface water supplies 60% of urban needs, while groundwater resources supply approximately 40%. Approximately 99.4% of the nation is covered by the water supply network. Approximately 100 BCM (Billion Cubic Meters) of water is currently extracted for agricultural (92%), municipal (7%), and industrial use (1%) –Figure 3 below – of which 40% come from surface water sources, 58.8% from groundwater sources, and 0.2% come from desalinated water. In Iran, agriculture uses most of the water, using over 42.43 billion cubic metres in 2023²¹. Groundwater resources provide more than 43% of agricultural demand and 62% of all irrigated lands (The distinction between agricultural demand and irrigated lands lies in the scope of water use: "agricultural demand" refers to all water used in agriculture, including for irrigation, livestock, and ancillary activities like food processing,

¹⁹ Caldera, U., Bogdanov, D., Fasihi, M., Aghahosseini, A., & Breyer, C. (2019). Securing future water supply for Iran through 100% renewable energy powered desalination. *International Journal of Sustainable Energy Planning and Management*, 23. <https://doi.org/10.5278/IJSEPM.3305>.

²⁰ International Groundwater Resources Assessment Centre (IGRAC). (2021). *Transboundary aquifers of the world: Update 2021*. Delft, Netherlands: IGRAC. Retrieved from <https://ggis.un-igrac.org/view/tba>

²¹ Khorsandi, M., Omidi, T., & van Oel, P. (2023). Water-related limits to growth for agriculture in Iran. *Heliyon*, 9(5), e16132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16132>

while "irrigated lands" refer specifically to water used directly for irrigation on farmland.). The total withdrawal of surface and groundwater resources represents about 83% of the total renewable water resources. The use of unconventional water resources is limited to the use of desalinated water in petrochemical plants in the Gulf, and use of some treated wastewater indirectly for agricultural purposes.²²

Figure 3 Water use by sector in Iran (source: Aquastat²³)

c. Water risks and challenges in Iran

Water resources management is a difficult issue in Iran because of a number of issues, including inadequate monitoring of pollution sources and water bodies, a lack of appropriate cooperation among significant governmental and non-governmental organisations, and inadequate guidelines and standards. Furthermore, periodic droughts and climate change may make water resources less plentiful and of lower quality.²⁵

One of the most pressing issues currently and in the future, on an institutional, legislative, and structural level is solving problems relating to the declining water quality due to the increase in agricultural water use. The use of agricultural water has increased significantly throughout the years. Iran predominantly uses traditional surface irrigation methods, which are often inefficient, with water losses due to evaporation, seepage, and runoff. Modern irrigation techniques, such as drip and sprinkler systems, are limited, with estimates suggesting irrigation efficiency across the country is only around 40%²⁴. As a result, in 2020, the total volume of return flows and wastewaters was more than a third of the total volume of renewable water. Moreover, the pressure increases on water

²²Fanack Water. (2022). Water use in Iran. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://water.fanack.com/iran/water-uses-in-iran/>

²³ AQUASTAT, 2008. Country Fact Sheet: Iran. FAO's global information system on water and agriculture. Available at www.fao.org/nr/water/aquastat/countries_regions/irn/index.stm.

²⁴ Karimi, P., Qureshi, A., Bahramloo, R., & Molden, D. (2012). Reducing carbon emissions through improved irrigation and groundwater management: A case study from Iran. *Fuel and Energy Abstracts*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AGWAT.2011.09.001>.

demand due to the increase in the total area of agricultural lands. Multiple impacts affect the overall water risk in Iran such as²⁵:

- Impact on river discharge: The last 20 years have seen a notable decrease in river discharges, according to data gathered from hydrometric stations. Iran's rivers discharge measured over a long period of time is approximately 89 billion cubic metres. Between 2005 and 2013, this value dropped to 53 billion cubic metres, a 42% decrease.
- Impact on groundwater resources: In the last 40 years, there have been 300 aquifers classified as forbidden (aquifers from which water withdrawal is not permitted). Previously, in the 1980s, there were only 25 such aquifers. This significant increase is primarily due to over-abstraction of groundwater for agricultural, industrial, and domestic use, exceeding the natural recharge capacity of these aquifers. Excessive pumping has led to severe depletion of groundwater levels, averaging a decline of 49 cm annually across the country²⁶.
- Land Subsidence: Subsidence, driven by factors like aquifer compaction, hydro-compaction, and sinkholes, is a significant issue in Iran. Over-extraction of groundwater is the primary cause, exacerbated by expanding land and water resource development. Subsidence leads to permanent inundation, increased flooding, surface ruptures, decreased aquifer storage, and infrastructure instability.
- Water use conflicts: Groundwater is a common resource, often leading to competing interests among users. Unregulated extraction from numerous illegal wells, coupled with political pressure for new well approvals in overdrawn aquifers, exacerbates aquifer depletion. Overdrafts also impact river discharges, intensifying conflicts during droughts.
- Decreasing discharge of wells: Declining groundwater tables reduce well discharge, prompting deeper drilling, which shortens well lifespans and increases energy use. Saline water intrusion further damages wells, as seen in Kordkuy, where 60% of drinking wells are affected by seawater. Despite the rise in well numbers over the last decade, groundwater extraction is limited by falling water tables in most aquifers.

Water sectors in Iran face certain limitations including:²⁷

- Low precipitation rates and their uneven distribution.
- Population growth and distribution.
- The reduction of water quality due to industrial pollution.
- The increase in water demand and the discharge of polluted water to other neighboring countries.
- The misuse of water in dams due to inefficient irrigation systems.

²⁵A. Moridi, "State of Water Resources in Iran," *International Journal of Hydrology*, vol. 1, no. 4, Nov. 2017, doi: 10.15406/ijh.2017.01.00021.

²⁶Noori, R., Maghrebi, M., Mirchi, A., Tang, Q., Bhattarai, R., Sadegh, M., Noury, M., Haghighi, A., Kløve, B., & Madani, K. (2021). Anthropogenic depletion of Iran's aquifers. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2024221118>.

²⁷K. Madani, "Water management in Iran: what is causing the looming crisis?," *Journal of Environmental Studies and Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 315–328, Aug. 2014, doi: 10.1007/s13412-014-0182-z.

2. Energy

a. Supply

In 2021, Iran's total energy supply was 3,420,886.11 GWh, with 2.2% of this supply being imported from Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan²⁸. Table 3 and **Error! Reference source not found.** below detail the energy supplied by resource.

Table 3 Energy supply per sector in 2021 – Iran (source: IEA²⁹)

Resource	Energy Supply (GWh)	%
Coal	16,044.44	0.47
Natural gas	2,419,251.11	70.72
Nuclear	9,371.39	0.27
Hydro	15,886.94	0.46
Wind, solar, etc.	1,378.61	0.04
Biofuels and waste	6,003.06	0.18
Oil	952,950.56	27.86
Total	3,420,886.00	100

Figure 4 Energy supplied per resource in Iran in 2021 (source: IEA²⁹)

b. Demand

In 2021, Iran's total energy consumption was 2,598,999.44 GWh²⁹, the Table 4 and Figure 5 below details the energy consumption per sector.

²⁸U.S. Energy Information Administration. (2022). Iran. Retrieved July 3, 2024, from <https://www.eia.gov/international/analysis/country/IRN>

²⁹International Energy Agency. (n.d.). Iran - Countries & regions. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://www.iea.org/countries/iran>

Table 4 Energy consumption per sector in 2021 – Iran (source: IEA²⁹)

Sector	Energy Consumption (GWh)	%
Industry	674,868.06	25.97
Transport	541,377.22	20.83
Residential	766,054.44	29.47
Commercial and public services	137,808.33	5.30
Agriculture / forestry	109,002.22	4.19
Non-specified	5,099.17	0.20
Non-energy use	364,790.00	14.04
Total	2,598,999.44	100.00

Figure 5 Energy Consumption by Sector in Iran in 2021 (source: IEA²⁹)

c. Energy risks in Iran

Iran's energy sector faces many risks that affect its energy security, encompassing infrastructure, and geopolitical challenges. These risks significantly affect the country's ability to maintain a stable and sustainable energy supply. Infrastructure risks include outdated technology, maintenance issues, and susceptibility to natural disasters, which can disrupt energy supply. Geopolitical risks primarily encompass the economic sanctions, imposed primarily by the United States, have severely impacted Iran's ability to export oil and gas, access international markets, and attract foreign investment. Moreover, Water scarcity, desertification, and extreme weather events can impact energy production, particularly hydropower and agriculture-based bioenergy³⁰.

³⁰Padam, S. S. (2017). Analysis of the strengthening of oil and gas sector of Iran's energy system in terms of continuity of production. *Iranian Energy Economics*, 5(20), 35–78. <https://doi.org/10.22054/jiee.2017.7311>

3. Food

a. Supply

The food supply system in Iran is a complex structure influenced by a range of factors, including local production capabilities, import requirements, economic policies, and geopolitical challenges. Iran's diverse geography and climate support a variety of agricultural activities. The country's agricultural sector is vital for providing food, supporting rural livelihoods, and contributing to the national economy. Iran is divided into several climatic zones, each suitable for different types of crops and livestock. Arable land in Iran is 15,699,000 ha, while permanent crops take up 1,891,000 ha of land area, and permanent meadows and pastures make up 29,477,000 ha^{31,32}.

Wheat and Barley are the staple grains produced extensively across the country, particularly in the northern and western regions, further, 14,812,659 tons of cereals were produced in Iran in 2022, with a harvested area of 8,107,539 hectares³³. Iran produces a wide range of fruits (e.g., apples, pomegranates, grapes, and citrus fruits) and vegetables (e.g., tomatoes, cucumbers, potatoes). The central and southern regions, with their warm climates, are particularly suitable for fruit production. Despite significant local production, Iran relies heavily on food imports to meet its overall consumption needs, especially for commodities not sufficiently produced domestically. The reliance on imports has grown due to several factors, including population growth, changing dietary patterns, and occasional agricultural shortfalls. Key imported commodities include wheat, corn, rice, and oilseeds, which are not produced in sufficient quantities domestically. For instance, Iran imported about 50% of its wheat and over 90% of its oilseeds in 2022. The primary sources of these imports are Russia, India, Türkiye, and Brazil, reflecting Iran's need to bridge the gap between local production and consumption requirements³⁴.

b. Demand

Food consumption in Iran is deeply influenced by traditional dietary habits, driven primarily by cultural factors, accessibility, and historical patterns of agriculture³⁵. Staples such as bread and rice are central to the Iranian diet. However, consumption patterns reflect certain food groups' overconsumption and others' underconsumption. While Iran focuses on fulfilling domestic food demand, it also exports certain agricultural products, leveraging its diverse agroclimatic conditions. Iran exports a variety of processed foods, including saffron, pistachios, dates, and dried fruits. These products are in high demand in international markets due to their quality and traditional processing methods³⁶. In the first five months of 2024, Iran exported 2.657 million tons of agricultural products valued at \$1.453 billion. Key exports include pistachios (\$352 million), tomatoes (\$177 million),

³¹Floor, W. M. (1983). The creation of the food administration in Iran. *Iranian Studies*, 16(3–4), 199–227. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00210868308701614>

³² AQUASTAT. (2008). Country fact sheet: Iran. FAO's global information system on water and agriculture. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://www.fao.org/aquastat/en/countries-and-basins/country-profiles/country/IRN>

³³ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (n.d.). FAOSTAT. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#country/102>

³⁴ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2023). World food and agriculture – Statistical yearbook 2023 [FAO eBooks]. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc8166en>

³⁵ Sobhani, S. R., Omidvar, N., Abdollahi, Z., & Jawaldehy, A. A. (2021). Shifting to a sustainable dietary pattern in Iranian population: current evidence and future directions. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2021.789692>

³⁶ Abdi F, Atarodi Z, Mirmiran P, Esteki T. Surveying Global and Iranian Food Consumption Patterns: A Review of the Literature. *JABS* 2015; 5 (2) :159-167. <http://jabs.fums.ac.ir/article-1-677-en.html>

apples (\$111 million), and dates, with Iran producing over 950,000 tons annually, primarily exporting to countries like Russia, Malaysia, Indonesia, India, and China^{37,38}.

The average daily caloric intake per person in Iran is higher than recommended levels. The typical caloric intake ranges from 2,800 to 3,200 kcal/day, which exceeds the global average of 2,400 kcal/day recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO). This excess is primarily due to the high consumption of carbohydrates and fats. Meat consumption, primarily chicken and lamb, is substantial but varies significantly between urban and rural areas. The average meat consumption is around 35 kg per person annually. Fish consumption remains low, averaging 6-8 kg per person yearly. Dairy intake is lower than recommended, with milk and dairy products consumption averaging 120 liters per person annually, compared to the recommended 180 liters. Fruit and vegetable consumption is also lower than global recommendations. An Iranian consumes about 120 kg of fruits and vegetables annually, whereas the WHO recommends at least 150 kg³⁶.

c. Food security

Food availability in Iran is ensured through domestic production and imports. Self-sufficiency levels vary significantly across different food commodities. For instance, Iran is about 90% self-sufficient in wheat production. However, water scarcity, land degradation, and climatic variability pose significant risks to food production. Approximately 29% of households in rural areas experience food insecurity, with food access heavily impacted by inflation and reduced purchasing power³⁹. Iran's food self-sufficiency has improved for some products but remains vulnerable, requiring effective policy measures to bolster resilience against environmental and economic shocks⁴⁰. Improving agricultural productivity, such as adopting modern farming techniques, better water management, and crop diversification, is essential to enhance food availability. Income levels, employment, and inflation influence economic access to food. High inflation rates, partly driven by economic sanctions, have eroded purchasing power, making it difficult for low-income households to afford sufficient and nutritious food. Social safety nets, such as subsidies and food assistance programs, are critical in improving access to food for vulnerable populations⁴¹.

Government policies and governance play a vital role in ensuring food security. Iran has implemented various policies to support agricultural development, enhance food production, and improve food distribution. These include subsidies for farmers, investment in agricultural research and development, and initiatives to improve water use efficiency. These policies include guaranteed minimum prices, subsidies, and cheap credit for farmers⁴². The government has developed a

³⁷ Tasnim News Agency. (2024). Iran exports \$1.5 billion of agricultural products in 5 months. Tasnim News Agency. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://www.tasnimnews.com/en/news/2024/08/25/3147578/iran-exports-1-5-billion-of-agricultural-products-in-5-months>

³⁸ Hashem, M. a. A. (2024). Iran reports major rise in agriculture exports in 5 months. Mehr News Agency. <https://en.mehrnews.com/news/220138/Iran-reports-major-rise-in-agriculture-exports-in-5-months>

³⁹ Hejazi, J., & Emamgholipour, S. (2020). The Effects of the Re-imposition of US Sanctions on Food Security in Iran. *International Journal of Health Policy and Management*, 11, 651 - 657. <https://doi.org/10.34172/ijhpm.2020.207>.

⁴⁰ Salami, H., Mohtashami, T., & Naeini, M. S. N. (2014). Prospects for food Self-Sufficiency in Iran in 2025. In Oxford University Press eBooks (pp. 115–134). <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199361786.003.0005>

⁴¹ Ghalibaf, M. B., Gholami, M., & Mohammadian, N. (2022). Stability of food security in Iran: Challenges and ways forward: A narrative review. *Iranian Journal of Public Health*, 51(12), 1777–1787. <https://doi.org/10.18502/ijph.v51i12.11456>

⁴² Dehnavi, S., Knerr, B., & Liaghati, H. (2010). Food security versus water security: A policy-related study about Iran. ResearchGate. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/264471517_Food_security_versus_water_security_A_policy_related_study_about_Iran

national document for food and nutrition security, emphasizing sustainable food supply, food safety, and nutrition⁴³.

4. Ecosystems in Iran

Iran's ecosystems are diverse and rich, encompassing habitats ranging from deserts to forests, each supporting unique flora and fauna. However, the country's ecosystems face significant pressures from human activities, climate change, and other environmental challenges, necessitating robust conservation efforts. Iran is home to unique ecosystems characterized by distinct biodiversity and environmental significance. These ecosystems include marshlands, forests, deserts, and mountain ranges, each playing a crucial role in the ecological balance and supporting a variety of plant and animal species⁴⁴.

Iran's groundcover was mapped in the Figure 6 below, showcasing 13 classes of groundcover with an area of about 162,629,464 ha.⁴⁵ Marshlands, more specifically the Al Hawizah Marshes, are a unique feature of Iran's ecosystem. Due to modern construction and agriculture, these marshlands have undergone significant changes over the past three decades, including drying due to dam construction. This has greatly affected wildlife in these areas, including 40 bird species, as the marshlands are an important site for bird migration. The drying of marshlands has also harmed fisheries impacted the livelihoods of neighboring communities.^{46,47}

⁴³ Damari, B., Abdollahi, Z., Hajifaraji, M., & Rezazadeh, A. (2018). Nutrition and food security policy in the Islamic Republic of Iran: Situation analysis and roadmap towards 2021. *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*, 24(2), 177–188. <https://doi.org/10.26719/2018.24.2.177>

⁴⁴ Jowkar, H., Ostrowski, S., Tahbaz, M., & Zahler, P. (2016). The conservation of biodiversity in Iran: Threats, challenges, and hopes. *Iranian Studies*, 49(6), 1065–1077. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00210862.2016.1241602>

⁴⁵ Ansari, A., Ghorbanpour, M., Kazemi, A., & Kariman, K. (2023). Ecological assessment of Iran's terrestrial biomes for wildlife conservation. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-45120-4>

⁴⁶ Partow, H., & United Nations Environment Programme. (2001). *The Mesopotamian marshlands: Demise of an ecosystem*. Geneva, Switzerland: United Nations Environment Programme.

⁴⁷ Bijnens, T. (2020). The border wetlands of Iran-Iraq: An environmental crisis with regional consequences. Save the Tigris Foundation. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://savethetigris.org/the-border-wetlands-of-iran-iraq-an-environmental-crisis-with-regional-consequences/>

Figure 6 Iran's landcover map (Ansari et al. 2023⁴⁵)

Iran also faces numerous environmental challenges that threaten its ecosystems and the well-being of its population. These challenges include pollution, deforestation, water scarcity, and climate change. Pollution from industrial activities and urban runoff degrades air, water, and soil quality, harming wildlife and reducing biodiversity. Deforestation leads to habitat loss, soil erosion, and desertification, further disrupting ecological balance. Water scarcity stresses aquatic ecosystems, affecting both freshwater species and the overall health of rivers and lakes. Climate change exacerbates these issues through increased temperatures, altered precipitation patterns, and more frequent extreme weather events, intensifying droughts and impacting agricultural productivity. Each of these issues is interconnected, creating a complex web of environmental pressures requiring comprehensive strategies.⁴⁸

1.3.3 National Policies and Legal Framework

1.3.3.1 Water Sector Institutional frameworks

The main ministries overseeing the water sector in Iran are the Department of Environment, the Ministry of Agriculture, and the Ministry of Energy, which has the dual responsibility of overseeing the energy and water resources sectors. Managing water resources in Iran presents numerous challenges, including limited authority of the Iran Department of Environment (IDOE) and Ministry of Energy (MOE) in regulating water withdrawal and pollution sources, particularly when the pollution originates from governmental sectors. Although the MOE controls the water sector, its limited regulatory authority over water management, especially in the context of environmental protection, creates a conflict of interest. This is because the MOE's primary focus is on water supply and infrastructure development rather than environmental conservation, leading to insufficient enforcement of regulations that protect water quality. The overlapping responsibilities and lack of a

⁴⁸Tahbaz, M. (2016). Environmental challenges in today's Iran. *Iranian Studies*, 49(6), 943–961. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00210862.2016.1241624>

clear, unified mandate between the MOE and IDOE undermine effective water governance, allowing pollution and over-extraction to persist unchecked. Additionally, uneven population distribution and economic activities, insufficient monitoring of pollution sources and water bodies, lack of effective cooperation among relevant governmental and non-governmental entities, and inadequate guidelines and standards further complicate the situation. Moreover, the impacts of climate change and recurrent droughts can exacerbate the quantity and quality issues of water resources. According to water laws in Iran, the assessment and development of water resources are directly overseen by the ministries shown in Table 5^{49,50}.

*Table 5. Ministries overseeing the water sector in Iran*⁵⁰

Ministry	Description
Ministry of Energy	Established in 1936 with the initial mandate of providing electricity and managing water resources, its responsibilities encompass energy supply, water services, and the development of irrigation infrastructure. The Water Affairs Directorate within this ministry supervises water resource management. This Directorate comprises several departments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Resources Management Company (WRMC): Oversees all water sectors within the Ministry of Energy, excluding rural and urban drinking water distribution. • Provincial Water Authorities (PWAs): Responsible for water management at the provincial level, including the development and operation of irrigation and sewage networks. Drinking water distribution within provinces is managed by water companies. Operations and maintenance (O&M) companies are responsible for managing modern irrigation and sewage networks.
Ministry of Agriculture	Tasked with supervising the development of rainfed and irrigated crops. While the Ministry of Energy oversees water management from river sources to secondary irrigation channels, the Ministry of Agriculture supervises groundwater aquifers, tertiary, and quaternary canals. Additionally, it oversees the development (including extension) of farms and irrigation techniques regulated and managed by agricultural organizations at the provincial level and the General Directorate of Infrastructure Affairs within the Ministry of Agriculture.
Iran Department of Environment	Responsible for formulating environmental protection policies, laws, instructions, and regulations to assess the environmental impacts of social and economic development projects (including climate change issues), particularly irrigation and water energy projects (like hydropower), and monitoring their implementation.

Several companies/departments that are associated with the water sector fall under the authority of the ministry of energy, there are as follows:

1. Production management and procurement of water and electricity company (SATKAB)

⁴⁹ Moridi, A. (2017). State of water resources in Iran. *International Journal of Hydrology*, 1(4). <https://doi.org/10.15406/ijh.2017.01.00021>

⁵⁰ Mohajeri, S. (2020). Water management in Iran: Appearance and reality. In S. Mohajeri, L. Horlemann, A. A. Besalatpour, & W. Raber (Eds.), *Standing up to climate change* (pp. 45–60). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-50684-1_3

2. National water and wastewater engineering company
3. Iran water resources management company

In addition to these ministries, the Ministry of Health and Medical Education is responsible for monitoring the physical, chemical, biological, and bacteriological quality of drinking water from its source to the point of consumption⁵¹.

1.3.3.2 Energy Sector Institutional Frameworks

The main ministries in charge of energy sector in Iran are the ministry of Energy, the ministry of petroleum, and the organization of renewable energy. One of the primary challenges identified in Iran's energy governance is the lack of integration in energy planning and management between the Ministry of Energy and Ministry of Power, as well as the concentration of regulatory and management functions within these two ministries⁵².

Subsequently, a specialized panel consisting of experts in various fields related to energy, including energy economics, upstream and downstream oil and gas, electricity, energy regulation, energy governance, and oil and gas rights, held over 110 sessions⁵³ to identify necessary reforms for establishing an efficient Ministry of Energy. These reforms were then discussed and validated in another panel of experts.

The proposed reforms include the appointment of a Deputy for Energy Affairs, establishment of the Strategic Energy Organization, refinement of the Supreme Energy Council law, compilation of a comprehensive energy law by the Strategic Energy Organization with the aim of reforming the energy governance system, and implementation of this comprehensive energy law by the Strategic Energy Organization⁵⁴.

Energy Sector Institutional Framework in Iran was divided as below. (Table 6):

Table 6 Institutions overseeing the energy sector in Iran

Ministry	Description
Management and Planning Organization (MPO)	This organization operates under the auspices of the President's Office. MPO prepares the Five-Year Development Plans (FYDP) which encompasses the national development programs and policies. The FYDPs require the approval of the Cabinet and the Islamic Assembly (Parliament). The Annual General Government Budgets (AGGBs) are also developed by MPO in the context of the FYDPs. The budget documents also require the approval of both the Cabinet and the Islamic Assembly.
Ministry of Energy (MOE)	The ministry is responsible for policymaking and management of generation, transmission and distribution of electricity TAVANIR (Generation, Transmission and Distribution of Electricity Company) and its regional subsidiary companies: the Regional Electricity Generation Companies and Regional Electricity Distributing Companies are responsible for generation, transmission and distribution

⁵¹ Fanack Water. (2022). Water management in Iran. Fanack Water. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from https://water.fanack.com/iran/water-management-in-iran/#_ftnref5

⁵² Climate Action Tracker. (2023). Policies & action. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://climateactiontracker.org/>

⁵³ Akbari, M., Souhankar, A., & Heidari, H. (2021). The roadmap to establish the Ministry of Energy in Iran. *Rahyaft*, 31(2), 87–104. <https://doi.org/10.22034/rahyaft.2021.10884.1267>

⁵⁴ Emerald Insight. (2023). Iran's approach to energy policy towards 2040: A participatory scenario method. *Future Studies*, 10(3). <https://doi.org/10.1108/fs-11-2021-0228>

Organization for Renewable Energies (SUNA)	The organization was established in 1995 as an affiliate under MOE's Deputy for energy Affairs. Since 2003, SUNA is responsible for development of renewable energies within the MOE, SUNA operates under the auspices of TAVANIR and through its departments that deal with solar, hydrogen, geothermal, and wind energy
Ministry of Petroleum (MOP)	The ministry is responsible for both policymaking and management of the oil and gas sector, management activities include production, refining, distribution, export and import of crude oil, gas and petroleum products as well as petrochemical industries management of upstream and downstream activities is mainly carried.

In addition to the above, other public sector bodies active in energy sector including:

- Ministry of Agriculture Jihad (MOA) which assists in the implementation of small-scale energy projects, such as solar water heaters, in rural areas.
- Agriculture Bank, which in addition to its main role as a specialized banking system, performs a mediation role in transferring the subsidized funds provided by the MOP to beneficiaries of the “electrification of agriculture wells” program.
- The Atomic Energy Organization helps to carry out research projects on wind potentials and the like in addition to its own research.

1.3.3.3 Food and Agriculture institutional frameworks

The governance structures within the agricultural sector encompass various institutions, such as the Ministry of Agriculture Jihad (MOAJ) and the Department of Environment, which serve as key stakeholders of the Country Programming Framework. These entities advocate for agriculture and rural development, contribute to food security, and address environmental protection concerns. Additionally, other relevant bodies, like the Ministry of Cooperation, Labor and Social Welfare and the Ministry of Health and Medical Education, play a role in food security, albeit without direct support from FAO. Unfortunately, governance in FAO-operated areas is marked by institutional and policy fragmentation, coordination issues, opaque decision-making processes, inefficiencies, inadequate accountability mechanisms, and high turnover rates, resulting in a loss of institutional knowledge.

While institutions in the country have a wealth of knowledge, expertise, and a broad network of research, training, and educational institutions, their ability to engage effectively with small-holder producers and grassroots communities is often limited. This gap is exacerbated by outdated management practices, which prevent the full utilization of these valuable resources and expertise⁵⁵.

Another set of national stakeholders comprises potential beneficiaries of development support, including various producer and consumer groups such as farmers, pastoralists, fishermen, providers of agricultural inputs, non-farming agricultural production operators (processors), producer associations, cooperatives, informal groups, traders, retailers, larger-scale entrepreneurs, investors, mid-sized farmers, and special interest groups such as women, the elderly, and youth. These

⁵⁵World Food Programme. (2023). Islamic Republic of Iran interim country strategic plan (2023–2027). World Food Programme. <https://www.wfp.org/operations/ir02-islamic-republic-iran-interim-country-strategic-plan-2023-2027>

categories occasionally overlap, and the capacity of national institutions to engage some of these potential beneficiaries through their development initiatives is not always satisfactory.

1.3.3.4 Environmental Sector institutional frameworks

As per the 2005 division of the country, Iran comprises 31 provinces and 252 townships. Within each province, there exists a Department of the Environment (DoE) provincial directorate tasked with overseeing all facets of environmental protection and the execution of Department initiatives.

Established in March 1972, the Department of the Environment (DoE) is responsible for safeguarding and enhancing the environment, managing wildlife and fisheries in inland waters, overseeing hunting and fishing activities in inland waters, administering protected areas and wetlands, preventing pollution and environmental degradation, and establishing emission and quality standards and criteria for air, water, soil, wastes, and noise. The Department conducts extensive environmental studies and management projects, formulates regulations on habitat management, and has implemented environmental legislation addressing pollution.⁵⁶ DoE has four main divisions as the following:

1. Division of Education and Planning: this department consists of three bureaus:
 - a. Bureau of Environmental Education and Training
 - b. Bureau of Public Participation
 - c. Bureau of Planning and Information
2. Division of the Human Environment: this division consists of the following bureaus:
 - a. Bureau of Environmental Impact Assessment
 - b. Bureau of Air Pollution Control
 - c. Bureau of Water and Soil Pollution
 - d. Bureau of Laboratories
3. Division of the Natural Environment and Biodiversity: this division consists of the following units:
 - a. Bureau of the Legislation and Parliamentarian Affairs
 - b. Bureau of Budget and Organization
 - c. Directorate of the Financial Affairs and Auditing
 - d. Directorate of the Administration
 - e. Technical and Engineering Supervisory group.
4. Division of Administrative and Parliamentarian Affairs: this division consists of the following units:
 - a. Bureau of the Legislation and Parliamentarian Affairs
 - b. Bureau of Budget and Organization
 - c. Directorate of the Financial Affairs and Auditing
 - d. Directorate of the Administration
 - e. Technical and Engineering Supervisory

Other relevant institutions include:

- National Fisheries Organization (Shilat)
- Ministry of Water and Power
- Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources
- National Centre for Marine Science
- Tehran University
- University of Tabriz
- University of Shiraz

⁵⁶Convention on Migratory Species. (2005). National report for Central Asian Flyway meeting. Convention on Migratory Species. https://www.cms.int/saiga/sites/default/files/document/inf_04_9_Iran_0.pdf

1.3.3.5 Interlinkages and gaps

The interconnection between water and energy in Iran is profound, primarily due to the country's reliance on hydropower and the water-intensive nature of fossil fuel extraction and processing. Iran's energy production requires substantial water resources, particularly in the oil and gas sectors. Conversely, energy is critical for water extraction, treatment, and distribution. The construction of dams for hydroelectric power has also impacted water availability for agricultural and domestic uses, illustrating the need for integrated management approaches. Energy is vital for various stages of food production, from irrigation to processing and transportation. Iran's agricultural sector relies on energy for pumping water, mechanized farming, and producing fertilizers and pesticides. Rising energy costs can directly impact food prices and security. Moreover, the shift towards bioenergy can compete with food production for land and water resources, necessitating careful management to avoid negative impacts on food availability⁵⁷.

One of the primary gaps in Iran's WEFE nexus policies is the lack of integrated management frameworks that address the complex interdependencies between water, energy, food, and ecosystems. Although the Ministry of Energy manages water resources, the policies often lack coordination between different sectors, leading to inefficient management and conflicting objectives. Policies are often developed in silos, leading to conflicting objectives and inefficient resource use. For instance, water policies focused on maximizing agricultural output can conflict with energy policies promoting hydropower development. This conflict arises because diverting water for irrigation can reduce the amount available for hydropower, potentially leading to decreased energy production. Additionally, prioritizing water for agriculture can negatively impact ecosystems, which are also crucial for maintaining energy resources and overall environmental health. which can degrade ecosystems if not managed holistically⁵⁸.

1.3.4 Socio-Economic Situation

Iran hosts a population of over 88.4 million people, of which 51% of the population are male, and 49% are female. The majority of the population (69.8%) are between the ages of 15 and 64, while 23.2% are under the age of 15, and 7% are 65 or over, with a median age of 33.8 years. Iran faces a 0.88% population growth rate, with a concentration of population in the north, northwest, and west. Approximately 77.3% of the population is urban, with the majority in the capital Tehran.

Iran has a state-controlled economy with strong oil, agricultural, and service sectors. However, unemployment rate is at 9.1%, and poverty has risen due to recent large inflation, international sanctions, and investor uncertainty, where 21.9% of the population sitting under poverty line⁵⁹. Iran's employment is at 36.9% of the population, with 14.1% working in the agricultural sector, 33.9% working in industry, and 48.9% working in services.⁶⁰ Further data on the economic situation is listed in Table 7.

Table 7 Socio-Economic Indicators - Iran

⁵⁷International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas. (2023). Enhancing food security in Iran. International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas. <https://www.icarda.org/media/news/enhancing-food-security-iran>

⁵⁸International Food Policy Research Institute. (2018). Perspectives on Iran's environmental policy process: Issues and constraints. International Food Policy Research Institute. <https://cgspace.cgiar.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/a7dcd165-5ad6-4b96-9e2b-3453668a5d7b/content>

⁵⁹Macrotrends. (2022). Iran poverty rate. Macrotrends. <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/IRN/iran/poverty-rate>

⁶⁰International Labour Organization. (n.d.). Country profiles - Iran. International Labour Organization. https://ilostat.ilo.org/data/country-profiles/?ref_area=IRN

Indicator	Value ⁶¹
GDP (USD Billion)	413.49
GDP per Capita (USD)	5507.53
GDP from Agriculture (%)	11
GDP from Mining (%)	38
GDP from Services (%)	51
Inflation Rate (%)	30.9
Unemployment Rate (%)	8.6
Youth Unemployment Rate (%) - (<24 years)	22.5

1.3.5 Recommendations

This section is the author’s recommendations based on the analysis of the literature review summarized above.

- **Enhance Water Resource Management**

Iran needs to improve how it manages its water resources to face growing challenges like drought and pollution. One key step is to set up better systems to monitor pollution from farms and factories, and to ensure water use in agriculture is more efficient. Introducing modern irrigation methods and encouraging farmers to use drought-resistant crops can help reduce water wastage. It’s also important to develop policies that bring together water, agriculture, and energy management to ensure sustainable water use across all sectors.

Groundwater is another critical issue, as overuse has led to dropping water levels, making it harder for farmers and communities to access enough water. Strict regulations are needed to stop illegal well drilling, and techniques like artificial recharge should be used to help refill depleted aquifers. Additionally, creating systems to resolve conflicts over water use between different sectors, especially during droughts, can help ensure fair water distribution and reduce tensions.

- **Energy Sector Resilience**

Iran’s energy sector is at risk due to outdated infrastructure and challenges like sanctions and water scarcity. To improve energy security, the country should invest in upgrading its energy systems with more modern and efficient technologies that are less vulnerable to natural disasters and climate impacts. Shifting towards renewable energy sources like solar and wind, which use less water, will help reduce reliance on hydropower and fossil fuels, making the energy system more resilient.

Water is also a key factor in energy production, so it’s important that energy policies take water needs into account. Managing hydropower carefully, for example, will ensure that electricity production doesn’t compromise water availability for farming and households. Additionally, by collaborating with neighboring countries, Iran can reduce the negative effects of sanctions and ensure access to essential resources to maintain its energy systems.

⁶¹Trading Economics. (n.d.). Iran indicators. Trading Economics. <https://tradingeconomics.com/iran/indicators>

- Enhance Food Security

Improving food security in Iran requires better water management and more efficient farming practices. Using modern irrigation techniques and encouraging farmers to grow more drought-tolerant crops can help protect food production from the impacts of water scarcity. Reusing treated wastewater for farming is another way to reduce dependence on freshwater and make the agriculture sector more resilient.

Economic access to food is also a challenge, especially for vulnerable families affected by inflation. Expanding food assistance programs and supporting farmers with subsidies and credit can help ensure food availability. At the same time, agricultural policies must balance the need for increased food production with protecting water and environmental resources to ensure long-term sustainability.

- Ecosystems Preservation

Iran faces environmental challenges like pollution, deforestation, and water shortages that are harming its ecosystems. To protect the environment, stricter rules are needed to reduce pollution from industries and cities, improving the quality of the air, water, and soil. Restoring forests and protecting habitats is also essential to stop soil erosion and loss of biodiversity, both of which worsen the effects of desertification.

Water scarcity is particularly hard on Iran's ecosystems, especially rivers and lakes that support wildlife and agriculture. It's important to manage water use in a way that ensures enough water remains in natural ecosystems to support aquatic life and maintain biodiversity. This will help preserve the environment while also ensuring that Iran's natural resources continue to support its economy and people.

- Addressing Interlinkages and Gaps in the WEFE Nexus

Water, energy, food, and ecosystems are deeply connected in Iran, but current policies don't always reflect these interlinkages. Often, decisions are made in isolation, leading to conflicts. For example, water policies that prioritize agriculture can reduce the water available for hydropower, affecting energy production. Iran needs an integrated management approach that brings together all sectors to ensure resources are used efficiently and sustainably, without creating unintended problems in other areas.

Investing in research and data can help improve understanding of how water, energy, and food systems interact. This will allow for smarter decision-making and more balanced policies. Also, promoting renewable energy in agriculture, such as solar-powered irrigation, can reduce reliance on water-intensive energy sources and support the sustainability of the entire WEFE system.

1.4 Iraq

1.4.1 Country Overview

Iraq is a country that is in southwest Asia (Figure 7). Geographically, the Republic of Iraq is split into four areas: the Euphrates Rivers; the mountains to the east and north; the desert to the south and west; and the vast Mesopotamian alluvial plains of the Tigris. Due to the severe weather, more than 40% of the nation is covered in desert and has a low population. Ancient civilizations have flourished in Iraq historically due to the presence of the two rivers as the rivers provided for water which supported agriculture in addition to fishing from the rivers. However, due to recent changes in the water use and storage in Iraq and upstream countries, the rivers are facing tremendous pressures related to reduction in water quality and quantity, because of salinity, mainly in central and southern Iraq (in some areas groundwater has exceeded sea water salinity at 45 dS/m), there is a shortage of high-quality water in many regions of the nation⁶². Due to desertification and water scarcity brought on by variations in river flow, Iraq is particularly vulnerable to the negative effects of climate change. As of 2023, there are about 45.5 million people living in Iraq and spans an area of 435,048 square kilometers, resulting in a population density of 97.8 inhabitants per square kilometer. Of the total population, 30% of the population reside in rural areas, while 70% of the population live in urban areas. Iraq's economy is primarily driven by its gas and oil industry, with the agriculture sector coming in second. Syria borders Iraq on the west, Saudi Arabia on the south, Jordan on the southwest, the Gulf and Kuwait on the southeast, and Iran on the east. Baghdad is the capital and biggest city. The majority of Iraq's population is Arab (75-80%), but there are also Kurdish (15-20%), and other ethnicities (5%), including Turkmen, Assyrians, Armenians, Yazidis, Mandaeans, Persians, and Shabakis, along with a similarly varied topography and fauna⁶³.

⁶²Falahi, A., & Qureshi, A. S. (2012). Relationship between groundwater table depth, groundwater quality, soil salinity and crop production. Iraq. <https://mel.cgiar.org/reporting/downloadmelspace/hash/ba313083d887a0b675ea4f793c936c06/v/945afd62b6d8d755aaadfcdfc93aa04>

⁶³Worldometer. (2024). Iraq population (2024). Worldometer. <https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/iraq-population/>

Figure 7 Iraq country map (source: Worldometer)⁶⁴

With the exception of the northern and north-eastern mountainous regions, which experience a Mediterranean climate, most of Iraq is characterised by a continental and subtropical semi-arid climate. The nation typically experiences dry summers with shifts between hot and extremely hot temperatures, and cool to cold winters. Summer spans from late April to October and is characterized by high temperatures. During this season, temperatures range between 15 and 44 degrees Celsius across the country. Winter lasts from November to March and is mild to cold, with temperatures ranging from 4.4 to 23 degrees Celsius⁶⁵. In Iraq, precipitation follows a seasonal pattern, with the majority of the country receiving rain from December to February during the winter months. The northeast and north of the country, on the other hand, experience rainy seasons from November to April. South and South-easterly Sharqi, dry dust winds that blow across the nation from April to June and September to November, also have an impact on the climate. The climate is also influenced by the north and northwest Shamal Winds, which cause significant surface heating⁶⁶.

1.4.2 WEF Situation

1. Water

a. Water Resources (Internal and Cross boundary)

The typical annual rainfall in Iraq is averaged at 204.06 mm between 1901 and 2022. The majority of this precipitation occurred in the northern areas of Iraq, including Duhok, Erbil, Al-Sulaymaniyah,

⁶⁴Worldometer. (n.d.). World map. Worldometer. https://www.worldometers.info/world-map/#google_vignette

⁶⁵ Al-Ansari, N. (2021). Topography and climate of Iraq. *Journal of Earth Science & Geotechnical Engineering*, 11, 1–13. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345639751_Topography_and_Climate_of_Iraq

⁶⁶World Bank. (n.d.). World Bank climate change knowledge portal. World Bank. <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/iraq/climate-data>

Kirkuk, and Ninewa. It peaked at 286.90 mm in 1954 and hit a low of 132.78 mm in 2008 (Figure 8)^{67,68}.

Figure 8 Precipitation (mm) in Iraq (1923 – 2022) (source: tradingeconomics, (2022)⁶⁷)

Regarding surface water in Iraq, the country is renowned about its fabled rivers. Where the watersheds, including their tributaries, account for 100% of the country's surface water⁶⁹.

The two dominant rivers in Iraq⁶⁹:

1. The Tigris River, which originates in Türkiye, flows for about 1,000 km inside Iraq's borders. The total natural run-off of the Tigris watershed, including its tributaries, is estimated to be between 41.2 and 58.3 (BCM/yr)⁶⁹.
2. The Euphrates River, which originates in Türkiye, flows for about 1,300 km inside Iraq's borders. The total natural run-off of the Euphrates watershed is estimated to be between 27 and 35.1 (BCM/yr)⁶⁹.

The major tributaries in Iraq:

- The Greater Zab, which originates in Türkiye.
- The Lesser Zab, which originates in Iran.
- The Diyala, which originates in Iran.
- The Adhaim, which drains about 13,000 square km² entirely in Iraq.
- The Nahr at Tib, Dewarege and Shehabi rivers, together draining more than 8,000 km².

⁶⁷Trading Economics. (2022). Iraq average precipitation. Trading Economics. <https://tradingeconomics.com/iraq/precipitation>

⁶⁸World Bank. (n.d.). What is climate change? Climate Change Knowledge Portal. World Bank. <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/>

⁶⁹Fanack Water. (2023). Water resources in Iraq. Fanack Water. <https://water.fanack.com/iraq/water-resources-in-iraq/>

- The Karkheh River, in southern Iraq, the main course of which is in Iran, brings over 50,000 km² of water and flows inside the Hawr al-Hawiza marsh⁶⁹, which is connected downstream with the Tigris and Euphrates system after running through the Hawizeh Marshes.
- The Karun River, the most significant downstream tributary, with a catchment of about 67,000 km², which has a primary impact on salinity intrusion along the Shatt al-Arab.

Fourteen major aquifers have been recognized and classified in Iraq, identified in Figure 9.

Figure 9 The major groundwater aquifers in Iraq (source: Othman et al. 2022⁷⁰)

The depths of the presence of groundwater beneath the earth’s surface are very crucial factors in investing groundwater, and its uses. Furthermore, it’s very important as well in estimating the costs of drilling, the type of drilling rigs, drilling methods, well designs and the type of pumping equipment. Figure 10 below shows the variation of the groundwater depths from one basin to another and from one aquifer to another in Iraq. It ranges between more than 300 meters in the faraway western desert while not more than 10 meters in the Mesopotamian region⁷¹ which is relatively shallow. Groundwater salinity in Iraq varies significantly, with levels in the Mesopotamian zone often exceeding 3,000 mg/L due to high evaporation and limited recharge, making it challenging for agricultural use. In the northern limestone aquifers, salinity levels are generally

⁷⁰ Othman, A., Abdelrady, A., & Mohamed, A. (2022). Monitoring Mass Variations in Iraq Using Time-Variable Gravity Data. *Remote Sensing*, 14(14), 3346. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14143346>

⁷¹ Diva-Portal. (n.d.). Simple search. Diva-Portal. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/>

lower, typically under 1,000 mg/L, though they fluctuate due to complex flows within the karst formations⁷². Transboundary aquifers passing through Iraq are highlighted in Table 8.

Figure 10 Groundwater depths in different zones in Iraq⁷³

⁷² Al-Ansari, N. (2021). Topography and climate of Iraq. *Journal of Earth Science & Geotechnical Engineering*, 11, 1–13. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345639751_Topography_and_Climate_of_Iraq

⁷³ Al-Jiburi, H. K., & Al-Basrawi, N. H. (2015). Hydrogeological map of Iraq, scale 1: 100 000, 2nd edition. *Iraqi Bulletin of Geology and Mining*, 11(1), 17–26. <https://www.iasj.net/iasj/download/69d0ec38d854102b>

Table 8 Transboundary Aquifers in Iraq⁷⁴

Groundwater Aquifer	Shared Countries	Area (Km ²)
Upper Jezira	Iraq, Syria, Türkiye	10294
Taurus-Zagros	Iran, Iraq, Türkiye	207478
Neogene Aquifer System (North- West): Upper and Lower Fars	Syria, Iraq	66266
Wasia-Biyadh-Aruma Aquifer System (North): Sakaka-Rutba	Saudi Arabia, Iraq	84212
Neogene Aquifer System (South- East): Dibdibba-Kuwait Group	Iraq, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia	148313
Umm er Radhuma-Dammam Aquifer System (North): Widyan-Salman	Iraq, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia	242966

Non-conventional water in Iraq

Desalination

- In 2019, construction of the country's first major desalination plant was completed in Al-Hartha, 20 km north of Basra. It was designed with a reverse osmosis system to desalinate 199,000 cubic meters of brackish water from the Shatt al-Arab daily, providing drinking water to 400,000 people in Basra.
- Plans are currently being developed for another large-scale desalination plant at Al-Faw along the Gulf Coast^{75,76}.

Wastewater reuse

Iraq currently has a negligible reuse rate for treated wastewater. While there have been some pilot projects using treated municipal wastewater in agriculture, there has yet to be widespread adoption. The Ministry of Water Resources intends to modernize its drainage water collection system in order to better reuse irrigation water, which is critical for meeting the country's future water requirements. Among other things, the treated water can be used for oil well re-injection, creating green belts to combat desertification, and supplementing the water available for the Mesopotamian Marshes of southern Iraq⁷⁷.

Rainwater harvesting

Water harvesting in Iraq can be founded into two main categories:

➤ Natural water harvesting ponds.

Several natural water harvesting formations exist in Iraq's deserts; these formations evolved naturally, and the majority of them were named after local names. These formations include Khabari, Ghidran, Thighab, Chaltat, Water Springs, and Faidhat..

⁷⁴International Groundwater Resources Assessment Centre. (2022). Transboundary aquifers of the Middle East map 2022. International Groundwater Resources Assessment Centre. <https://www.un-igrac.org/resource/transboundary-aquifers-middle-east-map-2022>

⁷⁵Tollast, R. (2020). Iraq and the desalination revolution: First steps, future trends. Iraq Energy Institute. <https://iraqenergy.org/2020/05/01/iraq-and-the-desalination-revolution-first-steps-future-trends/>

⁷⁶Smart Water Magazine. (2023). Iraq initiates enormous desalination project. Smart Water Magazine. <https://smartwatermagazine.com/news/smart-water-magazine/iraq-initiates-enormous-desalination-project>

⁷⁷Fanack Water. (2023). Water resources in Iraq. Fanack Water. <https://water.fanack.com/iraq/water-resources-in-iraq/>

➤ **Small water harvesting dams.**

Small dams in Iraq are in three main regions⁷⁸:

1. **Northern Area**, where small dams are built to store water for irrigation projects or in sub-catchments of major rivers. For example, the Duhok dam (52MCM).
2. **Eastern Valleys**, these valleys are distinguished by a relatively high sediment load as a result of soil erosion, altitude differences, and the frequency and intensity of rainstorms. Several dams were built after 2003, but the majority of them are suffering from sediment accumulation in their reservoirs. These dams are represented in Table 9 below.

Table 9 Small water harvesting dams in the Eastern Valleys in Iraq.

Dam Name	Location	Capacity	Notes
Qazaniyah Dam	Harran Valley, Diyala governorate	0.9 MCM	Dam mainly used for irrigation purposes. The dam suffers from accumulated sediments.
Mandalay Dam	Harran Valley, Diyala governorate	3.63 MCM	Dam mainly used for irrigation purposes. The dam suffers from accumulated sediments.
Shihabi Dam	Shihabi Valley, Wasit governorate	0.8 MCM	Dam mainly used for irrigation purposes. The dam suffers from accumulated sediments.
Dewerej Dam	Dewerej Valley, Maysan governorate	1.87 MCM	Dam mainly used for irrigation purposes. The dam suffers from accumulated sediments.
Badra Dam	Badra Valley, Wasit governorate	0.25 MCM	Dam mainly used for irrigation purposes. The dam suffers from accumulated sediments.

3. **Western Desert** is the most important in terms of need for water resources and providing habitat for man and animals. The existing water harvesting dams, that are mainly used for irrigation, are represented in Table 10 below.

Table 10 Small water harvesting dams in the Western Desert in Iraq.

Dam Name	Location	Capacity
Husub Dam	Husub Valley, Najaf governorate	4.2 MCM
Horan 2 Dam	Horan Valley, Anbar governorate	4.9 MCM
Rutbah Dam	Northern desert, Anbar governorate	32 MCM

⁷⁸Abdullah, M., Al-Ansari, N., & Laue, J. (2020). Water harvesting in Iraq: Status and opportunities. Journal of Earth Sciences and Geotechnical Engineering, 10(1), 199–217. <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2:1385302>

Al-Ubailah Dam	Western desert, governorate	Anbar	4 MCM
Al-Aghri Dam	Western desert, governorate	Anbar	6 MCM
Hussainiyah Dam	Western desert, governorate	Anbar	6 MCM
Shibaijah Dam	Western desert, governorate	Anbar	8 MCM
Rahaliyah Dam	Western desert, governorate	Anbar	4 MCM
Um Al-Tarfat Dam	Western desert, governorate	Anbar	7 MCM
Surry Dam	Western desert, governorate	Anbar	0.3 MCM
Abyadh Dam	Western desert, governorate	Anbar	25 MCM

b. Water Use by sector

Agriculture uses the great majority of Iraq's water resources. Approximately 73.47% of the 42.42 BCM of water extracted for human use in 2021 went to agriculture, 10.65% to industry, and 15.88% to municipal water supply⁷⁹. The decline of Iraqi industry after the 2003 US invasion, civil war, and conflict with the Islamic State in Iraq and Syria (ISIS) caused the trend to reverse and industrial water use to drop to its present low level after a sharp rise in the 1990s and early 2000s.⁸⁰

Approximately two-thirds of Iraq's cultivated land is irrigated, especially in the country's semi-arid and arid regions, meaning that the agricultural sector uses the majority of the country's water resources. Low irrigation efficiency, estimated at 30–40%, is another factor contributing to the excessive water use. This is mostly caused by water loss from irrigation canals and the use of ineffective flood irrigation⁸⁰.

Demand is set to outpace supply in the near future if Iraq does not embark on major reforms of the water sector. Report estimates a deficit of 10-20 BCM/yr by 2030, which would correspond to approximately one-third of Iraq's water demand^{81,82}.

c. Water risk

1. If Iraq is to meet its projected water needs over the next 20 years, it will need to address a number of issues, including infrastructure deterioration and leaks, an antiquated irrigation and drainage water collection system, perverse incentives in farm subsidies, and the use of fresh water for oil well re-injection (instead of more sustainable alternatives like treated wastewater)⁸⁴.
2. Even though these rivers are essential for supplying industry, delivering drinking water, and irrigating large areas of farmland, it is widely accepted that upstream pollution has decreased

⁷⁹ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). (2021). *AQUASTAT database*. <https://data.apps.fao.org/aquastat/?lang=en>

⁸⁰Fanack Water. *Water use in Iraq*. Retrieved November 26, 2024, from <https://water.fanack.com/iraq/water-use-in-iraq/>

⁸¹Fanack Water. (2023). *Water use in Iraq*. Fanack Water. <https://water.fanack.com/iraq/water-use-in-iraq/>

⁸²Alwash, A., Istepanian, H., Tollast, R., & Al-Shibaany, Z. (2018). *Towards sustainable water resources management in Iraq*. Iraq Energy Institute. <https://iraqenergy.org/wp/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/Water-Report.pdf>

surface runoff by about 30%. Over the next 20 years, this impact is expected to worsen much further, lowering Iraq's water supply by as much as 60%⁸³.

3. Originating in Turkey, the Euphrates and Tigris are both transboundary rivers. Iraq is in a challenging situation when it comes to planning for and managing its water resources because these significant rivers do not originate there, which has long been a source of contention with its riparian neighbors.
4. Like other nations in the region, Iraq is now dealing with a severe water shortage issue. Iraq's population is growing and its economy is developing, which is increasing the country's need for water resources⁸⁴.
5. The decline in the amounts and deterioration of the two significant rivers, the Tigris and Euphrates, has resulted in a severe water crisis for Iraq. Over 98% of Iraq's water needs for the different uses that are shared with other nations are met by the Tigris and Euphrates rivers. It is anticipated that this issue would worsen in the future. According to estimates, the discharges from the Tigris and Euphrates rivers will continue to decline until they are entirely dry by 2040.
6. Iraq is reliant on water that enters the nation from the Tigris and Euphrates rivers as well as several tributaries. Iraq is in a precarious situation due to decreases in the flows of these rivers brought on by upstream agricultural development, population growth, industrial development, dam construction, and other water diversions. The absence of long-term agreements governing the distribution of water among the main rivers or the quality of the water that enters Iraq's borders makes this vulnerability worse. extra than 9 million extra people are anticipated to live in the Euphrates-Tigris basin in Iran, Syria, and Turkey during the course of the next 20 years⁸⁵.
7. More than 1.5 million hectares of agricultural land will be added by Turkey, Syria, and Iran to the Euphrates and Tigris watershed at the same time as the population grows. If complete agricultural development is attained, the total cultivated land in these three nations will reach around 2.5 million hectares by 2035. The water quality will deteriorate and Iraq will receive less water as a result of this intensive agricultural expansion, which would significantly increase water usage outside of Iraq. According to estimates made by the Ministry of Water Resources when it created its national water strategy, Iraq would have 24% less water available in 2035 than it does now if all of the planned irrigation projects and water diversions in the upstream nations were carried out⁸⁵.
8. Reusing wastewater. Iraq currently reuses very little treated wastewater for two main reasons: first, the country's wastewater treatment infrastructure capacity is inadequate, especially in rural regions; and second, the water sector lacks information about effective wastewater reuse⁸⁵.

2. Energy

a. Supply

In 2021, Iraq's total energy supply was 509,381.39 GWh, with 38% of this supply being imported. Table 11 and Figure 11 highlight Iraq's energy resources and supply.

⁸³Fanack Water. (2023). *Water resources in Iraq*. Fanack Water. <https://water.fanack.com/iraq/water-resources-in-iraq/C>

⁸⁴Zarei, M. (2020). The water-energy-food nexus: A holistic approach for resource security in Iran, Iraq, and Türkiye. *Water-Energy Nexus*, 3, 81–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wen.2020.05.004>

⁸⁵Fanack Water. (2023). *Shared water resources in Iraq*. Fanack Water. <https://water.fanack.com/iraq/shared-water-resources-in-iraq/>

Figure 11 Energy supply per resource in Iraq (source: IEA).

Table 11 Energy supply per resource in 2021 – Iraq (source: IEA⁸⁶)

Energy Resources	Energy Supply (GWh)	%
Natural gas	183,634.72	36.05
Hydro	4,775.83	0.94
Wind, solar, etc.	57.22	0.01
Biofuels and waste	608.33	0.12
Oil	320,305.28	62.88
Total	509,381.39	100.00

b. Demand

Table 12 and Figure 12 highlight Iraq's energy demands, in which, the major energy consuming sector in the country is the Transportation sector, consuming over 43% of the country's energy followed by Industry and residential sectors.

Table 12 Energy consumption per sector in 2021 – Iraq (source: IEA⁸⁶)

Sector	Final Consumption (GWh)	%
Industry	73,798.61	24.72
Transport	130,917.78	43.85
Residential	72,015.28	24.12
Commercial and public services	10,565.00	3.54
Agriculture / forestry	1,061.94	0.36
Non-specified	271.11	0.09
Non-energy use	9,913.33	3.32
Total	298,543.06	100

⁸⁶ International Energy Agency. (n.d.). Iraq. International Energy Agency. Retrieved from <https://www.iea.org/countries/iraq>

Figure 12 Energy consumption in Iraq per sector in 2021 (source: IEA⁸⁶)

c. Energy risk

Iraq's energy sector has suffered for many years, causing frequent blackouts, significant losses, and shortages in gas supplies that have a negative impact on the economy of the nation. Several development initiatives have been started to increase the urgently required power capacity. However, these have been subjected to a mix of risks related to politics, the economy, and violence. New investments in Iraq's power generation will probably continue to be impeded by this difficult risk environment. Implementing power investments has been hampered by contract risks resulting from political meddling and corruption as well as macroeconomic risks like the COVID-19 pandemic and the government's excessive reliance on oil revenue. Power generation and interconnection projects are expected to face pressure from both internal and external political risks, including political wrangling that may arise from legislative elections. Additionally, due to high technical transmission and distribution losses as well as rising nontechnical losses like electricity theft from the grid and unpaid power bills, losses in the power network account for roughly half of the total demand⁸⁷.

3. Food

a. Supply

The amount of wheat required locally is about 4.2 million tonnes, and while Iraq produced over 6.2 million tonnes of wheat in 2020, the country still imports about 1 million tonnes of wheat to supplement its domestic output for quality matters. Iraq produced more barley than was needed locally, totalling about 1.7 million tonnes. One of the causes of the surpluses was Iraq's encouragement of local production of those two commodities by buying them at a premium over the global market. Among the commodities in excess are dates, tomatoes, eggplants, onions, and others⁸⁸. The Iraqi Ministry of Trade has signed a contract, in 2015, with Etihad Food Industries to

⁸⁷Al Assam, Z. (2022). Multiple risks hinder the future of Iraq's struggling power sector. S&P Global. <https://www.spglobal.com/commodityinsights/en/ci/research-analysis/multiple-risks-hinder-the-future-of-iraqs-struggling-power.html#:~:text=Iraq%20relies%20on%20Iran%20for,threat%20to%20recent%20power%20projects.>

⁸⁸ Logistics Cluster. Iraq: Food and additional suppliers, from <https://lca.logcluster.org/35-iraq-food-and-additional-suppliers>

supply sugar and sunflower oil. The factory produces corn oil, sugar, vegetable ghee, sunflower oil and RDB palm oil. The factory can produce 2400 MT (Metric Tons) of sunflower oil and 4000 MT (Metric Tons) of sugar per day. Altunsa Company, which is also present in Iraq, supplies dry pulses, rations, sunflower oil with a daily capacity of 2000 MT, and wheat flour with a daily capacity of 1000 MT. Iraq's major markets for export include China, India, South Korea, the United States, and Italy.

b. Demand

Iraq's rice production over the past ten years has only been able to supply 8–21% of the country's domestic demand, with the remainder coming from imports. This was mostly brought on by the scarcity of water resources in addition to the restricted amount of land available for rice production. As a result, Iraq was one of the top ten rice-importing nations in the world. In general, the amount of cereals produced in a given year has a significant impact on the amount of cereals imported⁸⁹. For example, in 2020, Iraq produced approximately 6.2 million tonnes of wheat and 1.7 million tonnes of barley, surpassing local demand... Furthermore, Iraq is one of the largest importers of wheat flours worldwide⁹⁰. Iraq, despite being one of the largest importers of wheat flour globally, occasionally experiences surpluses in wheat production. This paradox arises from several factors, including a lack of adequate storage and milling infrastructure, which limits the country's ability to process and distribute domestically produced wheat efficiently. Additionally, logistical and governance challenges in managing the agricultural supply chain lead to reliance on imports to meet the demand for processed wheat flour products. High consumer demand for wheat-based staples further exacerbates the issue^{91,92}.

c. Food security

Iraq has survived effects resulting from wars and insurgencies; however, these incidents continue to influence the nation's social and economic structure. Among the most pervasive domestic issues facing the nation are poverty and hunger. The World Food Programme (WFP) estimates that 31% of Iraqis are living in poverty and that 2.4 million of the country's 45.5 million citizens suffer from acute hunger. USAID reports that nearly 1 million Iraqis face food insecurity.⁹³

Following the damage caused due to political conflicts in the region, many Iraqis are in danger of being displaced (internal displacement). The United Nations estimates that 1.2 million Iraqis have been displaced and that 4.1 million need humanitarian aid. Iraq has been using the public distribution system (PDS) since 1990 to provide families with staple foods on a monthly basis, thereby achieving food security and mitigating the crippling effects of the economic sanctions imposed on the country. In 2016, 90% of Iraqi households, received food subsidies. The program's cost was estimated to be 0.6% of GDP, and the PDS was legible for all Iraqis. However, in 2021, the government decided to remove some categories. White sugar, wheat flour, sunflower oil, and rice are the primary food commodities used in PDS. The PDS then added beans, chickpeas, and tomato

⁸⁹Abdullah, Y. Y., & Mohammed, R. M. (2023). Estimating demand for imported food categories in Iraq. *Mağallaṭ Al-‘ulūm Al-iqtisādiyyaṭ Wa-al-idāriyyaṭ*, 29(137), 146–159. <https://doi.org/10.33095/jeas.v29i137.2759>

⁹⁰Al Assam, Z. (2022). Multiple risks hinder the future of Iraq's struggling power sector. S&P Global. <https://www.spglobal.com/commodityinsights/en/ci/research-analysis/multiple-risks-hinder-the-future-of-iraqs-struggling-power.html#:~:text=Iraq%20relies%20on%20Iran%20for,threat%20to%20recent%20power%20projects>.

⁹¹ FAO. (2024). Iraq country brief. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Retrieved from <https://www.fao.org/gIEWS/countrybrief/country.jsp?code=IRQ>

⁹² Miller Magazine. (2024). Iraq: The biggest wheat importer in the Middle East after Egypt. Miller Magazine. Retrieved from <https://millermagazine.com/blog/iraq-the-biggest-wheat-importer-in-the-middle-east-after-egypt-2919>

⁹³Food Assistance Fact Sheet - Iraq," U.S. Agency For International Development, 2020. <https://www.usaid.gov/food-assistance/iraq> (accessed Jul. 04, 2024).

paste. The allocation of all commodities and their frequency differed from month to month based on Iraq's economic circumstances. The Ministry of Agriculture has therefore stated that Iraq is attempting to achieve food security by raising the production of strategic goods like wheat and barley⁹⁴.

Despite the fact that many agricultural markets, especially in the Kurdistan region, have reopened, they are still beset by a number of persistent problems, including unfavourable agroclimatic conditions, uneven domestic cereal production, disruptions in the public distribution system, unfavourable policies regarding agricultural investment, and low purchasing power⁹⁵. The agricultural sector in Iraq is also under pressure from unfavourable weather patterns and droughts. Iraq's food systems have been weakened by the depletion of water supplies from the Tigris and Euphrates Rivers, as well as economic collapses brought on by the conflicts in the region. These factors have made hunger in the country even worse. Hope and optimism regarding Iraq's food security, however, are abundant for the future. The next generation has the ability to welcome a better future now that the conflicts and security issues have been resolved⁹⁵. In recent years, Iraq's food security situation appears to be less dire than that of neighbouring nations like Yemen and Syria. Iraq has a moderate GHI (Global Health Index) score of 13.7, placing it 66th out of 121 countries in the Global Health Index⁹⁵.

4. Ecosystem

The terrestrial ecosystems of Iraq are composed of various primary and secondary eco-regions, which include:⁹⁶

- **Tigris-Euphrates alluvial Salt Marsh (PA0906) – 35,600 km²**

The marshland has climate that is subtropical, hot, and arid, with reeds and rushes growing within, making it of prime importance to winter migratory birds from Eurasia and to the spawning fish of the Gulf. The area is a globally important bird area, with 159 species recorded, of which 34 are of conservation concern and eight are globally threatened. Unique mammals occurring in the area include the Bunn's short-tailed bandicoot rat, Mesopotamian gerbil, and smooth-coated otter.

Despite this, the area is now categorized as "Critical/Endangered" due to the extensive conversion of the ecosystems from draining the marshlands in southern Iraq. Most of these poorly known mammals, insects, amphibians, and reptiles, therefore, represent many species worthy of essential conservation.

- **Arabian Desert and East Sahero-Arabian Xeric Shrublands (PA1303) – 1,851,300 km²**

The desert biome over the Arabian Peninsula, which extends from Oman into Iraq, has low biological diversity. This region is noted for extremely low rainfall with sporadic oases and dry river channels. Temperatures vary extremely and can be over 45°C in summer, while winter temperatures may fall into the teens. The area also houses brackish salt flats.

The biodiversity is relatively less known. However, commonly found in the desert area are Steppe Eagle, Bar-tailed Lark, Temminck's Lark, Eurasian Eagle Owl, Macqueen's Bustard, Spotted

⁹⁴Iraq Food Suppliers | Digital Logistics Capacity Assessments." <https://dlca.logcluster.org/351-iraq-food-suppliers>

⁹⁵B. Project and B. Project, "Everything You Need to Know About Hunger in Iraq," BORGEM, Nov. 10, 2023. <https://www.borgenmagazine.com/hunger-in-iraq/>

⁹⁶ Republic of Iraq Ministry of Environment. (2010). Iraqi fourth national report to the Convention on Biological Diversity. CBD. Retrieved July 10, 2024, from <https://www.cbd.int/doc/world/iq/iq-nr-04-en.pdf>

Sandgrouse, Cream-Coloured Courser, Desert Wheatear, and Desert Finch. Reptiles, such as the spiny-tailed lizards, are present⁹⁷.

The conservation status of the region is "Critical/Endangered." There are several records from surveys, but still, a large portion remains unvisited because of conflict.

- **Mesopotamian Shrub Desert (PA1320) – 211,000 km²**

The Mesopotamian Shrub Desert ecoregion extends throughout the entire Fertile Crescent within the valleys of the Tigris and Euphrates rivers, reaching both parts of the Syrian Desert and northern steppe regions. Arid climatic conditions and temperature follow approximately the same patterns as that of the Arabian Desert. Elevations vary from 600 m high on the west to less than 100 m on the east next to the Zagros foothills, with human concentrations working right along the river basins.

Augla, GasrMuhaiwir, Attariya plains, and Abu Habba are considered important bird areas. Bird surveys found the species of Macqueen's Bustard and Sociable Lapwing, as well as Eurasian migratory species. Mammals are in scattered numbers yet those seen include the wolf, hyena, gazelle, and wild boar⁹⁷.

The status of the area is "Vulnerable" due to limited research focus and security concerns.

- **Middle East Steppe (PA0812) – 132,300 km²**

This ecoregion features dry and moist steppes, spanning from western Jordan and southwestern Syria through northern Iraq, parts of the Tigris-Euphrates River valleys, and the foothills of the Zagros Mountains. The area has calcareous Mesozoic and Tertiary rocks, alluvial-colluvial soils, and regions of black basalt. The continental climate is characterized by high summer temperatures, low rainfall (less than 250 mm) and frosty winters.

Important bird species include Lesser kestrel, Eurasian griffon vulture, and Egyptian Vulture and Greater flamingos. Large mammals present are wolves, red fox, Golden jackals, caracals' jungle cats, and Goitered gazelle. The status of many species, especially insects, amphibians, and reptiles are poorly known. The ecoregion is characterized as "Vulnerable"⁹⁷.

- **Zagros Mountains Forest Steppe (PA0446) – 397,800 km²**

The Zagros Mountains Forest Steppe region ranges from northwest to southeast Iran and part of northern Iraq (Iraqi Kurdistan). It has a semi-arid temperate climate, with 400-800 mm in precipitation per year. Temperatures can fall as low as -25 °C in the winter and reach up to 40 °C in the summer. This ecoregion, part of the Irano-Anatolian biodiversity hot spot, supports a significant diversity of flora consisting of oak and pistachio almond forests, with sub-alpine vegetation found at higher elevations⁹⁷.

Biodiversity includes key bird species such as Golden Eagle, Eurasian Griffon Vulture, and Lesser Kestrel, while mammals include brown bear, wolf, jackal, wild cat, leopard, gazelle, roe deer, and wild goats, with the Persian fallow deer recently rediscovered. The total area is considered critical/endangered and is under some protection by the Kurdistan Regional Government's resource management rules⁹⁷.

Freshwater Ecosystems include:

⁹⁷ Republic of Iraq Ministry of Environment. (2010). Iraqi fourth national report to the Convention on Biological Diversity. CBD. Retrieved July 10, 2024, from <https://www.cbd.int/doc/world/iq/iq-nr-04-en.pdf>

- **The Tigris River.**

The Tigris River, one of the largest in the Middle East, extends 1,900 km, of which 1,415 km is in Iraq itself. The major tributaries to the Tigris are the Greater Zab, Rawanduz, and Kazir Rivers. The Greater Zab flows into the Tigris 1,161 km from the outfall; on the other hand, the Lesser Zab, originating in the Zagros Ridge of Iran, extends 456 km with a catchment area of 22,250 km² and flows into the Tigris 1,046 km from the outfall. The Adhaim River is 230 km long, with a catchment area of 10,780 km², and flows fully within Iraq. On the other hand, the Diyala River is 485 km long and has a catchment area of 29,900 km², beginning in Iran, collecting its waters from several tributaries, and forming Darbandikhan Lake in Kurdistan⁹⁷.

- **The Euphrates River:**

The Euphrates is the longest river in the Middle East and the second largest in terms of volume. Its source is in Türkiye's mountains, approximately 3,000–3,500 meters above sea level. It is created by the meeting point of the Murad rivers. The Euphrates River spans 2,940 km in total, 1,159 km of which are located inside Iraq⁹⁷. The area of the watershed is 388,000 km².

- **Shatt Al Arab:**

The Tigris and Euphrates Rivers meet close to the southern Iraqi village of Qurnah to form Shatt Al Arab. It transports the waters of these two rivers and the Southern marshlands to the Gulf. At its southernmost point, it forms a vast protruding delta. The catchment area is up to 108,000 km², and the river is 195 km long overall⁹⁷.

- **The Mesopotamian Marshlands**

The Mesopotamian Marshlands in southern Iraq form an important part of the freshwater and brackish water ecosystems of Iraq, falling within the Tigris-Euphrates Alluvial Salt Marsh ecoregion. The marshlands represent an extended wetland system with extensive regions of *Phragmites australis* reed beds, containing at least three key ecosystems: the Central Marshes, the Hammar Marshes, and the transboundary Hawizeh Marshes. There are also many minor wetlands beside these systems.

In the 1970s, the marshes covered an area of 12,000 to 15,000 km², thus being one of the largest wetland ecosystems in the world. They were drained due to political reasons in the 1990s, with negative effects on biodiversity, fisheries, and the local climate, also impacting species reliant on these habitats. Restoration efforts started in 2003, focusing on reversing the ecological damage caused by large-scale drainage in the 1990s. Over the last 20 years, significant progress has been made, including the partial re-flooding of the marshes, which has allowed for the recovery of many native plant and animal species, and the reestablishment of traditional livelihoods for Marsh Arabs. By 2016, portions of the marshlands were recognized as a UNESCO World Heritage Site, highlighting their cultural and environmental importance⁹⁸. However, challenges persist due to climate change, reduced water flow from upstream dams, and ongoing water quality issues⁹⁹. These factors continue to threaten the sustainability of restoration achievements and the resilience of the ecosystem.

⁹⁸ United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2016). The Ahwar of Southern Iraq: Refuge of biodiversity and the relict landscape of the Mesopotamian cities. UNESCO. Retrieved from <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/1481/>

⁹⁹ Al-Saidi, M., & Hussein, H. (2021). The water–energy–food nexus and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development: An institutional perspective from the Mesopotamian Marshlands. *Water*, 13(3), 354. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13030354>

These marshland's biodiversity include reeds, rushes, poplars, willows, and tamarisk trees that form habitats for many wildlife species. Freshwater habitats behave as vital wildlife corridors across the arid surrounding deserts.

The fauna is dominated by cyprinids, particularly the economically important *Barbus* species, as well as other marine fish like bull shark, Hilsa shad, and Yellowfin seabream. Also found are unique species: Iraq blind barb, smooth-coated otter subspecies, Bunn's short-tailed bandicoot rat, and softshell turtle¹⁰⁰.

Marine Ecosystems:

The gulf ecoregion is bounded by Iran to the north, the Arabian Peninsula to the south, and Iraq and Kuwait to the northwest, where the Shatt Al Arab and Shatt Al Basrah/Khor Az Zubayr rivers empty into the Gulf. The high temperature, coupled with low precipitation and high evaporation, makes the waters of the Gulf highly saline. The seabed is flat and composed of soft sediments. Increased sedimentation from the drainage of the marshlands has caused degradation in the water quality¹⁰⁰.

Biodiversity in the Gulf Ecoregion holds a variety of marine, endangered, and threatened turtle species: Loggerhead Sea Turtle, Green Turtle, Hawksbill Turtle, Olive Ridley, and Leatherback Sea Turtle. Other reptiles consist of sea snakes, with the Beaked Sea snake and Graceful Small-headed Sea Snake. Some of the important marine fish here are the Bull Shark, Hilsa shad, Yellow-finned seabream, and Silver Pomfret. Marine birds in this region are the Crab-Plover and Slender-billed Gull.¹⁰⁰

1.4.3 National Policies and Legal Framework

1.4.3.1 Water Sector Institutional Frameworks

Water governance encompasses the political, social, economic, and administrative frameworks that shape and regulate the utilization and management of water resources. In Iraq, this involves various ministries, with primary responsibilities shared among the Ministry of Water Resources (MoWR), the Ministry of Finance (MoF), and the Ministry of Planning (MoP) for tasks such as water infrastructure development and resource allocation.

Established by Law No. 50 of 2008¹⁰¹, the MoWR, led by the Minister of Water Resources, provides the institutional framework for water resource management in Iraq. Its key responsibilities include planning water resource investments, regulating the use of groundwater and surface water, and managing water sources and their utilization.

Furthermore, the Ministry of Environment and the Ministry of Health assess the environmental and health impacts of water projects. The Ministry of Environment ensures that activities by companies and individuals do not harm Iraq's waterways and biodiversity, while the Ministry of Health evaluates the health effects on citizens. Additionally, the Ministry of Municipalities and Public Works is tasked with enhancing municipal water services, such as water supply and sewage treatment, and plays a pivotal role in formulating, budgeting, and executing centrally funded projects.¹⁰²

¹⁰⁰Republic of Iraq Ministry of Environment. (2010). Iraqi fourth national report to the Convention on Biological Diversity. CBD. Retrieved July 10, 2024, from <https://www.cbd.int/doc/world/iq/iq-nr-04-en.pdf>

¹⁰¹ Republic of Iraq. (2008). Ministry of Water Resources Law No. 50 of 2008. Retrieved from <https://leap.unep.org/en/countries/iq/national-legislation/ministry-water-resources-law-no-50-2008>

¹⁰²Japan International Cooperation Agency & NJS Consultants Co., Ltd. (2015). Report on data collection survey on water sector in Southern Iraq. Japan International Cooperation Agency. <https://openjicareport.jica.go.jp/pdf/1000020477.pdf>

The ministry of water resources also undergoes different water resource management activities including surface water management in the agricultural, industrial, and municipal sectors. Other functions include water quality management, and ecosystem management.

1.4.3.2 Energy Sector Institutional Frameworks

The organizational framework of the electricity sector comprises three primary departments housed within the Ministry of Electricity, directly reporting to the Minister: the Electric Energy Production Office, the Electric Energy Transmission Office, and the Electric Energy Distribution Office. Moreover, five directorates, each comprising distinct divisions responsible for electricity generation, transmission, distribution, and new projects, operate within the sector. These divisions are further subdivided based on geographical regions or specific responsibilities. The electricity sector functions as a vertically integrated monopoly without independent regulatory oversight, with the Ministry assuming responsibility for policymaking, supervision, and strategic planning¹⁰³.

The Ministry of Electricity oversees energy efficiency initiatives, lacking a specific legal framework for regulation. Instead, voluntary reference specifications for buildings serve as guidance for energy efficiency endeavors. Importantly, there are currently no mandated minimum energy performance standards established for household appliances within the existing framework.

In 2010, the Ministry of Electricity established a dedicated unit for renewable energy and environmental concerns, while the Ministry of Science and Technology operates a department focused on renewable energy research. However, there are presently no legal provisions permitting private entities to produce renewable energy and contribute excess electricity to the grid.

Iraq, on the other hand, is one of OPEC's largest crude oil producers, second only to Saudi Arabia, accounting for 17% of Middle Eastern proven reserves and 8% of total reserves¹⁰⁴. As a major producer, Iraq's electricity sector is almost entirely reliant on fossil fuels, accounting for more than 80% of power generation. Despite the country's vast energy resources, the power sector performs sub optimally. The unsustainable growth in power demand—averaging 7% annually over the past decade—is driven by several factors, including population growth, urbanization, and increased industrial activity^{105,106}. Additionally, underinvestment and inadequate reforms in generation, transmission, and distribution systems exacerbate the issue. The result is an increasing mismatch between power supply and demand¹⁰⁷.

1.4.3.3 Food and Agriculture institutional frameworks

The Ministry of Agriculture (MoA) is tasked with fostering the growth of the agricultural sector and overseeing the management of natural resources within the country. The primary objective of the Ministry of Agriculture is to facilitate agricultural advancement and conduct research aimed at increasing productivity. It offers a range of services encompassing plant and animal production,

¹⁰³ REGlobal. (2020). Iraq's power sector: Struggling, ailing, but crawling towards a better future. REGlobal. Retrieved from <https://reglobal.org/iraqs-power-sector-struggling-ailing-but-crawling-towards-a-better>

¹⁰⁴The U.S. Energy Information Administration. (2024, February). Country analysis brief: Iraq. Washington, DC, USA. Retrieved from https://www.eia.gov/international/content/analysis/countries_long/Iraq/pdf/iraq_2024.pdf

¹⁰⁵ International Energy Agency (IEA). (2022). Iraq Energy Outlook: Key Challenges in the Electricity Sector. Paris: IEA Publications. Retrieved from <https://www.iea.org/reports/iraq-energy-outlook>

¹⁰⁶ United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2023). Urbanization and Energy Demand in Iraq: A Pathway to Sustainability. Amman, Jordan: UNDP Regional Hub. Retrieved from <https://www.undp.org/publications/urbanization-energy-demand-iraq>

¹⁰⁷Obeid, J. (2023). Iraq needs renewables, but they won't solve its power problems without broader reforms. Middle East Institute. Retrieved March 11, 2024, from <https://www.mei.edu/publications/iraq-needs-renewables-they-wont-solve-its-power-problems-without-broader-reforms>

dissemination of modern farming techniques, provision of agricultural essentials, and the advancement of initiatives related to prevention, guidance, collaboration, training, and animal welfare services. Moreover, the ministry is dedicated to implementing agricultural legislation to foster self-sufficiency and ensure food security within the nation.

In 2021, Iraq devised a strategy aimed at enhancing the efficiency, inclusivity, and resilience of its agricultural food systems in alignment with the objectives of the Food Systems Summit. This initiative sought to guarantee universal access to affordable, safe, and nutritious food, enabling individuals worldwide to lead active and healthy lifestyles. It also incorporated milestones, such as reducing food insecurity rates by 10% by 2025, increasing the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices by 2030, and achieving full integration of climate-smart agriculture by 2040. While progress has been made, initial steps include pilot projects in drought-affected regions and the allocation of funding for infrastructure improvements, though comprehensive progress reporting remains limited¹⁰⁸.

The United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) works in Iraq to help achieve the National Development Plan's goals of poverty reduction, food security, natural resource management, and improved livelihoods for the poor and vulnerable. FAO also incorporates gender equality, nutrition, climate change adaptation, disaster risk reduction, capacity building, and governance into all interventions at all levels. FAO continues to assist the Government in rebuilding and rehabilitating the social, economic, and environmental fabric of former ISIL-occupied areas in central and northern Iraq¹⁰⁹.

One of FAO's initiatives in Iraq was the Seed Industry Rehabilitation Project, launched in 2004 in response to the aftermath of the 2003 US invasion. Collaborating with the Iraqi government, FAO concentrated on restoring the devastated infrastructure and offering training programs to enhance expertise in seed industry essentials. As part of this initiative, FAO conducted a comprehensive review of seed policies and national legislation, culminating in recommendations aimed at aligning seed industry reforms with Iraq's broader agricultural policy. The project successfully contributed to the reestablishment of seed production facilities, improving the quality and quantity of certified seeds available to farmers¹¹⁰. The organization provided critical equipment and facilities, such as data processing tools, agricultural machinery, seed processing equipment, and laboratory infrastructure¹¹¹.

1.4.3.4 Environmental Sector institutional Frameworks

Iraq's environment has been subject to various intersecting pressures arising from population expansion, the aftermath of three conflicts, climate change, inadequate land use planning, and encroachment on delicate ecosystems. The country grapples with significant environmental challenges, spanning from compromised water quality, soil salinity, and air pollution to conflict-related pollution, degradation of vital ecosystems, climate change repercussions, and the looming threat of water scarcity¹¹². In response to these challenges, the Ministry of Environment (MoEnv)

¹⁰⁸El Hajj Hassan, S. (2022). Joint statement by FAO & WFP in Iraq on World Food Day. FAO & WFP. Retrieved March 11, 2024, from <https://iraq.un.org/en/203643-joint-statement-fao-wfp-iraq-world-food-day>

¹⁰⁹ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). (n.d.). *FAO in Iraq*. FAO. Retrieved from <https://www.fao.org/iraq/en/>

¹¹⁰ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). (2006). *Seed Industry Rehabilitation Project: Final Report on Achievements in Iraq*. Rome: FAO. Retrieved from <https://www.fao.org>

¹¹¹FAO. (2015). *FAO works to increase food security in Iraq*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Retrieved March 11, 2024, from <https://www.fao.org/in-action/fao-works-to-increase-food-security-in-iraq/en/>

¹¹²Price, R. A. (2018). *Environmental risks in Iraq (K4D Helpdesk Report)*. Institute of Development Studies. Retrieved from https://opendocs.ids.ac.uk/articles/online_resource/Environmental_risks_in_Iraq/26483989?file=48259111

addresses environmental priorities through the National Strategy for the Protection and Improvement of the Environment in Iraq (2024-2030). This strategy aligns with national policies by focusing on sustainable water resource management, combating soil salinity and desertification, improving air quality, preserving ecosystems such as the Mesopotamian Marshes, and integrating climate-smart initiatives to meet Iraq's commitments under the Paris Agreement. Through these efforts, MoEnv aims to tackle environmental risks, enhance resilience, and promote sustainable development^{113,114,115}.

Enshrined in Law No. 37 of 2008, the establishment of the Ministry of Environment (MoEnv) signifies Iraq's commitment to environmental stewardship. Tasked with both domestic and international environmental oversight, the ministry holds authority over environmental protection and enhancement efforts. Its overarching mission is to safeguard and enhance the environment, safeguarding public health, preserving natural resources, biodiversity, and cultural heritage. By fostering sustainable development and promoting international and regional collaboration, the ministry endeavors to uphold Iraq's environmental integrity.

Further, the Center for Restoration of the Iraqi Marshlands and Wetlands was established by the Ministry of Water Resources in Iraq in 2003 with the aim of overseeing and monitoring the rehabilitation process of the marshlands. Between 2005 and 2010, these initiatives led to the partial revival of hydrological systems, ecological functions, biodiversity, and local livelihoods. However, challenges such as fluctuating water availability, pollution, and climate change continue to threaten the marshlands' long-term sustainability. The Center also works to raise global awareness by advocating for the inclusion of these marshes in the World Heritage List and the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands^{116,117}.

1.4.3.5 Interlinkages and gaps

Iraq's national policies and legal frameworks are interconnected across various sectors, but several gaps hinder effective implementation and integration. Most of the water used in Iraq is used for agriculture, but vital infrastructure like irrigation networks, water canals, and pumping stations has been neglected and deteriorated for decades. Efficient water use in agriculture is crucial for food security, especially given the increasing water scarcity. Policies to modernize irrigation systems and adopt water-efficient agricultural practices are essential to ensure sustainable food production. The depletion of groundwater resources due to over-extraction for irrigation has led to significant land subsidence and reduced agricultural productivity, highlighting the critical linkage between water management and food security. Relevant institutions, such as the Ministry of Water Resources (MoWR) and the Ministry of Agriculture (MoA), play pivotal roles in addressing these issues. The

¹¹³ United Nations Development Programme in Iraq. (2024). National Strategy for the Protection and Improvement of the Environment in Iraq. Retrieved from <https://www.undp.org/iraq/publications/national-strategy-protection-and-improvement-environment-iraq>

¹¹⁴ United Nations Development Programme. (2024). Iraq unveils a blueprint for a greener future: national strategy for environmental protection and improvement (2024-2030). Retrieved from <https://www.undp.org/arab-states/press-releases/iraq-unveils-blueprint-greener-future-national-strategy-environmental-protection-and-improvement-2024-2030>

¹¹⁵R. Price, "Environmental risks in Iraq," UK Government, 2018. Accessed: Mar. 11, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5b3b63a3e5274a6ff466faa5/Environmental_risks_in_Iraq.pdf

¹¹⁶Centre for Restoration of the Iraqi Marshlands and Wetlands," IUCN. <https://www.iucn.org/our-union/members/iucn-members/centre-restoration-iraqi-marshlands-and-wetlands#:~:text=After%202003%2C%20the%20Ministry%20of,hydrologically%2C%20ecologically%2C%20economically%20and%20serviceably>

¹¹⁷ Douabul, A. (2013). Restoration of the Marshes of Southern Iraq: Prospects and Challenges. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/112709051/Restoration_of_the_Marshes_of_Southern_Iraq_Prospects_and_Challenges

MoWR is responsible for developing and implementing water management strategies, maintaining infrastructure, and regulating water use, while the MoA focuses on promoting sustainable agricultural practices and improving irrigation efficiency¹¹⁸.

There exist some significant gaps in Iraq's policies most notably in implementation and resource allocation, data monitoring, and policy coherence. Addressing these gaps requires coordinated efforts, international support, and robust governance mechanisms to ensure the successful integration and execution of policies¹¹⁸.

1.4.4 Socio-Economic Situation

Iraq has a total population of 42.1 million people, of which 50.4% are male and 49.6% are female. 61.7% of the population is between the ages of 15 and 64, while children under 15 make up 34.6% and 3.6% are 65 or older. Iraq has a population growth rate of 1.99%, with inhabitants concentrated in the north, center, and eastern parts of the country. 71.6% of the population is urban, with the majority of the urbanization concentrated in the capital city Baghdad. Access to education, healthcare, and basic services in Iraq varies significantly across regions. Urban areas, such as Baghdad, generally have better infrastructure and resources, while rural and conflict-affected regions face substantial challenges. Primary school net enrollment is at 94%, but secondary education enrollment drops to 70.3%, with higher dropout rates among girls, exacerbated by overcrowded classrooms, a lack of qualified teachers, and inadequate facilities. Healthcare services are similarly uneven; while over 90% of births are attended by skilled personnel, rural areas and regions affected by conflict struggle with shortages of medical staff, essential medicines, and functioning facilities. Basic services such as clean water, sanitation, and electricity remain unreliable in many areas, particularly in underserved rural communities, due to years of conflict and underinvestment in infrastructure^{119,120}.

Housing quality and public infrastructure in Iraq show significant regional disparities. Urban areas, particularly Baghdad, benefit from relatively better housing and access to public services, while rural regions often face inadequate housing, poor sanitation, and unreliable access to electricity and clean water. Decades of conflict and underinvestment have left much of Iraq's infrastructure in disrepair, with government-built housing meeting only about 15% of national needs, most of which were constructed in the 1960s and 1970s. Public services, including waste management and public transportation, are insufficiently developed in many regions, further exacerbating living conditions for vulnerable populations. Addressing these challenges requires targeted investment in infrastructure rehabilitation and equitable resource allocation to improve the quality of housing and public services across the country^{121,122}.

¹¹⁸Yousif, B., El-Joumayle, O., & Baban, J. (2022). Challenges to Iraq's environment: Applying the water-energy-food nexus framework. Economic Research Forum (ERF). Retrieved from <https://ideas.repec.org/p/erg/wpaper/1564.html>

¹¹⁹ ACAPS. (2020). Education in Iraq. Retrieved from https://www.acaps.org/fileadmin/Data_Product/Main_media/20201109_acaps_thematic_report_on_education_in_iraq.pdf

¹²⁰ UNICEF. (2023). Country Office Annual Report 2023 Iraq. Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org/media/152576/file/Iraq-2023-COAR.pdf>

¹²¹ Republic of Iraq Ministry of Construction & Housing. (2006). Iraq Housing Market Study. Retrieved from https://www.humanitarianlibrary.org/sites/default/files/2013/05/4997_65700_IHMS_Main_Report.pdf

¹²² United Nations Development Programme. (2022). Post-Conflict Infrastructure Rehabilitation in Iraq. Retrieved from <https://www.undp.org/iraq/infrastructure-rehabilitation>

Iraq's economy is highly dependent on oil, yet has a high unemployment rate at 15.32%, and 23% of the population fall below the poverty line. Table 13 provides more detail on the country's economic situation¹²³

Table 13 Socio-Economic Indicators - Iraq

Indicator	Value ¹²⁴
GDP (USD Billion)	264.18
GDP per Capita (USD)	5937.2
GDP from Agriculture (%)	3
GDP from Mining (%)	51
GDP from Services (%)	46
Inflation Rate (%)	5
Unemployment Rate (%)	15.6
Youth Unemployment Rate (%)	31.76

1.4.5 Recommendations

This section is the author's recommendations based on the outcomes of the literature review summarized above.

- Water Risk

Iraq needs to focus on upgrading its water infrastructure to address its growing water scarcity. Immediate action (when funding is secured) should include repairing and modernizing irrigation and drainage systems, while reducing leakages and losses in water distribution. Additionally, fresh water used for oil well re-injection should be replaced with treated wastewater to alleviate pressure on water resources (taking into account any related socio-economic impacts and scalability of the available infrastructure). This shift, along with better agricultural water management, will help meet Iraq's future water needs. Strengthening water-sharing agreements with upstream neighbors, particularly Türkiye, Syria, and Iran, is also crucial to ensure a stable water supply. Iraq should also develop a comprehensive national water management strategy that focuses on sustainable usage and increased wastewater reuse. The country's reliance on transboundary rivers makes it vulnerable, so diplomatic engagement and regional cooperation are essential for long-term water security. Iraq can also explore modern water conservation technologies such as drip irrigation, water recycling, and aquifer (while taking into account their economic feasibility) recharge to better manage its limited water resources in the face of climate change and population growth

- Energy Risk

To enhance its energy security, Iraq should focus on modernizing its energy infrastructure and reducing transmission and distribution losses, which can be achieved through initiatives designed to increase energy use efficiency like public awareness campaigns and the use of energy efficient

¹²³CIA, "Iraq," The World Factbook, (2024). <https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/countries/iraq/#economy> (accessed Jul. 03, 2024).

¹²⁴World Bank Open Data," World Bank Open Data. <https://data.worldbank.org/country/iraq>

appliances. Significant investment, by securing required funds using the PPP (Public-Private Partnerships) strategy for example, is needed to upgrade outdated power plants and transmission lines. Implementing policies that curb electricity theft and improve bill collection is critical to reducing non-technical losses in the power grid. Additionally, diversifying energy sources by promoting renewable energy, such as solar and wind, will lessen the country's dependence on fossil fuels and increase the resilience of the energy sector.

Political instability and corruption continue to hinder progress in Iraq's energy sector. Transparent governance reforms are needed to attract foreign investments and improve project implementation. Strengthening energy cooperation with neighboring countries could also mitigate geopolitical risks and secure more reliable energy imports. By improving its legal framework and addressing political risks, Iraq can create a more stable environment for energy sector growth.

- Food Security

Iraq should continue strengthening its public distribution system (PDS) to ensure food security for vulnerable populations while modernizing its agricultural sector to become more self-sufficient. These goals can be achieved by digitizing the PDS for transparency, improving supply chain efficiency, integrating local food production, and providing targeted subsidies to vulnerable populations. Investments in irrigation efficiency, drought-resistant crops, and modern farming techniques can help boost domestic food production and mitigate the impact of water shortages. Promoting local production of strategic crops such as wheat and barley will reduce reliance on food imports and build resilience against future economic and environmental shocks.

To address hunger and poverty, Iraq must also improve its social safety nets, particularly for rural populations heavily dependent on agriculture. Expanding food assistance programs and providing targeted support to farmers will help alleviate food insecurity. Alongside this, the government should prioritize rebuilding agricultural markets, especially in regions impacted by conflict, to stabilize food systems and increase purchasing power for Iraqis. Challenges that affect food security such as land degradation, water scarcity, and political instability can be tackled by strengthening governance, investing in sustainable agricultural practices, and improving water management systems are essential steps to overcome these issues and achieve long-term food security and resilience.

- Ecosystem Challenges

Iraq should increase efforts to protect and restore its endangered ecosystems, including the Mesopotamian marshlands and desert regions. These ecosystems are vital for biodiversity and provide critical services like water purification and flood control. Conservation programs should focus on preventing further habitat loss and supporting the regeneration of species that are at risk. Expanding protected areas and enforcing stronger environmental regulations are key steps toward preserving Iraq's natural heritage. Iraq can protect and restore its ecosystems by reintroducing native species, improving water allocation, stabilizing soils, providing funding and training, partnering with global organizations, and using technology to monitor ecosystem health.

The country also needs to address pollution in its freshwater and marine ecosystems. Reducing agricultural runoff and industrial waste will help improve water quality in the Tigris and Euphrates Rivers. Additionally, restoring the Mesopotamian marshlands can create sustainable livelihoods for local communities and contribute to biodiversity conservation. Iraq must also invest in research to better understand its ecosystems and prioritize those areas most in need of protection.

- Addressing Interlinkages and Gaps in the WEFE Nexus

Iraq must adopt an integrated approach to managing its water, energy, food, and ecosystems (WEFE) to address the interconnected challenges it faces. The government should develop policies that promote the efficient use of water and energy resources in agriculture, reducing the strain on both sectors. Encouraging the reuse of treated wastewater (which requires upgrading treatment infrastructure, establishing water quality standards, and enforcing legal frameworks to ensure safe and effective practices.) for irrigation and energy production can help alleviate water scarcity and reduce pressure on fresh water sources.

Moreover, Iraq needs to improve coordination between its ministries of agriculture, energy, environment, and water resources to prevent conflicting policies. Establishing an integrated management framework for the WEFE nexus will allow for better resource allocation and long-term sustainability by fostering inter-ministerial communication through regular meetings, aligning policies with shared goals, and leveraging platforms for data sharing and decision-making. Iraq should also focus on building resilience by investing in renewable energy in agriculture, which will reduce dependence on water-intensive energy sources and ensure more sustainable food production.

1.5 Syria

1.5.1 Country Overview

Syria, officially known as the Syrian Arab Republic, is a country in the Middle East, bordered by Türkiye to the north, Iraq to the east, Jordan to the south, Israel to the southwest, Lebanon to the west, and the Mediterranean Sea to the northwest (Figure 13). The country's geographical coordinates range from approximately 32° to 37° north latitude and 35° to 42° east longitude, covering an area of about 185,180 square kilometers. Syria's topography is diverse, featuring coastal plains, mountain ranges, and arid desert regions. The western part of the country is dominated by the Coastal Mountain Range (Jabal an-Nusayriyah), which runs parallel to the Mediterranean coast. The highest peak in this range is Mount Nabi Yunis, reaching an elevation of 1,562 meters. The fertile Orontes River valley is East of the coastal mountains, a critical agricultural region¹²⁵.

Figure 13 Syria country map (source: Worldometer¹²⁶)

Syria's climate varies significantly across its regions, influenced by its diverse topography and geographical location. Along its coast, the country experiences a Mediterranean climate characterized by hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters. The average annual precipitation varies significantly across regions in Syria. Most areas receive approximately 100 to 250 mm of rainfall per year, while the coastal regions experience substantially higher precipitation levels, with averages reaching up to 1200 mm annually, with most rainfall occurring between November and March. Before the outbreak of the civil war in 2011, Syria had a rapidly growing population. According to

¹²⁵Wikipedia contributors. (2024, March 16). *Geography of Syria*. Wikipedia. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Geography_of_Syria

¹²⁶Worldometer. (n.d.). World map. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from https://www.worldometers.info/world-map/#google_vignette

estimates, Syria's population was approximately 21 million in 2010. The annual growth rate was around 2.5% in the early 2000s, driven by high fertility rates and declining mortality rates¹²⁷. As of 2021, Syria's population is estimated to be around 17 million. The reduction is attributed to conflict-related deaths, emigration, and declining birth rates¹²⁸.

1.5.2 WEFE Situation

1. Water

a. Water Resources (Internal and Cross boundary)

Syria's water resources are critical to its national development and environmental sustainability. The country's water resources are derived from various sources, including surface water, groundwater, and unconventional water resources. Surface water in Syria is primarily sourced from rivers and lakes. The major rivers include the Euphrates, Tigris, Orontes, and the Yarmouk. The most significant Euphrates River originates in Türkiye and flows through Syria into Iraq. The Orontes River, originating in Lebanon, and the Yarmouk River, originating from the Anti-Lebanon mountains and forming part of the border with Jordan, are also vital surface water sources. There are seven primary water basins in Syria: The Coastal Basin, the Euphrates, the Barada and Awaj, Al-Yarmouk, the Orontes, Khabour, and the Desert as shown in Figure 15 below.

¹²⁷Roudi, F. (2001). Demographic developments and population policies in Ba'thist Syria. *The Middle East Journal*, 55(4), 619-635. Retrieved from <https://cris.haifa.ac.il/en/publications/demographic-developments-and-population-policies-in-bathist-syria>

¹²⁸United Nations. (2021). *World population prospects 2021*. United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. Retrieved from <https://population.un.org/wpp/>

Figure 14 Water basins in Syria (Fanack¹²⁹)

The average supply of surface water is estimated to be around 10BCM¹³⁰. Syria has total water resources amounting to 18,802 million cubic meters per year. This equates to 809 cubic meters of renewable water resources per capita annually. Table 14 below details all water resources in Syria.

Table 14 Water resources in Syria 2020.¹³¹

Water resource	Value
Total renewable groundwater (MCM/year)	6,174
Total renewable surface water (MCM/year)	12,628
Total renewable water resources (MCM/year)	18,802
Treated municipal wastewater (MCM/year)	299
Long-term average annual precipitation (mm/year).	252

Groundwater is another critical source of water in Syria. The country relies on several significant aquifers, including the Damascus, Homs-Hama, and coastal basins. Groundwater extraction has

¹²⁹ Fanack Water. (2022). Water resources in Syria. Fanack Water. https://water.fanack.com/syria/water-resources/#_ftn3

¹³⁰ Al-Ansari, N., & Sissakian, V. (2019). Water shortages and its environmental consequences within Tigris and Euphrates rivers. *Journal of Earth Sciences and Geotechnical Engineering*, 9(4), 45–59. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337318040_Water_Shortages_and_its_Environmental_Consequences_within_Tigris_and_Euphrates_Rivers

¹³¹ Mourad, K. A., & Berndtsson, R. (2011). Syrian water resources between the present and the future. *Air, Soil and Water Research*, 4, 105–114. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/220240014_Syrian_Water_Resources_between_the_Present_and_the_Future

increased significantly due to the demand for irrigation and domestic use, leading to over-exploitation and a decline in water tables, averaging 1.5 m/year¹³²¹³³. However, the quality and quantity of groundwater vary across regions, with coastal and urban areas facing significant challenges due to salinity and pollution¹³⁴.

Syria shares several transboundary water bodies with its neighbors, including the Euphrates and Tigris Rivers with Türkiye, Iraq, the Yarmouk River with Jordan, the Orontes River with Lebanon. Managing these transboundary waters is complex and has been a source of tension due to varying national interests and upstream dynamics¹³⁵. The Euphrates River contributes significantly to Syria's water supply and is regulated by agreements between Syria, Türkiye, and Iraq. However, these agreements have been strained, particularly during drought and increased water demand. The Yarmouk River is similarly contentious, with Syria and Jordan negotiating water-sharing agreements to manage this vital resource¹³⁶. Syria has increasingly turned to unconventional water resources, including wastewater and greywater reuse, with WWTPs in Syria treating up to 299 MCM/year, to address water scarcity¹³⁷. These sources are critical for supplementing traditional water supplies and ensuring water availability during drought or conflict.

b. Water Use by sector

In Syria, agriculture consumed the largest share of water at 87% in 2020¹³³. While the municipal sector consumed 9% of water resources and the remaining 4% was consumed by the industrial sector (see Figure 15).

¹³² Aw-Hassan, A., Rida, F., Telleria, R., & Bruggeman, A. (2014). The impact of food and agricultural policies on groundwater use in Syria. *Journal of Hydrology*, 513, 204–215. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022169414002285>

¹³³Baba, A., Al Karem, R., & Yazdani, H. (2021). Groundwater resources and quality in Syria. *Groundwater for Sustainable Development*, 14, 100617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsd.2021.100617>. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352334224_Groundwater_Resources_and_Quality_in_Syria100617

¹³⁴Mourad, K. A., & Berndtsson, R. (2011). Syrian water resources between the present and the future. *Air, Soil and Water Research*, 4, 105–114. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/220240014_Syrian_Water_Resources_between_the_Present_and_the_Future

¹³⁵Gleick, P. H. (2014). Water, drought, climate change, and conflict in Syria. *Weather, Climate, and Society*, 6(3), 331–340. https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/wcas/6/3/wcas-d-13-00059_1.xml

¹³⁶Mazlum, I. (2018). ISIS is an actor controlling water resources in Syria and Iraq. In *Violent non-state actors and the Syrian civil war: The ISIS and YPG cases* (pp. 153–167). Springer. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321440458_ISIS_as_an_Actor_Controlling_Water_Resources_in_Syria_and_Iraq

¹³⁷Fanack Water. (2022). Water resources in Syria. Fanack Water. https://water.fanack.com/syria/water-resources/#_ftn3

Figure 15 Water consumption by sector in Syria in 2020¹³⁸

c. Water risk

Syria faces significant water stress driven by its limited renewable water resources, high demand for agricultural and domestic use, and uneven distribution of precipitation. The country's annual renewable water resources are estimated at approximately 16.7 BCM, while water demand far exceeds supply, reaching 19 to 21 BCM annually in recent years, creating a persistent deficit¹³⁹. The Annual precipitation varies from as little as 50–100 mm in the eastern deserts to a maximum of 1000 mm in the coastal mountain ranges, not exceeding this upper limit¹⁴⁰. These variations contribute to an uneven distribution of water resources, exacerbating stress in drier regions reliant on groundwater and irrigation.

Droughts have become more frequent and severe, with notable instances in 1999–2001 and 2006–2010, leading to significant agricultural losses and migration. Floods, although less common, have caused localized damage, particularly in areas with degraded infrastructure. Pollution of rivers, aquifers, and other freshwater sources due to untreated industrial and municipal wastewater further diminishes water quality¹⁴¹. Climate change amplifies these risks, with models predicting a 20–30% reduction in precipitation in some regions by 2050, alongside increased evapotranspiration and rising temperatures¹⁴².

The ongoing conflict in Syria has devastated its water infrastructure. Over 50% of water supply networks have been damaged, while approximately 35% of treatment plants and 70% of pumping

¹³⁸ Baba, A., Al Karem, R., & Yazdani, H. (2021). Groundwater resources and quality in Syria. *Groundwater for Sustainable Development*, 14, 100617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsd.2021.100617>

¹³⁹ FAO. (2020). AQUASTAT database: Syria. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

¹⁴⁰ Kattan, Z. (2018). Using hydrochemistry and environmental isotopes in the assessment of groundwater quality in the Euphrates alluvial aquifer, Syria. *Environmental Earth Sciences*, 77(2), 1–17.

¹⁴¹ Baba, A., Al Karem, R., & Yazdani, H. (2021). Groundwater resources and quality in Syria. *Groundwater for Sustainable Development*, 14, 100617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsd.2021.100617>

¹⁴² IPCC. (2021). *Sixth Assessment Report: Climate Change 2021 – Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability*. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.

stations have been rendered inoperable in some regions¹⁴³. These losses have significantly reduced access to clean water for millions, especially in rural and conflict-affected areas. Furthermore, poor maintenance and inadequate investment in infrastructure have led to leakage rates exceeding 40%, intensifying water loss¹⁴¹.

2. Energy
a. Supply

In 2021, Syria’s total energy supply was 100,620GWh, with 48% of this supply being imported, primarily from Iraq and Iran. Table 15 illustrates energy supply per resource.

Table 15 Energy supply per resource in 2021 – Syria¹⁴⁴

Energy Resource	Energy Supply (GWh)	%
Coal	7.78	0.01
Natural gas	31102.22	30.91
Hydro	753.89	0.75
Biofuels and waste	93.06	0.09
Oil	68663.06	68.24
Total	100,620.00	100.00

Syria has significant potential to harness renewable energy sources to address its growing energy challenges. The country’s geographical location provides abundant solar energy, with an average annual solar radiation of 5.2 kWh/m² per day, making solar photovoltaic (PV) and solar thermal systems a viable solution for electricity generation and heating¹⁴⁵. Additionally, Syria’s mountainous regions and coastal areas offer opportunities for wind energy development, with wind speeds in some locations exceeding 6 m/s, suitable for commercial-scale wind turbines¹⁴⁵. Biomass from agricultural and municipal waste also represents an untapped resource, particularly in rural areas where waste-to-energy systems can simultaneously address energy and waste management issues¹⁴⁶.

b. Demand

In 2021, Syria’s total energy demand was 58,707.22 GWh. Table 16 and Figure 16 illustrates energy consumption per resource.

Table 16 Energy consumption per sector in 2021 – Syria (source: IEA¹⁴⁷)

Sector	Energy Consumption (GWh)	%
Industry	13,302.22	22.66
Transport	18,872.22	32.15
Residential	12,847.22	21.88
Commercial and public services	2,677.50	4.56

¹⁴³ UNICEF. (2019). *Water under fire: For every child, water and sanitation in complex emergencies*. United Nations Children's Fund.

¹⁴⁴ International Energy Agency. (2021). Energy system. <https://www.iea.org/energy-system>.

¹⁴⁵ IRENA. (2020). Renewable energy prospects for the Arab region. International Renewable Energy Agency.

¹⁴⁶ FAO. (2020). Renewable energy potential in agriculture: An opportunity to diversify rural energy resources. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/29d17480-ee46-405d-a8fd-413cf900d039/content>

¹⁴⁷ International Energy Agency (IEA). (2021). Syria Energy Profile. IEA World Energy Statistics.

Agriculture / forestry	2,056.67	3.50
Non-specified	2,086.67	3.55
Non-energy use	6,864.72	11.69
Total	58,707.22	100.00

Figure 16 Energy consumption per sector in Syria 2021 (source: IEA¹⁴⁷)

c. Energy risk

Energy risk in Syria encompasses a range of factors, including infrastructure vulnerabilities, geopolitical challenges, and the impacts of ongoing conflict.

The ongoing conflict has significantly damaged Syria's energy infrastructure, leading to reduced capacity and reliability by approximately 70%¹⁴⁸. Key risks include¹⁴⁹:

- **Damage to Power Plants:** Many of Syria's thermal power plants, the backbone of its electricity generation, have been damaged or destroyed due to the recent wars and conflicts. This has resulted in frequent power outages and reduced electricity generation capacity¹⁴⁹.
- **Pipeline Disruptions:** Oil and gas pipelines have been frequent targets during the conflict, leading to interruptions in the supply of these critical fuels. Pipeline disruptions affect both domestic energy supply and export potential¹⁵⁰.
- **Aging Infrastructure:** Even in areas not directly impacted by the conflict, much of the energy infrastructure is outdated and needs modernization. Transmission lines, substations and distribution networks are prone to inefficiencies and failures¹⁵¹.

¹⁴⁸ World Bank. (2021). The toll of war: The economic and social consequences of conflict in Syria.

¹⁴⁹Rosner, K. (2016). Water and electric power in Iraq and Syria: Conflict and fragility implications for the future. Strauss Center for International Security and Law.

¹⁵⁰International Energy Agency (IEA). (2021). Syria Energy Profile. IEA World Energy Statistics.

¹⁵¹Gleick, P. H. (2014). Water, drought, climate change, and conflict in Syria. *Weather, Climate, and Society*, 6(3), 331-340. https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/wcas/6/3/wcas-d-13-00059_1.xml

The geopolitical landscape in the Middle East has a pressing influence on Syria's energy security. The urgency of the situation is underscored by key geopolitical risks, which include¹⁵²:

- **Transboundary Water and Energy Disputes:** Syria's energy supply is directly affected by disputes over transboundary water and energy resources it shares with neighboring countries, such as Türkiye and Iraq. These conflicts can lead to energy supply disruptions. For instance, Türkiye's control over the Euphrates River significantly impacts Syria's hydropower generation¹⁵². Türkiye's control over the Euphrates River has led to reductions in water flow into Syria, affecting hydropower generation capacity by up to 50%¹⁵³.
- **Sanctions and Trade Restrictions:** International sanctions have severely restricted Syria's ability to import critical energy supplies and technologies. These sanctions also limit foreign investment in the energy sector, hampering efforts to rebuild and modernize infrastructure¹⁵⁰.
- **Regional Instability:** The broader instability in the Middle East, including the activities of non-state actors and ongoing conflicts, poses a continuous threat to Syria's energy infrastructure and supply chains¹⁵⁴.

3. Food

a. Supply

The food supply in Syria has been significantly affected by various factors, including climate conditions, conflict, and economic policies. Syria's agricultural sector is a vital component of its food supply, with most of the population relying on agriculture for their livelihoods. The country produces a variety of crops, with wheat and barley being the most significant. Wheat is the most critical crop in Syria for domestic consumption and as a staple food. The northeastern region, known as the breadbasket of Syria, is the primary area for wheat production. Barley is also widely cultivated and primarily used as animal feed. The estimated amount of wheat produced in 2021 is 1.05 million tons, which is a quarter of the pre-crisis average of 4.1 million tons (during the period 2002-2011) and down from 2.8 million tons in 2020. Syria's annual wheat consumption is estimated at 3.5–4.5 million metric tons (MMT). This has turned Syria from a self-sufficient wheat producer and occasional exporter into a major importer, relying on 1.5–2.5 MMT of wheat annually, primarily from Russia, to meet its needs.¹⁵⁵ The production of barley, at 268 000 tons, represents roughly 10% of the record harvests in 2019 and 2020. Syria also produces many fruits and vegetables, including tomatoes, cucumbers, olives, citrus, and apples. Production is concentrated in the coastal and southern regions, which have more favorable climatic conditions^{156,157}.

Syria's annual wheat consumption is estimated at 3.5–4.5 million metric tons (MMT), but domestic production has dropped sharply due to conflict, climate change, and damaged infrastructure, producing only 1–1.5 MMT annually in recent years. This has turned Syria from a self-sufficient

¹⁵²Tilmant, A., Lettany, J., & Kelman, R. (2007). Hydrological risk assessment in the Euphrates-Tigris River basin: A stochastic dual dynamic programming approach. *Water International*, 32(3), 474-488.

¹⁵³ FAO. (2020). AQUASTAT database: Transboundary water management. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

¹⁵⁴Mazlum, I. (2018). ISIS is an actor controlling water resources in Syria and Iraq. In *Violent non-state actors and the Syrian civil war: The ISIS and YPG cases* (pp. 153–167). Springer. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321440458_ISIS_as_an_Actor_Controlling_Water_Resources_in_Syria_and_Iraq

¹⁵⁵ FAO. (2023). Special Report: 2023 Syria Wheat Supply and Demand. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

¹⁵⁶Ababsa, M. (2019). Syria's Food Security: From Self-Sufficiency to Hunger as a Weapon. In *Syria: From National Independence to Proxy War*. Springer.

¹⁵⁷FAO. (2021). Crop and food supply assessment mission to the Syrian Arab Republic. Reliefweb. Retrieved from <https://reliefweb.int/report/syrian-arab-republic/fao-crop-and-food-supply-assessment-mission-syrian-arab-republic>

wheat producer and occasional exporter into a major importer, relying on 1.5–2.5 MMT of wheat annually, primarily from Russia, to meet its needs.

Given domestic production challenges, Syria has increasingly relied on food imports to meet its needs. The country imports significant quantities of wheat from Russia and rice from India, Thailand and Pakistan to supplement domestic production^{158,159}. These imports are critical for maintaining food security, especially in urban areas. Syria also imports vegetable oils and sugar, which are essential diet components. These imports help to stabilize prices and ensure availability. Of the percentage of all imported products, food imports reached 21.04% in 2010^{160,161}. However, the conflict has drastically altered this dynamic, with food imports increasing due to reduced domestic production capacity and heightened reliance on external supplies. Sanctions have compounded the issue by restricting Syria's ability to engage with international markets, particularly for wheat and other staple goods, while foreign currency shortages have limited the government's ability to fund large-scale imports. By 2020, food imports were estimated to account for 30–40% of all imports, reflecting a sharp rise in dependency compared to pre-conflict levels¹⁶².

b. Demand

Various factors, including population growth, changing dietary habits, economic conditions, and the ongoing conflict, influence food demand in Syria. Syria's population has grown significantly over the past decades, leading to increased food demand. As of 2021, Syria's population is estimated to be around 21.6 million. Despite the conflict and displacement, the population continues to grow, leading to a higher demand for food. Moreover, urbanization has also contributed to changing food consumption patterns. Urban areas are experiencing higher population growth rates than rural areas. This urbanization has shifted food consumption patterns, with increased demand for processed foods and a greater variety of food products¹⁶³.

The Syrian diet is based on wheat, barley, fruits, vegetables, and dairy products. Meat, particularly lamb and chicken, is also essential to the diet. With increased urbanization and exposure to global food trends, there is a growing demand for processed and convenience foods. This shift is particularly noticeable among younger populations and in urban areas. The nutritional needs of the population, particularly children and pregnant women, drive demand for specific food products. Addressing malnutrition and improving overall health influence food consumption patterns¹⁶³.

c. Food security

Syria is one of the six nations in the world with the least amount of food security¹⁶⁴. There were 12 million food insecure people by the end of 2022, with 2.5 million of them severely so. More than half of all Syrians were classified as belonging to one of these categories. The current report focuses

¹⁵⁸ UN COMTRADE Database. (2023). Syria: Imports of wheat and rice by origin. United Nations Statistics Division.

¹⁵⁹ World Bank. (2022). The impact of conflict on Syria's agricultural trade.

¹⁶⁰ Breisinger, C., Zhu, T., Al Riffai, P., Nelson, G., et al. (2013). Economic impacts of climate change in Syria. *Climate Change Economics*, 4(3), 1350002.

¹⁶¹ Trading Economics. (n.d.). Syria - Food imports (% of merchandise imports) - 2024 data, 2025 forecast, 1974-2010 historical. Trading Economics. Retrieved from <https://tradingeconomics.com/syria/food-imports-percent-of-merchandise-imports-wb-data.html>

¹⁶² FAO. (2023). Syria's cereal supply and trade: Addressing food security challenges. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

¹⁶³ FAO. (2020). Syria - Agriculture sector review and investment planning. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

¹⁶⁴ United Nations News. (2023). More than half of all Syrians going hungry: WFP.

on a variety of violent conflict-related incidents that have exacerbated food insecurity in Syria since 2017¹⁶⁵.

The ongoing conflict, economic challenges, and environmental factors have significantly impacted food security in Syria. Before the conflict, Syria had a relatively high level of food security, mainly due to its robust agricultural sector and policies aimed at achieving self-sufficiency. However, the situation has drastically changed over the past decade. Prior to 2011, Syria was largely self-sufficient in key staple crops like wheat and barley. Government policies focused on supporting agricultural production and maintaining strategic reserves of food staples. Moreover, the conflict has led to widespread destruction of agricultural infrastructure, disruption of food supply chains, and significant displacement of people. These factors have severely compromised food production and access to food¹⁶⁶.

4. Ecosystem

The ecosystem situation in Syria has been profoundly affected by a combination of natural and anthropogenic factors, including climate variability, agricultural practices, urban development, and, significantly, the ongoing conflict. Syria is characterized by diverse ecosystems ranging from coastal areas and mountains to deserts and river valleys. This diversity supports a wide range of flora and fauna. Syria's vegetation varies significantly with altitude and climate. The coastal and mountainous regions are rich in Mediterranean-type vegetation, including pine, oak, and cedar forests. Drought-resistant shrubs and grasses dominate the steppe and desert regions. The country also hosts a variety of animal species, including mammals like gazelles, wolves, and hyenas, as well as numerous bird species, some of which are migratory. Wetlands, such as those around the Euphrates River, are crucial habitats for birdlife¹⁶⁷.

Some of the main ecosystems present in Syria is the Badia, or the Steppe. These are semi-arid rangelands that cover over 50% of the country's land area. Average rainfall in the Steppe region is 127 mm/year, with drastic fluctuations. Al Badia is home to four unique ecosystems: shrubby plains that are flat or undulating, uplands with rocky cliffs and plateaus, and seasonal wetlands and oasis. The majority of Al Badia's vegetation is made up of dwarf shrublands and annual grasses, which are diminishing year after year, yet have long been used as food sources for both domestic animals like sheep, goats, and camels as well as wild herbivores like gazelles, oryx, onagers, and ostriches. Furthermore, the wind and water are eroding the soil as there is no longer any vegetation to protect it. Sandstorms are getting stronger every year as a result. Syria could implement afforestation programs, as reintroducing native vegetation can stabilize the soil and reduce erosion. Additionally, conservation agriculture practices, such as no-till farming and soil mulching, can protect vulnerable areas from further degradation. Internationally supported land rehabilitation projects, including the restoration of degraded rangelands and promoting sustainable grazing, could also play a significant role.

The ongoing conflict in Syria has had a devastating impact on the environment, exacerbating existing issues and creating new challenges. The Syrian conflict has resulted in significant forest cover loss and species population declines. Forested areas, which made up 2.9% of Syria's land pre-conflict,

¹⁶⁵Insecurity Insight. (2023). The links between conflict and hunger in Syria – Conflict, hunger, and aid access. Insecurity Insight. Retrieved from <https://www.insecurityinsight.org>

¹⁶⁶Ababsa, M. (2019). Syria's Food Security: From Self-Sufficiency to Hunger as a Weapon. In Syria: From National Independence to Proxy War. Springer.

¹⁶⁷FAO. (2020). Syria - Agriculture sector review and investment planning. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

have decreased by up to 30–40% in some regions, driven by illegal logging, wildfires, and military activities. Biodiversity has been severely impacted, with habitat destruction from bombings and land conversion displacing wildlife, while the collapse of wildlife protection has increased overhunting and poaching¹⁶⁸. The conflict has destroyed water and waste management infrastructure, resulting in pollution and uncontrolled waste disposal. This has severely affected water quality and public health. Moreover, the displacement of millions of people has increased pressure on natural resources in certain areas, leading to overuse and further degradation. Refugee camps and informal settlements often lack proper sanitation, contributing to environmental pollution¹⁶⁹.

1.5.3 National Policies and Legal Framework

This section provides an overview of the national policies and legal frameworks in Syria and incorporates the different policies per sector (Water, Energy, Food, Ecosystem) and highlights the interlinkages and gaps in the policies and legal framework.

1.5.3.1 Water Sector Institutional frameworks

Established in 1982, the Ministry of Irrigation (MOI) in Syria assumes primary responsibility for water-related endeavors within the country. It is formally entrusted with tasks such as policy formulation, research, issuance of water permits, planning, construction, and the operation and maintenance of hydraulic infrastructures, including dams and canals. The MOI operates under the framework of Law No. 31 of 2005, which defines water resource management strategies, and Decree No. 3 of 2005, which regulates water use and protection, ensuring sustainable allocation and preservation. Through central and general directorates, the ministry oversees the management of seven hydrological basins, which encompass divisions dedicated to irrigation, water resources, and operation and maintenance^{170 171}. Additionally, the National Water Strategy (2008–2030) provides a roadmap for integrated water resource management, focusing on efficient use and environmental sustainability¹⁷². The ministry also conducts hydrological and hydrogeological monitoring, collects water resources data, and assesses resources for strategic planning. However, the ongoing conflict in Syria has severely impacted the water sector, leading to damaged infrastructure, reduced funding, and limited operational capacity. Many dams, pumping stations, and canals have been partially or completely destroyed, and governance structures have weakened due to fragmented authority and resource scarcity. The conflict has also exacerbated water scarcity by reducing access to transboundary rivers like the Euphrates and increasing unregulated groundwater extraction in conflict-affected areas¹⁷³.

Responsibilities within the MOI are distributed among seven General Directorates based on hydrological basin delineations, with a relatively conducive environment for decentralized water management at the basin level compared to neighboring countries. The General Directorates

¹⁶⁸ FAO. (2019). *Forests under pressure: The impact of conflict on forest ecosystems in Syria*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

¹⁶⁹ Qandeel, M., & Sommer, J. (2022). *Syria Conflict and its Impact: A Legal and Environmental Perspective*. *Journal of International Humanitarian Legal Studies*.

¹⁷⁰ Government of Syria. (2005). *Decree No. 3 of 2005: Regulation of water use and protection*. Syrian Ministry of Irrigation.

¹⁷¹ Government of Syria. (2005). *Law No. 31 of 2005: Water resource management in Syria*. Syrian Ministry of Irrigation.

¹⁷² National Water Strategy (2008–2030). (2008). *Integrated water resource management for Syria*. Syrian Ministry of Irrigation and Ministry of Agriculture.

¹⁷³ FAO. (2020). *Syria: Water resources and irrigation*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

oversee the planning, design, operation, and maintenance (O&M) of irrigation projects, including dams, canals, and pumping stations. For smaller-scale irrigation projects, feasibility studies are conducted by Irrigation Divisions within General Directorates and assessed by the Central Directorate of Water Resources and Irrigation. For larger-scale projects, international consulting firms are engaged via bidding processes, with the Central Directorate supervising the review process.

Key government organizations involved in water management include the Ministry of Irrigation, the Ministry of Agriculture and Agrarian Reform, and the Farmers Unions. The Ministry of Housing and Utilities also plays a role in the water supply and sewerage sectors. However, despite these frameworks, the absence of adequate coordination and feedback among these entities has hindered effective water management. Blurred lines of responsibility and accountability, coupled with the impacts of the ongoing conflict, have further complicated the operational landscape of Syria's water sector.

Figure 17 Organizational Chart of Ministry of Irrigation in Syria

1.5.3.2 Energy Sector Institutional Frameworks

As part of the national energy strategy, renewable energy was incorporated as early as 2002, when the government set a target for renewable sources to account for 4.3% of the nation's total primary energy supply by 2011. Moreover, in the Five-Year Plan covering 2011 to 2015, the utilization of renewable resources was emphasized as a pivotal element in the establishment of power generation facilities. In addition to policy initiatives, a project by the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) focusing on Supply-side Efficiency and Energy Conservation and Planning was executed between 1999 and 2005¹⁷⁴. The incorporation of renewable energy into Syria's national energy

¹⁷⁴International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). (2017). Country Nuclear Power Profiles 2017 Edition: Syrian Arab Republic. IAEA. Retrieved from <https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/cnpp2017/countryprofiles/SyrianArabRepublic/SyrianArabRepublic.htm>

strategy is guided by Law No. 18 of 2010, which establishes the framework for renewable energy development and private sector participation in energy projects. This law promotes investment in renewable technologies and outlines incentives for renewable energy projects, including solar, wind, and biomass. Additionally, Decree No. 49 of 2006 regulates electricity tariffs and encourages energy efficiency measures^{175 176}. The Five-Year Plan emphasizing renewable resources was severely disrupted by the Syrian conflict, which began in 2011. The conflict led to the destruction of infrastructure, reduced investment in renewable energy projects, and a lack of operational capacity to implement the outlined initiatives. As a result, many renewable energy projects planned during this period were either postponed or abandoned¹⁷⁷.

The Ministry of Electricity oversees investment, tariff setting, planning, and policy development within the power sector (see Figure 18). The power system is managed by the Public Establishment for Electricity (PEE), which comprises two main divisions: PEEGT (Generation and Transmission) and PEDEEE (Distribution and Exploitation of Electrical Energy). PEEGT is responsible for transmission activities, operating at the 400 kV and 230 kV levels, while PEDEEE supervises operations at the 66 kV, 20 kV, and 0.4 kV levels. Consequently, PEEGT serves customers at the 230 kV level, including large industries and irrigation, while all other customers fall under the purview of PEDEEE.

PEDEE is further subdivided into 14 regional distribution authorities, tasked with distribution and exploitation of electrical energy. PEEGT manages electricity generation and transmission, accounting for 88% of the total electricity production, whereas PEDEEE oversees sales and distribution activities. The organizational structure of the Ministry of Electricity is depicted below.

¹⁷⁵ Government of Syria. (2010). Law No. 18 of 2010: Framework for Renewable Energy Development. Syrian Ministry of Electricity.

¹⁷⁶ Government of Syria. (2006). Decree No. 49 of 2006: Regulation of Electricity Tariffs and Energy Efficiency. Syrian Ministry of Electricity.

¹⁷⁷ IRENA. (2021). Renewable energy development in conflict-affected regions: Syria case study. International Renewable Energy Agency.

Figure 18 Chart illustrating the organizational structure of the Ministry of Electricity in Syria

1.5.3.3 Food and Agriculture institutional frameworks

The Ministry of Agriculture and Agrarian Reform (MAAR) holds a crucial position in irrigation, offering guidance to farmers on agricultural practices, water utilization, and extension services. MAAR also provides basic extension and research services to farmers. Within MAAR, the Department of Irrigation and Water Use (DIWU) is tasked with researching crop water needs, farm water management techniques, and advancements in irrigation methods and technology. The DIWU conducts extensive nationwide research focusing on crop water requirements, farm water management, and advancements in irrigation methods and technologies. With seven research stations strategically located in the seven river basins, the DIWU tailors its research programs to the specific water, soil, crop, and climatic conditions of each basin. Various activities are undertaken in the realm of irrigation techniques and methods, including technology transfer initiatives in collaboration with the local Department of Extension, featuring field days and seminars. Collaborative research endeavors with ICARDA, particularly on supplementary irrigation (SI), are conducted at the Sirbaya research station of the DIWU in Aleppo. Similarly, research on drainage and the reuse of drainage water is conducted at the Deir es Zor station in the Euphrates basin. The activities of the MAAR align with Law No. 31 of 2005, which governs water resource management in Syria and highlights the role of ministries in sustainable irrigation practices. Additionally, Decree No. 49 of 2006 establishes the legal framework for agricultural water use efficiency and modern irrigation adoption, emphasizing collaboration between ministries for water resource

optimization^{178 179}. These policies underscore the importance of the research and extension activities undertaken by MAAR and its DIWU.

Moreover, in 2017, the DIWUs research station in the capital established a computerized laboratory aimed at testing locally manufactured modern irrigation equipment (such as drip and sprinkler systems) free of charge¹⁸⁰. However, the testing process requires formalization and linkage to the Ministry of Industry for standardization and formal certification. Additionally, research has commenced on the reuse of treated wastewater in irrigation. Nonetheless, there is minimal coordination between the research conducted by the Ministry of Irrigation (MOI) and that of the Ministry of Agriculture and Agrarian Reform (MAAR).

1.5.3.4 Environmental Sector institutional frameworks

The Ministry of Local Administration and Environment oversees all activities related to environmental protection, including efforts to combat climate change. Additionally, the ministry is responsible for managing water supplies and implementing measures to address desertification.

It has been reported that a critical necessity for developing a comprehensive plan for water quality management and pollution control is the establishment of a robust water quality monitoring network. Currently, the monitoring network operated by the Department of Pollution Control (DPC) of the Ministry of Irrigation (MOI) focuses solely on surface water quality (such as rivers, lakes, reservoirs, and coastal areas), with occasional monitoring of groundwater quality carried out on an ad-hoc basis. The proposed draft water law by the MOI in 2019 includes provisions concerning water pollution control and legal measures against violations¹⁸¹. While the enforcement of this law would undoubtedly aid in pollution control, it alone may not suffice without being part of a comprehensive framework. Such a framework should encompass strengthened monitoring capacities, wastewater treatment and reuse, enhanced water quality management, intersectoral coordination, development of appropriate standards for wastewater disposal, active involvement of stakeholders, and increased public awareness regarding the risks associated with maintaining the status quo.

Collaboration with the Ministry of Local Administration and Environment is also crucial to identify major sources of pollution and critical areas of concern.¹⁸²

1.5.3.5 Interlinkages and gaps

Syria's national policies and legal frameworks are interconnected across various sectors, but several gaps hinder effective implementation and integration. There is a strong emphasis on integrating environmental, energy, water, and food policies to achieve sustainable development. For instance, water policies are linked to agricultural practices, and energy policies promote using renewable resources to support environmental sustainability. Effective governance requires coordination among different ministries, such as the Ministry of Water Resources, the Ministry of Agriculture, and

¹⁷⁸ Government of Syria. (2005). Law No. 31 of 2005: Water resource management in Syria. Ministry of Agriculture and Agrarian Reform.

¹⁷⁹ Government of Syria. (2006). Decree No. 49 of 2006: Regulation of agricultural water use efficiency. Ministry of Irrigation.

¹⁸⁰ FAO. (2017). Enhancing irrigation technologies in Syria: Establishment of a computerized laboratory for testing irrigation equipment. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

¹⁸¹ Government of Syria. (2019). Draft water law: Provisions for pollution control and legal enforcement. Ministry of Irrigation.

¹⁸² World Bank Group. (2001). Syrian Arab Republic Irrigation Sector Report. World Bank Group. Retrieved from <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/248751468777620327/pdf/multi0page.pdf>

the Ministry of Environment. Integrated water resource management (IWRM) is a process in which multiple sectors collaborate to optimize water usage and conservation efforts.

Reported gaps exist in Syria’s national policies related to policy implementation, resource allocation, data monitoring, and community involvement hinder the effectiveness of these frameworks. Addressing these gaps requires coordinated efforts, international support, and robust governance mechanisms to ensure the successful integration and execution of policies¹⁸³.

The integration of Syria’s national policies across sectors is guided by key legal frameworks. Notable among these is Law No. 31 of 2005, which provides the foundation for integrated water resource management (IWRM), emphasizing sustainable water use and coordination between sectors¹⁸⁴. Decree No. 49 of 2006 supports water resource efficiency and sustainable agricultural practices, particularly through modern irrigation systems¹⁸⁵. Additionally, Law No. 18 of 2010 establishes the legal basis for renewable energy integration into Syria’s energy policy, promoting environmental sustainability¹⁸⁶. However, gaps in the enforcement and harmonization of these legal frameworks hinder their effectiveness.

1.5.4 Socio-Economic Situation

Syria has a total population of 23.23 million capita in 2023 , of which 50.2% are male and 49.8% are female. As of 2023, 62.8% of the population is aged between 15 and 64, while children under 15 make up 33% of the population and those over 65 years old make up 4.2%. Syria has a population growth rate of 1.67%, with the population concentrated along the coast of the Mediterranean. Only 57.4% of the population is urban, with major urban areas including Damascus, Aleppo, and Hums¹⁸⁷.

Syria’s economy is being impacted by the ongoing conflict and imposed sanctions by the US. Unemployment rate is at 13.8%, with 82.5% of the population below the poverty line¹⁸⁷. Table 17 shows the socio-economic indicators in Syria in 2021.

Table 17 Socio-Economic Indicators - Syria

Indicator	Value ¹⁸⁸
GDP (USD Billion)	8.97
GDP per Capita (USD)	420.6
GDP from Agriculture (%)	27.82
GDP from Mining (%)	28.91
GDP from Services (%)	43.27
Inflation Rate (%)	36.7
Unemployment Rate (%)	13.5
Youth Unemployment Rate (%)	33.99

¹⁸³Nilsson, M., et al. (2022). Interlinkages, integration, and coherence. In Cambridge University Press eBooks (pp. 92–115). <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009082945.005>

¹⁸⁴ Government of Syria. (2005). Law No. 31 of 2005: Integrated water resource management. Syrian Ministry of Irrigation.

¹⁸⁵ Government of Syria. (2006). Decree No. 49 of 2006: Water efficiency and modern irrigation systems. Syrian Ministry of Agriculture.

¹⁸⁶ Government of Syria. (2010). Law No. 18 of 2010: Renewable energy integration. Syrian Ministry of Electricity.

¹⁸⁷CIA. (2024). Syria. The World Factbook. Retrieved July 3, 2024, from <https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/countries/syria/#economy>

¹⁸⁸Statista. (2024). Share of economic sectors in the GDP in Syria 2021. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/326616/share-of-economic-sectors-in-the-gdp-in-syria/#:~:text=In%202021%2C%20the%20share%20of,sector%20contributed%20about%2043.27%20percent.>

1.5.5 Recommendations

This section is the author's recommendations based on the outcomes of the literature review summarized above. These recommendations were developed considering the limited financial and logistical capacities of the Syrian government.

- Water Sector

Syria needs to address its water scarcity and infrastructure issues to mitigate the growing water risks. Immediate efforts should focus on rebuilding damaged water infrastructure, improving maintenance, and modernizing irrigation systems to reduce water loss. Given the country's semi-arid climate and the variability in precipitation, efficient water management practices, such as rainwater harvesting and better storage facilities, should be promoted to maximize the use of available water. Additionally, investment in wastewater treatment and reuse can help alleviate pressure on fresh water sources, especially in agriculture.

Syria also faces significant challenges related to climate change, which will increase the frequency of droughts and floods. The government must develop a comprehensive water management strategy that incorporates climate adaptation measures. Collaboration with neighboring countries, particularly in managing transboundary water resources like the Euphrates, is essential for ensuring a sustainable water supply. Strengthening governance and establishing clear regulations on water usage can also help reduce inefficiencies and prevent over-extraction.

- Energy Sector

To reduce its energy risks, Syria must prioritize the restoration and modernization of its damaged energy infrastructure. Rebuilding power plants, repairing pipelines reforming energy policy, building institutional capacity, and upgrading outdated transmission networks should be key priorities to ensure reliable electricity supply and reduce outages, taking into considerations issues like conflicts, economic constrains, and lack of investments. Modernization efforts should also focus on reducing inefficiencies in transmission and distribution, which contribute to frequent power losses. In addition, investing in renewable energy sources like solar and wind can help diversify Syria's energy mix and reduce reliance on vulnerable oil and gas supplies, taking into considerations about resource availability, technological readiness, and financing mechanisms.

Geopolitical challenges, such as disputes over transboundary water and energy resources, must be addressed through diplomatic efforts. Cooperation with neighboring countries, particularly Türkiye and Iraq, is crucial for stabilizing Syria's energy supply, especially in areas dependent on hydropower. Furthermore, the government should explore ways to mitigate the impacts of international sanctions, such as increasing local energy production and improving energy efficiency across sectors to reduce dependence on imported fuels and technologies.

- Food Sector

Syria must rebuild its agricultural infrastructure to restore food security, addressing critical challenges such as land degradation, climate variability, and water scarcity. The conflict has destroyed farmland, irrigation systems, and supply chains, making integrated solutions essential.

Restoring soil fertility and adopting climate-resilient farming practices, such as drought-resistant crop varieties and efficient irrigation techniques (e.g., drip irrigation), can mitigate resource constraints. These practices should be introduced through extension services, public-private partnerships, and international support to ensure accessibility for farmers. Food security is deeply tied to water management and energy availability. Solar-powered irrigation systems and improved water governance, guided by Law No. 31 of 2005, can stabilize production while reducing reliance on fossil fuels. National policies must align agricultural, water, and energy strategies, while institutional reforms in governance, such as enhanced coordination between the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of Irrigation, are critical. Reviving wheat and barley production will strengthen self-sufficiency, while targeted food assistance programs and regional cooperation on shared resources are essential to address immediate needs and secure Syria's long-term food supply.

- Ecosystem Challenges

Syria must take immediate steps to protect and restore its damaged ecosystems, which have been severely impacted by conflict and unsustainable practices. Restoration efforts should focus on rehabilitating the Al Badia steppe, where overgrazing and erosion have degraded the land. Initiatives to replant native shrubs and grasses can help prevent further soil erosion and restore habitat for wildlife. Additionally, protecting wetlands and river ecosystems like those around the Euphrates is crucial for preserving biodiversity and supporting migratory bird species. This should be carried out with government support and oversight. The ongoing conflict has also worsened pollution and waste management issues, impacting public health and the environment. Syria needs to rebuild its waste management and water treatment infrastructure to reduce pollution and improve water quality. Addressing the environmental impacts of refugee camps and informal settlements by providing adequate sanitation and waste disposal facilities is also essential to prevent further environmental degradation. Efforts to restore ecosystems will not only benefit biodiversity but also help sustain agriculture and water resources in the long term.

- Addressing Interlinkages and Gaps in the WEFE Nexus

Syria's national policies emphasize integrating environmental, energy, water, and food sectors to promote sustainable development, but gaps in policy implementation and coordination remain. To effectively address these interlinkages, Syria must establish formal mechanisms to improve collaboration between key ministries, including the Ministry of Water Resources, Ministry of Agriculture, and Ministry of Environment. Mechanisms such as inter-ministerial committees, guided by a centralized authority like the National Council for Sustainable Development, can ensure regular communication and alignment of strategies. Additionally, implementing integrated resource management platforms for data sharing and planning can reduce overlaps. Clearly delineating roles and responsibilities through legislative frameworks, such as updated amendments to Law No. 31 of 2005, will also be critical to avoid conflicts and improve accountability in resource management.

Key gaps, such as poor resource allocation, insufficient data monitoring, and lack of community involvement, hinder the effectiveness of Syria's integrated management frameworks. Addressing these issues requires not only national efforts but also international support to provide technical

and financial assistance. Enhancing data collection and monitoring systems will improve decision-making, while involving local communities in water and energy conservation projects will increase the sustainability and effectiveness of national policies.

1.6 Türkiye

1.6.1 Country Overview

Türkiye is a transcontinental nation that spans two continents (Europe and Asia). The Bosphorus, the Sea of Marmara, and the Dardanelles (which together form a water link between the Black Sea and the Mediterranean), divide Asian Türkiye from European Türkiye (Figure 19). Asian Türkiye makes up 97% of the country while the remaining 3% of the country is called European Türkiye, which is Rumelia (or Eastern Thrace) that lies on the Balkan Peninsula. Türkiye's total area is 783,562 square kilometres, of which 23,764 square kilometres are in Europe and 759,798 square kilometres are in Southwest Asia. The Mediterranean Sea borders Türkiye on the south, the Black Sea borders it to the north, and the Aegean Sea borders it to the west. The Sea of Marmara lies to the northwest of Türkiye. Eight nations border Türkiye: Iraq and Syria to the southeast; Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Iran to the east; Bulgaria to the northwest; Greece to the west; and Georgia to the northeast¹⁸⁹.

Figure 19 Türkiye country map (source: Worldometer)¹⁹⁰

The varied topography of the country, particularly the presence of mountains running parallel to the coasts, causes notable variations in the climate from one area to other. The inland Anatolian plateau experiences extremes of hot summers and cold winters with little rainfall, while the coastal areas enjoy milder climates. Most of the Türkiye's rainfall falls during the winter. During this season, the

¹⁸⁹K.T. Üniversitesi. (n.d.). About Türkiye - Geography and climate | International Studies. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://www.ktu.edu.tr/obsen/aboutturkeygeographyandclimate>

¹⁹⁰Worldometer. (n.d.). World map. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from https://www.worldometers.info/world-map/#google_vignette

average temperature is typically below 5°C with minimal evaporation. Winters along the Aegean and Mediterranean coasts receive between 500 to 1300 mm of rainfall annually. The coast of the Black Sea receives the greatest amount reaching around 2200 mm annually in its eastern parts. The climate in Istanbul and the surrounding area of the Sea of Marmara is moderate, with summer temperatures reaching 27°C and winter temperatures dropping below zero. Western Anatolia experiences mild Mediterranean winter temperatures of 9°C and summer temperatures of 29°C on average. Anatolia's southern coast experiences comparable weather conditions. Around the Black Sea, the weather is humid and rainy (summer 23°C, winter 7°C)¹⁹¹.

In 2023, the population in Türkiye is about 86.2 million with a 0.52% growth rate¹⁹². At 2,900 inhabitants per square kilometer, Istanbul has the highest population density of any province. Kocaeli, with 528 people/km², and İzmir, with 360 people/km². The percentage of people living in provincial and district centers is around 93 % while 7% of people live in rural areas¹⁹³.

1.6.2 WEFE Situation

1. Water

a. Water Resources (Internal and Cross boundary)

Türkiye receives roughly 574 mm of precipitation on average per year, or 450 billion cubic metres (BCM) of water. Of this, 45 BCM seep into aquifers and 219 BCM evaporate. 181 BCM of the total are combined with surface water from lakes and rivers. 41 BCM are extracted from groundwater that contributes to surface water, and this amount is included in the water budget, whereas 6 BCM originate from neighbouring countries. Türkiye has a 239 BCM total water potential. This equates to 2,515 cubic meters of renewable water resources per capita annually. Of the 239 BCM total available water resources, 112 BCM is the total usable potential (95 BCM surface waters, 17 BCM groundwaters). Table 18 below details all water resources in Türkiye. Water Stress in Türkiye is at 47%¹⁹⁴.

Table 18 Water resources in Türkiye 2020¹⁹⁵

Water resource	Value
Total renewable groundwater (MCM/year)	67,800
Total renewable surface water (MCM/year)	171,800
Total renewable water resources (MCM/year)	239,600
Desalinated water produced (MCM/year)	21
Treated municipal wastewater (MCM/year)	4,358

There are twenty-five hydrological basins in Türkiye, as shown in Figure 20 below. Each of these basins has a distinct catchment area and a broad range of variables related to annual precipitation, evaporation, and surface runoff. River discharges are therefore unpredictable. Sixteen rivers originate in the mountains inside Türkiye's borders and flow into the Marmara, Mediterranean, Black, and Aegean seas. There is no outflow to the sea from the Konya Basin, Akarçay Basin, Burdur Lakes, or Lake Van, as they are closed basins. The main transboundary basins are the Çoruh,

¹⁹¹Sensoy, Serhat&Demircan, Mesut. (2016). Climate of Türkiye.

¹⁹² World Bank. (2023). World development indicators: Türkiye population statistics. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/turkey>

¹⁹³Worldometer. (2024). Türkiye population (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/Türkiye-population/>

¹⁹⁴ DSI (State Hydraulic Works of Türkiye). (2023). Water resources management in Türkiye: Annual precipitation, water potential, and water stress overview. www.dsi.gov.tr.

¹⁹⁵ Fanack Water (2023), Water Resources in Turkey,. <https://water.fanack.com/Türkiye/water-resources-in-Türkiye/>

Euphrates-Tigris, Maritza, Orontes (Asi), and Araks-Kura basins. Türkiye has 320 natural lakes, some being seasonal, meaning that they get more precipitation in the winter and less in the summer, which causes them to dry out. The largest lakes are The largest lakes in Türkiye include Lake Eğirdir (482 km²), Lake Beyşehir (656 km²), Lake Tuz (Salt Lake, 1,665 km²), and Lake Van (3,713 km²)¹⁹⁶.

Figure 20 The 25 Catchments of Türkiye (source: Fanack Water¹⁹⁵)

There are 370,000 certified wells as of the end of 2020, with 38,100 for domestic use, 17,900 for industrial use and 314,000 for irrigation. The Groundwater Law of 1962 governs groundwater resources. Under this law, the state is responsible for managing groundwater resources. This law also addresses the use, registration, research, and protection of these waters. Wells must all be registered, but it can be challenging to stop unauthorised well digging. Türkiye's groundwater resources are mostly utilised for irrigation¹⁹⁷.

Five transboundary river basins exist in Türkiye. The Çoruh River Basin, Aras and Kura River Basin, Euphrates-Tigris River Basin, Asi (Orontes) River Basin, and Meriç (Maritza) River Basin are the ones that run from north to south. Due to these basins' transboundary features, Türkiye views them as having a significant role in international relations. Transboundary waters make up slightly more than 36 percent of Türkiye's total water potential. One of the most significant river basins in Türkiye and the Middle East is the Euphrates-Tigris River Basin. The combined average annual discharge of the Euphrates and Tigris rivers is 84 BCM. Ninety percent of Türkiye's water comes from the Euphrates, with an average yearly flow of 32 BCM. 10% of it is sourced from Syria. The Tigris has an average annual flow of 52 BCM. As the principal riparian countries of the Euphrates-Tigris River Basin,

¹⁹⁶ DSI (State Hydraulic Works of Türkiye). (2023). Lakes and water bodies in Türkiye: Dimensions and official names. Retrieved from www.dsi.gov.tr

¹⁹⁷ Yeraltı Suları Hakkında Kanun (Law on Groundwater), 2011. DSI Yeraltı Suları Teknik Yönetmeliği. Retrieved from www.dsi.gov.tr

Türkiye, Syria, and Iraq rely heavily on it for food, energy, and drinking water. While Syria and Iraq treat the Euphrates and Tigris Rivers as separate basins, Türkiye views them as one¹⁹⁸.

b. Water Use by sector

Türkiye has 18 billion cubic metres of operating groundwater reserves, of which only 16.62 billion cubic meters have been used. Of these, 11.21 billion cubic meters are used for agricultural irrigation (private, public, and cooperative), 1.49 billion cubic meters are used for industrial water, and 3.92 billion cubic meters are used for drinking water¹⁹⁹.

In Türkiye, agriculture consumed the largest share of water at 67.5% in 2020. While the municipal sector consumed 23.5% of water resources and the remaining 9% was consumed by the industrial sector (Figure 21).

Figure 21 Water consumption by sector in Türkiye in 2021²⁰⁰

c. Water risk

As Türkiye's economy and population expand, so do the challenges associated with managing its water resources. Almost all river basins are experiencing an increase in demand on their supply and quality of water. Water management requires more than hydraulic engineering and technical solutions; it requires integrated water resource management involving institutional, economic, environmental, and social aspects. Türkiye uses water far less efficiently than nations with higher incomes. For example, Türkiye generates approximately \$2,000 in GDP per cubic meter of water used, which is about 40% of the \$5,000–\$6,000 GDP per cubic meter achieved by high-income

¹⁹⁸Devlet Su İşleri (DSİ). (2020). Retrieved from www.dsi.gov.tr.

¹⁹⁹ Anadolu Agency. (2020). Condition for controlled consumption of groundwater. Retrieved from <https://www.aa.com.tr/tr/turkiye/yer-alti-sularina-kontrollu-tuketim-sarti/1773890>

²⁰⁰ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (n.d.). Country profile - Turkey. AQUASTAT. Retrieved December 3, 2024, from <https://www.fao.org/aquastat/en/countries-and-basins/country/TURR>

countries such as Germany and Japan. In many river basins, excessive water is drawn from surface and groundwater due to inefficient use of water in agriculture²⁰¹.

Water resource pollution in Türkiye remains a significant challenge due to untreated or partially treated wastewater from both industrial and residential sources. According to recent estimates, approximately 13.4 BCM of wastewater are discharged annually into natural water bodies, with 65% of industrial wastewater and 82% of residential wastewater undergoing treatment²⁰²

2. Energy

a. Supply

In 2021, Türkiye's total energy supply was 1,785,054.72 GWh, with 80% of this supply being imported, primarily in the form of natural gas, crude oil, and petroleum products. The majority of these imports came from Russia, which accounted for approximately 45% of Türkiye's natural gas imports and a significant portion of its crude oil. Other key suppliers included Iran, Azerbaijan, and Iraq, which together provided substantial amounts of natural gas and oil to meet Türkiye's energy demand²⁰³. (see Figure 22 and Table 19).

Table 19 Energy supply per resource in 2021 – Türkiye²⁰³

Energy Resource	Energy Supply (GWh)	%
Coal	448,784.44	25.14
Natural gas	488,760.28	27.38
Hydro	67,195.28	3.76
Wind, solar, etc.	206,179.17	11.55
Biofuels and waste	60,751.67	3.40
Oil	513,383.89	28.76
Total	1,785,054.72	100.00

²⁰¹Baris, M. E., & Karadag, A. A. (2007). Water resources management issues in Türkiye and recommendations. *Journal of Applied Sciences*, 7(24), 3900–3908. <https://doi.org/10.3923/jas.2007.3900.3908>

²⁰²TurkStat. (2023). Wastewater statistics in Türkiye: Annual discharge and treatment ratios. Turkish Statistical Institute. <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Water-and-Wastewater-Statistics-2020-37197&dil=2>

²⁰³ International Energy Agency. (2022). Türkiye energy profile: Energy supply and infrastructure. Retrieved from <https://www.iea.org/countries/turkiye>

Figure 22 Energy supply in Türkiye 2021 (source: IEA²⁰³)

b. Demand

Energy consumption per sector is highlighted in Table 20 and Figure 23, showing the industrial sector as the largest energy consumer.

Table 20 Energy consumption per sector in 2021 – Türkiye (source: IEA²⁰³)

Sector	Energy Consumption (GWh)	%
Industry	427,200.00	31.91
Transport	347,586.39	25.96
Residential	276,391.67	20.64
Commercial and public services	163,370.56	12.20
Agriculture / forestry	57,473.33	4.29
Fishing	1,542.78	0.12
Non-energy use	65,316.67	4.88
Total	1,338,881.39	100.00

Figure 23 Energy consumption per sector in Türkiye 2021 (source: IEA²⁰⁴)

c. Energy risk

The economy of Türkiye is significantly influenced by the energy sector, which plays a central role in industrial development and economic stability. On one hand, Türkiye's industry and income levels have grown rapidly, albeit erratically, resulting in a corresponding rise in energy demand. However, the country imports the majority of its energy due to its limited domestic fossil fuel resources. This dependency creates severe economic vulnerabilities, as fluctuating global energy prices directly impact industrial costs and household energy expenses, thereby influencing inflation and economic growth. Furthermore, reliance on imports exposes Türkiye to external political risks, as major energy-exporting countries like Russia, Iran, and Iraq can potentially use energy supplies as a tool for political leverage²⁰⁴.

Türkiye's geostrategic position between Europe and the Middle East's leading energy producers, such as Russia and the Caspian Basin, enhances its importance in the global energy market. Its borders host five critical international pipelines:

1. Kirkuk-Ceyhan Oil Pipeline: Transports oil from Iraq to the Mediterranean coast.
2. Baku-Tiflis-Ceyhan Oil Pipeline: Connects Azerbaijan's oil resources to the Mediterranean.
3. Türkiye-Iran Gas Pipeline: Delivers natural gas from Iran.
4. Blue Stream Gas Pipeline: Transports Russian gas to Türkiye.
5. Southern Gas Corridor Pipeline: Carries natural gas from Azerbaijan to Italy.

While this infrastructure underscores Türkiye's critical role as a transit state, it also highlights vulnerabilities. Energy security—defined as the continuous availability of energy at reasonable costs—faces potential threats from geopolitical conflicts in the Middle East and the use of energy exports as political tools by countries like Russia. Additionally, Türkiye's aspiration to transform into an "energy hub" where buyers and sellers convene for free trade, or where Turkish businesses could

²⁰⁴ International Energy Agency. (2022). Türkiye energy profile: Energy supply and infrastructure. Retrieved from <https://www.iea.org/countries/turkiye>

profit by reselling imported gas, requires significant investments in infrastructure and internal market liberalization²⁰⁵.

Internally, the heavy reliance on energy imports constrains industrial development. High energy costs reduce competitiveness in manufacturing and other industries, making it more difficult for Türkiye to attract foreign investments. To mitigate these challenges, Türkiye must enhance its domestic energy production capacity, expand renewable energy projects, and liberalize its energy market to reduce import dependency²⁰⁶.

3. Food

a. Supply

Türkiye is the world's largest producer of apricots and hazelnuts, contributing over 65% of the world's hazelnut production and nearly 25% of apricots annually. It is also a significant global producer of wheat, sugar beets, milk, chicken, cotton, tomatoes, rice, and other fruits and vegetables. For example, Türkiye produces approximately 20 million tonnes of wheat annually, making it a vital part of its domestic food supply and export economy²⁰⁷. Similarly, domestic rice production totals approximately 900,000 tonnes annually, primarily grown in the Thrace region to meet a significant portion of domestic demand²⁰⁸. Additionally, Türkiye produces 2.5 million tonnes of sugar beets, placing it among the world's top five producers²⁰⁸. The food production sector has shown steady growth over the past decade, with the number of food-producing businesses increasing by 12% between 2013 and 2020. Revenue in TRY terms rose significantly during this period; however, sales volumes in USD terms declined in 2015 and 2017 due to exchange rate fluctuations. Cotton production, vital for Türkiye's advanced textile industry, averages 800,000 tonnes annually. While this largely meets domestic demand, Türkiye occasionally imports additional cotton to supplement its textile production needs. Locally grown fruits, vegetables, grains, and rice form the backbone of Türkiye's agricultural sector, supporting its domestic market and lucrative export industry.

b. Demand

Türkiye's growing population and rapidly industrializing economy have created strong demand for both raw agricultural materials and processed food products. The country imports 140,000 tonnes of rice annually, primarily from India, Pakistan, and the United States, to meet consumer preferences and fill gaps in domestic production²⁰⁹. Additionally, soybeans and oilseeds, amounting to over 2.5 million tonnes annually, are imported to supply its meat and poultry industries, which have expanded significantly in recent years²¹⁰. These imports are critical for supporting Türkiye's production of poultry and livestock feed, ensuring the consistent availability of meat products domestically. Other consumer-oriented imports include dried beans, almonds, walnuts, bananas, coffee, cocoa, meat, fish, and various processed foods. These materials also supply Türkiye's bakery, food processing, and confectionery industries. For example, raw materials for pasta, pastries, and

²⁰⁵ World Bank. (2023). The impact of energy imports on Türkiye's economy and industrial competitiveness.

²⁰⁶ European Commission. (2021). Türkiye's role in European energy security and the Southern Gas Corridor.

²⁰⁷ FAO. (2021). Türkiye's Food Supply and Agricultural Production. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

²⁰⁸ TurkStat. (2022). Agricultural Statistics in Türkiye: Annual Report 2022. Turkish Statistical Institute. <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Crop-Production-Statistics-2022-45504&dil=2>

²⁰⁹ FAO. (2021). Türkiye's Food Supply and Agricultural Production. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

²¹⁰ OECD. (2023). Türkiye's Agricultural Imports and Industry Dynamics. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. <https://www.oecd.org/en/countries/turkiye.html>

confectionery production support Türkiye's robust export market, which includes \$1.15 billion in wheat flour exports and \$1.52 billion in pasta and pastry exports in 2021.

c. Food security

The three pillars of ensuring food security are accessibility, availability, and affordability. In Türkiye, accessibility and availability are not major concerns, however, affordability has been recently impacted due to the large inflation in the Turkish market in 2023²¹¹. In recent years, inflation in Türkiye has significantly impacted food affordability. Inflation surged to 36.08% in 2021 and further climbed to 64.27% in 2022, driven by rising energy costs, currency depreciation, and global supply chain disruptions. Although it began stabilizing in 2023, with a forecast of 43.68%²¹². Türkiye's food and agricultural industries combined are net exporters. In addition, Türkiye's retail industry has grown significantly over the past ten years.

Türkiye has a relatively low poverty rate, with only 0.4% of the population living below the international poverty line of \$2.15 per day²¹³. The country achieves 93% self-sufficiency in fruit and vegetable production, meeting its domestic needs effectively²¹⁴. However, harvest and post-harvest losses account for 14–20% of total agricultural output, particularly in perishable goods like fruits and vegetables, which highlights a significant area for improvement²¹⁵. Reducing these losses through better storage, transportation, and handling could make a major contribution to food security for Türkiye and the global market. Türkiye meets adequate standards and focuses on food safety, protein quality, and financial accessibility in its food programs, reducing malnutrition risk across its population²¹⁴.

Türkiye's own food security can be compromised due to the pressure that climate change puts on the food-water-energy nexus which causes Türkiye's water availability to decrease, threatening Türkiye's lucrative food export earnings and its place in global food supply chains. Türkiye's production of cereal grains, especially wheat, maize, and barley, is a vital component of its role as a food supplier to Europe and the MENA area. When it comes to water requirements, these grains are far more than vegetables.

4. Ecosystem

Türkiye boasts an exceptionally rich and unique biodiversity, and is made up of various biogeographic regions, each with its own natural ecosystems, and microclimatic zones. The country has a diverse range of flora and fauna, many of which are endemic. Türkiye's genetic diversity is significant because it lies at the meeting point of the Near Eastern and Mediterranean gene centres. Numerous domestic animal races originated in Anatolia and eventually dispersed throughout the world, contributing to the genetic resources of animals. In terms of plant endemism, Türkiye is a top contender. There are roughly 33% of plant species that are unique to Türkiye. Türkiye has a great deal of responsibility because of the exceptional amount of endemism to make sure that these species are sufficiently protected to prevent extinction. In addition, Türkiye's forest areas have grown as a result of extensive

²¹¹ World Bank. (2023). Türkiye's Economic Challenges: Inflation and Food Security.

²¹² Gazetesi, E. (2023). Inflation in Turkey: 43.68 per cent according to the government, 105.19 per cent according to independent researchers. Evrensel.net. <https://www.evrensel.net/daily/489058/inflation-in-turkey-43-68-per-cent-according-to-the-government-105-19-per-cent-according-to-independent-researchers>

²¹³ World Bank. Türkiye Poverty and Equity Brief - April 2024 (English). Poverty and Equity Brief Washington, D.C. : World Bank Group. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/099061224142029970/P1800971fc6f6d08b1867a13dae6c3c00df>

²¹⁴ FAO. (2021). Türkiye's Food Supply and Agricultural Production. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

²¹⁵ TurkStat. (2022). Post-Harvest Losses and Agricultural Efficiency in Türkiye. Turkish Statistical Institute.

afforestation programmes, which also support efforts to stop desertification²¹⁶. The following are Türkiye's main ecosystems:²¹⁷

- **Balkan Mixed Forests.**

These forests have a humid subtropical and warm summer continental climate, with relatively high rainfall occurring in some regions. Most of the mixed forests found in the Balkans are dominated by deciduous oaks. European beech and conifers like silver firs and Scots pines grow in the upper reliefs. In the highest peaks, alpine tundra vegetation is also present.

- **Caucasus Mixed Forests**

A variety of plant and animal species can be found in the mixed forests of the Caucasus. The area is mostly home to the Caucasian grouse and the Caucasian tur. Here also reside predators including Asian leopards, bears, and wolves. In addition to two wetlands that are essential for wetland animals and waterfowl, the forests are home to around 1500 indigenous plant species. The sustainability of the environment is threatened by human activity and improper management of the forests, Nonetheless, steps are being taken to manage, safeguard, and control these imperiled ecosystems and biomes.

- **Central Anatolian Deciduous Forests**

Cranes and avocets are among the migratory species who consider this region home. Waterfowl like the White Pelican have breeding grounds and habitats due to the lakes and ponds. High plateaus and mountains dominate the area, and in the fall, golden Türkiye oak trees cover the untamed landscape, giving it a distinctive yellow hue. The Turkish chamois, mountain meadows, and marbled polecat are just a few of the creatures that call the ecoregion home.

- **Northern Anatolia Conifer and Deciduous Forests**

These ecosystems are found in Türkiye's northwest, where the summers are warm, and the winters are cold with adequate precipitation. Most of the areas are dominated by evergreen conifers and coniferous forests. The forests' moisture levels encourage the growth of mosses, shrubs, and ferns. The main trees include Kauri, Douglas fir, Sitka spruce, and coast redwood. The Dalmatian pelican, black stork, and purple heron rely on the conifer and deciduous woods of Northern Anatolia, making it an important bird region.

- **Eastern Anatolian Montane Steppe**

The biome of the ecoregion is composed of shrublands, savannas, and temperate grasslands. The region has snowy winters and warm, dry summers. Two sizable salt lakes in the rough ecoregion are important to the environment because they serve as bird breeding sites. The ecoregion is home to a wide variety of plants, including nut trees and fruits like wild pears and grapes. These regions are home to birds like the Peregrine falcon and Golden eagle, reptiles like Armenian vipers, and mammals including Marbled polecats and striped hyenas. The ecology has been degraded by industrialization and agriculture, and additional reserves are required to safeguard the variety of habitats and nearly extinct species. The area's swamps have been converted to agricultural land.

²¹⁶European Environment Agency. (2015). Türkiye country briefing - The European environment — state and outlook 2015. Retrieved from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/soer/2015/countries/turkey>

²¹⁷Sawe, B. E. (2017). Ecological regions of Türkiye. WorldAtlas. Retrieved from <https://www.worldatlas.com/articles/ecological-regions-of-Türkiye.html>

- **The Aegean and Western Türkiye Sclerophyllous and Mixed Forests**

These Mediterranean-style forests, woodlands, and shrubs are found along Türkiye's western coast. Their summers are dry, and their winters are rainy. The different types of vegetation include shrublands, forests, woodlands, and savannahs. The majority of the trees in the forest are broadleaf species like oaks, along with some sclerophyllous and coniferous trees.²¹⁸

1.6.3 National Policies and Legal Framework

1.6.3.1 Water Sector Institutional frameworks

The development of water resources stands out as a pivotal sector in modern Türkiye's institutional framework. Its significance in propelling economic growth and fostering social advancement has consistently received prominent attention at the political level. Türkiye's water security policy encompasses a range of strategic objectives, including boosting agricultural output and ensuring food security, fulfilling the escalating water demands of both urban and rural populations as well as industry, reducing reliance on imported energy sources, addressing regional, economic, and social disparities within the nation, and elevating living standards for its populace²¹⁹.

Türkiye's water security policy framework delineates distinct parameters and is executed through well-established institutions. A variety of public, private, and non-governmental bodies have been established to secure water for agricultural and hydropower development, domestic and industrial purposes, and environmental preservation. Foremost among these institutions is the Directorate General of State Hydraulic Works (DSI), operating under the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MAF), which has overseen Türkiye's water resources development and management since 1954. The DSI's mission encompasses the efficient utilization of Türkiye's water resources, mitigating losses from floods and droughts, and the comprehensive development of land and water resources, guided by scientific and technical principles and national interests.

The General Directorate of State Hydraulic Works (DSI) serves as the principal executive state agency in Türkiye for overall water resources planning, management, execution, and operation. Established under the Ministry of Public Works, it possesses a separate budget and legal personality, tasked with multiple objectives including irrigation, flood prevention, power generation from water, examination and approval of water supply and sewerage designs for urban areas, conducting research, surveys, and assessments related to soil types, crop cultivation, and agricultural productivity. Branch directorates and operational organizations are established in alignment with this legislation.

Conversely, the Ministry of Health plays a pivotal role in Türkiye's water sector, dating back nearly a century ago when improving public health was a paramount concern for the young Republic. As early as 1926, the Ministry of Health formulated the Law on Waters, leading to significant investments in drinking water supply and swamp drainage. Key responsibilities of the Ministry of Health include setting quality standards for drinking and domestic water, monitoring compliance, enacting legislation in these areas, and overseeing environmental protection and urban wastewater management in alignment with public health objectives²¹⁹.

²¹⁸European Environment Agency. (2015). Türkiye country briefing - The European environment — state and outlook 2015. Retrieved from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/soer/2015/countries/turkey>

²¹⁹Kıbaroğlu, A. (2022). Türkiye's water security policy: Energy, agriculture, and transboundary issues. *Rethinking Environmental Security*, 24(Spring), 69–88. <https://doi.org/10.25253/99.2022242.5>

1.6.3.2 Energy Sector Institutional Frameworks

The Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources (MENR) plays a vital role in shaping and executing energy policies throughout Türkiye, collaborating with associated institutions as well as public and private entities. At the forefront of this endeavor is the General Directorate of Energy Affairs (EIGM), serving as the principal policymaking entity within MENR. EIGM conducts comprehensive research on various aspects of energy, including overarching policies, market dynamics, renewable energy sources, fossil fuels, energy efficiency, and environmental considerations. Additionally, it oversees the coordination of electricity and natural gas reform initiatives, addressing the impacts of previous endeavors to attract private investments into the electricity sector.

Moreover, the regulatory framework is reinforced by organizations such as the General Directorate of Petroleum Affairs (PIGM), responsible for overseeing exploration and production activities in the oil and natural gas sectors. Furthermore, the Electrical Power Resources Survey and Development Administration (EIE), operating under MENR's jurisdiction, actively promotes initiatives aimed at enhancing energy efficiency and harnessing renewable energy sources. Meanwhile, the Energy Market Regulatory Authority (EMRA) assumes a crucial role as the regulatory body overseeing electricity, natural gas, oil, and liquefied petroleum gas markets, ensuring equitable and transparent market practices. Additionally, the competition authority retains jurisdiction to grant authorizations pertaining to mergers or acquisitions within the market, fostering a competitive landscape. The institutions in Türkiye's energy sector is depicted in Figure 24 below.²²⁰

Figure 24 Key Institutions in Türkiye's Energy Sector

²²⁰European Commission. (2019). Türkiye EU support to the Energy sector. Retrieved March 13, 2024, from https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2019-12/c_2019_8726_ad_energy.pdf

1.6.3.3 Food and Agriculture institutional frameworks

The Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, a governmental body of the Republic of Türkiye, assumes responsibility for overseeing agricultural and forestry matters within the country. The Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry's General Directorate of Food and Control collaborates with various authorities to undertake diverse projects aimed at ensuring a dependable supply of food and feed. These initiatives involve formulating policies, inspecting their implementation, and enforcing principles for food traceability, food additives, and materials used in food production, processing, and marketing. Measures are taken to safeguard consumers and public health by addressing plant, animal, food, and feed safety concerns. This includes practices and oversight related to plant health, evaluation of the biological impacts of approved pesticides, enhancements in monitoring and controlling Salmonella in poultry and food products, improvements to national food safety systems, regional collaboration efforts, and strengthening control mechanisms.

In addressing food safety, waste management, and sustainability challenges in Türkiye, numerous stakeholders contribute to various initiatives. The initiatives addressing food safety, waste management, and sustainability in Türkiye align with the country's broader national policies, such as the National Agricultural Strategy and the Food Safety Action Plan. These policies prioritize safe food production, waste reduction, and sustainable agricultural practices. Stakeholders, including food manufacturers, processors, inspectors, academic institutions, and professionals in the food sector, collaborate through webinars, training sessions, projects, and meetings to enhance food safety controls and promote public awareness, thereby supporting the objectives outlined in national strategies^{221,222,223}.

Additionally, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) collaborates with the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry in Türkiye, along with food safety authorities in other nations, on issues related to food and feed safety within the EFSA's scope of responsibilities.²²⁴

1.6.3.4 Environmental Sector institutional frameworks

The Ministry of Environment and Urbanization (MoEU) serves as the primary National Focal Point for climate change matters and acts as the coordinating governmental entity for issues pertaining to climate change within Türkiye. It is tasked with aligning national environmental legislation with that of the European Union (EU) and ensuring its effective implementation.

Established with the objectives of formulating necessary legislation concerning settlement areas, environmental concerns, and the settlement process itself, the Ministry of Environment and Urbanization (MoEU) oversees urban transformation projects, conducts inspections on relevant practices, enhances vocational services, prevents environmental pollution, and safeguards both the environment and nature. With the transition to the Presidential Government System, entities such as the Housing Development Administration (TOKİ) Directorate, Directorate General of National

²²¹ Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. (2018). Strategic Plan 2018–2022. Retrieved from <https://leap.unep.org/en/countries/tr/national-legislation/strategic-plan-2018-2022-ministry-food-agriculture-and-livestock>

²²² Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. (2020). National Strategy Document on Prevention, Reduction and Monitoring of Food Loss and Waste. Retrieved from <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/2d810e01-en/1/3/2/25/index.html>

²²³ UN Food Systems Summit. (2021). National Pathway of Türkiye. Retrieved from <https://www.unfoodsystemshub.org/docs/unfoodsystemslibraries/national-pathways/turkey/2021-12-22-en-designed-edition-booklet-national-pathway-of-turkiye.pdf>

²²⁴ Özkan, G., & Capanoglu, E. (2022). Food safety, waste management, and sustainability issues in Türkiye. *eFood*, 3(4). <https://doi.org/10.1002/efd2.23>

Property, and the newly formed General Directorate of Local Authorities have been incorporated into the Ministry of Environment and Urbanization.

Climate change initiatives are carried out by the Ministry of Environment and Urbanization through the inter-ministerial Coordination Board on Climate Change (CBCC). Established in 2001 following a circular issued by the Prime Ministry, the CBCC holds overarching responsibility for implementing policies aimed at prevention, mitigation, and adaptation to climate change. It is also tasked with fulfilling obligations under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), including the preparation of National Communications on Climate Change. Consequently, the CBCC plays a crucial role in fostering dialogue among various stakeholders engaged in climate change-related activities.²²⁵

1.6.3.5 Interlinkages and gaps

To achieve sustainable development, integrating policies related to the environment, energy, water, and food is highly prioritized. For example, energy policies encourage the use of renewable resources to support environmental sustainability, and water policies are related to agricultural practices. Türkiye's dependence on hydropower and the water-intensive extraction and processing of fossil fuels have resulted in a close relationship between water and energy. Significant water resources are needed for Türkiye's energy production, especially in the oil and gas industries²²⁶.

The absence of integrated management frameworks that consider the interdependencies between water, energy, food, and ecosystems is one of the main weaknesses in Türkiye's WEFE nexus policies. Policies are frequently created in groups, which results in competing goals and ineffective resource use.

1.6.4 Socio-Economic Situation

Türkiye has a total population of 82,482,383 people, with the majority (43%) aged 25-54 years old. Those aged 15-24 make up 15.67% of the population, whereas children under 15 make up 23.41%. Further, adults aged 55-64 comprise 9.25%, and elders above the age of 64 make up 8.35% of the population. The country has a population growth rate of 0.7%, and the most densely populated area is found around the Bosphorus in the northwest. 76.6% of total population is urbanized, with major urban areas including Istanbul and Ankara cities²²⁷.

Türkiye's economy is significant. It belongs to the OECD and the G20 and is categorised by the World Bank as an upper-middle-income nation. With strengths in manufacturing, agriculture, and tourism, Türkiye's economy is diverse but has to also deal with issues like excessive inflation and foreign imbalances. Türkiye's economy is a hybrid, combining traditional agriculture with contemporary industry and trade. It is distinguished by an emerging market status, a solid private sector, and significant state involvement in important industries. The largest contributor to the Turkish GDP is the service sector, which includes retail, banking, and tourism. After this sector comes industry, which includes construction and manufacturing. Agriculture also has a significant role though a smaller one than in services and industry. Table 21 includes more data on Türkiye's economy.

²²⁵European Commission. (2011). Support to Mechanism for Monitoring Türkiye's Greenhouse Gas Emissions. Retrieved March 13, 2024, from https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2016-12/tr2011.0327.21_monitoring_ghg_emissions-.pdf

²²⁶Akpınar, A. (2013). The contribution of hydropower in meeting electric energy needs: The case of Türkiye. *Renewable Energy*, 51, 206–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2012.09.049>

²²⁷Central Intelligence Agency. (2021). *Türkiye - The World Factbook*. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/about/archives/2021/countries/Türkiye/#economy>

Table 21 Socio-Economic Indicators - Türkiye

Indicator	Value ^{228,229}
GDP (USD Trillion)	1.024
GDP per Capita (USD)	11.939
Inflation Rate (%)	48.58
Unemployment Rate (%)	10.3
Youth Unemployment Rate (%) (<24 years)	22.5

1.6.5 Recommendations

This section is the author’s recommendations based on the outcomes of the literature review summarized above.

- **Water Sector**

Türkiye needs to adopt more efficient water use practices, particularly in agriculture, to address growing water demand and pollution. Modernizing irrigation systems to reduce water wastage and investing in technologies like drip irrigation or precision farming will help conserve water. Additionally, improving wastewater treatment and promoting the reuse of treated water for agricultural or industrial purposes can reduce the strain on natural water bodies. Integrated water resource management (IWRM) should be expanded to involve institutional, economic, environmental, and social dimensions to ensure sustainable water use.

Pollution control must also be prioritized, as untreated wastewater from industrial and residential areas continues to degrade water quality. Strengthening enforcement of pollution control laws and expanding wastewater treatment infrastructure, especially for industrial sectors, will help protect Türkiye’s water resources. Moreover, promoting public awareness of water conservation and efficiency can contribute to better water management practices across all sectors.

- **Energy Sector**

Türkiye should focus on diversifying its energy sources, reducing its reliance on imported fossil fuels, and increasing its renewable energy capacity. Investments in solar, wind, and geothermal energy can help reduce Türkiye’s exposure to geopolitical risks and energy supply disruptions, especially from countries like Russia and Iran. Additionally, Türkiye can further leverage its strategic position as a transit hub by investing in infrastructure and liberalizing its internal energy market to potentially become an energy trading hub for Europe and the Middle East.

At the same time, upgrading and modernizing energy infrastructure is essential to improve efficiency and reduce transmission losses. Given its geopolitical importance and heavy reliance on energy imports, Türkiye must also prioritize diplomatic relations with energy-exporting nations and work on securing stable energy supply chains. Encouraging energy conservation programs and increasing energy efficiency in industries and households can also help reduce overall energy demand.

²²⁸World Bank. (n.d.). Overview: Türkiye. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/Türkiye/overview>

²²⁹ Trading Economics. (2024). Turkey inflation rate. Retrieved November 28, 2024, from <https://tradingeconomics.com/turkey/inflation-cpi>

- Food Sector

To improve food security, Türkiye needs to focus on reducing food loss and waste during harvest and post-harvest stages. Investing in better storage facilities, transportation systems, and food processing technologies can help minimize losses and improve food availability. This will not only enhance Türkiye's food security but also strengthen its position as a key food exporter to Europe and the Middle East. At the same time, addressing food affordability is crucial, especially given the recent rise in inflation. Implementing targeted subsidies or price control mechanisms can help ease the burden on consumers.

Additionally, Türkiye must develop strategies to protect its agricultural sector from the impacts of climate change, particularly its water-intensive cereal crops like wheat and barley. Promoting crop diversification and improving water use efficiency in agriculture will help maintain Türkiye's food production capacity, even under challenging environmental conditions. These measures will support both domestic food security and export earnings.

- Ecosystem Challenges

Türkiye should continue expanding its afforestation and reforestation programs to combat desertification and protect biodiversity. These efforts should be complemented by stronger protection measures for critical ecosystems, including the Balkan Mixed Forests and the Anatolian steppes. Türkiye's rich biodiversity, particularly its high number of endemic plant species, must be preserved through conservation programs and habitat protection to prevent further loss of species. Strengthening the management of protected areas and increasing public awareness of conservation efforts will be key steps in achieving these goals.

Furthermore, combating the degradation of ecosystems due to industrialization and unsustainable agricultural practices requires stricter enforcement of environmental regulations. Türkiye should establish more protected reserves, especially in areas like Eastern Anatolia, where industrial expansion and agriculture have significantly impacted ecosystems. These measures will not only preserve biodiversity but also help maintain ecosystem services that are vital for agriculture and water management.

- Addressing Interlinkages and Gaps in the WEFE Nexus

Türkiye must develop a comprehensive framework that integrates the management of water, energy, food, and ecosystems (WEFE) to address the challenges of sustainability and resource efficiency. Current policies often function in silos, resulting in conflicting objectives and inefficient use of resources. Creating an integrated WEFE nexus approach will enable Türkiye to better balance the needs of its agricultural, industrial, and environmental sectors. For instance, promoting the use of renewable energy in agriculture can reduce water consumption and enhance sustainability. National policies and legal frameworks should be adapted by incorporating sector-specific strategies, enhancing enforcement mechanisms, and fostering inter-agency coordination to effectively address these issues.

Türkiye should also focus on the synergies between water and energy, as water plays a critical role in energy production, particularly in hydropower and fossil fuel extraction. By adopting energy-efficient technologies and reducing water usage in energy sectors, Türkiye can optimize its resource management. Additionally, increasing research and data collection on the interdependencies between these sectors will allow for more informed policy decisions that support long-term sustainable development.

WEFE Nexus successful and unsustainable practices

1.7 Successful Practices

This section examines successful practices, showcasing examples where the WEFE Nexus approach has been effectively applied to enhance resource efficiency, promote environmental sustainability, and improve socioeconomic outcomes. These cases serve as models of best practices, illustrating how integrated strategies can yield long-term benefits across sectors. Table 22 below showcases these practices.

Table 22 Successful WEFE NEXUS projects

No.	Project	Country	Sectors	Overview	Outcomes
1	As Samra Wastewater Treatment Plant ²³⁰	Jordan	Water, Energy	<p>The As Samra Wastewater Treatment Plant in Jordan (Figure 25) is a significant public-private partnership initiative aimed at addressing water scarcity by treating wastewater and reusing it for agricultural purposes. Constructed between 2003 and 2008, the plant underwent an expansion completed in 2015, significantly increasing its capacity to treat wastewater using advanced biological treatment processes. The facility also generates biogas from sludge digestion, which is used to produce electricity.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 25 As Samra Wastewater Treatment Plant</i></p>	<p>The plant now treats about 267,000 cubic meters of wastewater per day, with a peak capacity of 365,000 cubic meters following its expansion. This treated water is primarily used for irrigation in the Jordan Valley, helping to alleviate water scarcity and support agriculture in the region. The project has been recognized with several awards for its innovative financing and significant impact on water and energy management in Jordan.</p>
2	The Shahid Abbaspour Dam ²³¹	Iran	Water, Energy	<p>The Shahid Abbaspour Dam, also known as Karun-1, is a cornerstone of Iran's infrastructure, strategically positioned on the Karun River in Khuzestan Province. This dam is essential in the water-energy nexus, standing 200 meters tall with a primary focus on hydroelectric power generation and flood control. Annually, it produces over 2,000 megawatts of electricity, serving as a key renewable energy source for the region. The reservoir, with a capacity of 3.1 billion cubic meters, plays a pivotal role in water resource management, supporting agricultural activities downstream through regulated water release, which secures a consistent water supply for irrigation.</p>	<p>The Shahid Abbaspour Dam has made substantial contributions to the energy sector in Iran by supplying clean, renewable hydroelectric power and lessening reliance on fossil fuels. The energy produced is crucial for both residential and industrial needs within the area. Moreover, the dam's ability to control water flow has enhanced agricultural productivity in neighboring regions by providing dependable irrigation water, even during dry spells. This regulation supports the irrigation of about 340,000 hectares of farmland, vital for growing key crops such as wheat, barley, and sugarcane. Additionally, the dam is instrumental in flood management, safeguarding local</p>

²³⁰ World Bank. (2022). Jordan: As-Samra Wastewater Plant Expansion. https://ppp.worldbank.org/public-private-partnership/sites/ppp.worldbank.org/files/2022-06/P3Briefs_JordanAsSamraWastewaterPlantExpansion.pdf

²³¹ Shourijed, P. T., Soroush, A., Nemati, N., & Izad-doustdar, A. H. (2006). Karun River hydropower cascade development and its socio-environmental impacts. In L. Berga et al. (Eds.), *Dams and reservoirs, societies and environment in the 21st century* (Vol. 1). Taylor & Francis Group. <https://www.fid-bau.de/en/research/search/id/BLCP:CN063417334?cHash=4be62b52fc0dff8541244d19c0747286>

communities and farmlands from seasonal flooding, which has historically caused extensive damage in the region

Figure 26 The Shahid Abbaspour Dam

3	Al Rawafed Agriculture Organic Farm ²³²	UAE	Water, Food, Ecosystem	<p>Al Rawafed Agriculture Organic Farm (Figure 27), is a vibrant example of sustainable agriculture in a region predominantly characterized by its desert environment. Spanning 50 hectares, this farm utilizes organic farming techniques to cultivate a diverse range of crops including tomatoes, bell peppers, lettuce, herbs, bananas, and even grapes. Established on previously arid land, the farm represents a significant transformation, turning a desert landscape into a productive and sustainable agricultural enterprise. The farm is dedicated to producing organic food without the use of synthetic pesticides or fertilizers, instead employing natural methods such as garlic and chili water sprays and introducing beneficial insects to control pests</p>	<p>Al Rawafed Agriculture Organic Farm significantly contributes to the local food supply in Abu Dhabi, delivering nearly ten tons of fresh produce daily to supermarkets and restaurants. This output includes a variety of vegetables and fruits, all grown organically. The farm's practices not only support the sustainability goals of the region but also provide a model for organic agriculture in arid environments. By leveraging innovative agricultural techniques and focusing on organic certification, the farm ensures high-quality produce that meets both local and European standards. The success of Al Rawafed is part of a broader movement in the UAE to increase self-sufficiency in food production and reduce reliance on food imports</p>
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²³² Sankar, A. (2016). Inside a 50-hectare organic farm in Abu Dhabi. Gulf News. Retrieved from <https://gulfnews.com/uae/environment/inside-a-50-hectare-organic-farm-in-abu-dhabi-1.1830514>

Figure 27 Rawafed Agriculture Organic Farm

4	Southeastern Anatolia Project (GAP) ²³³	Türkiye	Water, Energy, Food	<p>The Southeastern Anatolia Project (GAP) is Türkiye’s largest integrated regional development initiative, designed to harness the water, energy, and agricultural potential of the Tigris and Euphrates river basins. The project involves the construction of 22 dams and 19 hydroelectric plants with a combined energy capacity of over 7,500 megawatts. The project also aims to provide irrigation to over 1.7 million hectares of land, constituting one-fifth of Türkiye’s irrigable land, with the goal of boosting agricultural production and regional development. GAP spans multiple sectors, integrating hydropower, irrigation, agriculture, transportation, telecommunications, and social infrastructure. This \$32 billion project has been a cornerstone of Türkiye’s efforts to reduce regional disparities and increase the economic output of its southeastern provinces.</p>	<p>The project has significantly increased agricultural productivity by irrigating large swaths of previously arid land. The hydroelectric plants are contributing over 27 billion kilowatt-hours of electricity annually, making GAP a crucial part of Türkiye’s energy mix. The improved water management and energy generation have raised living standards in the southeastern region, reducing economic disparities. However, GAP has also sparked tensions with downstream nations, particularly Iraq and Syria, due to reduced water flow along the Tigris and Euphrates Rivers. Despite these challenges, GAP is viewed as a model for integrated water-energy-food management, with its multi-sectoral approach supporting both local development and national growth.</p>

²³³ Altınbilek, H. (1997). Water and Land Resources Development in Southeastern Türkiye . International Journal of Water Resources Development, 13, 311-332. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07900629749719>.

Figure 28 GAP Project Locations (source: Rufin et.al., 2021²³⁴)

5	The Jordan Hydroponic Agriculture and Employment Development Project (HAED-Jo) ^{235,236}	Jordan	Water, Food, Energy	<p>The Jordan Hydroponic Agriculture and Employment Development Project (HAED-Jo) (Figure 29) is a significant initiative aimed at enhancing agricultural efficiency and creating employment opportunities within Jordan. Funded by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Netherlands, the project commenced in 2017 with a focus on integrating advanced agricultural technologies like hydroponics into Jordanian farming practices. This initiative primarily targets the resilience of communities hosting Syrian refugees by improving local horticulture productivity and expanding economic opportunities in the agricultural sector.</p>	<p>HAED-Jo has successfully implemented various technological advancements in agriculture, notably in hydroponic systems, which are particularly suited to arid and semi-arid climates like Jordan's. These systems significantly reduce water and fertilizer use, thereby increasing the sustainability of agricultural practices. The project has also fostered the development of improved greenhouse technologies that enhance climate control and pest management, which extends the growing season and improves both the quality and quantity of produce. Additionally, HAED-Jo emphasizes capacity building and skills development, providing training to farmers, agricultural engineers, and local workers, which enhances their ability to operate advanced agricultural systems effectively.</p>

²³⁴ Rufin, Philippe & Müller, Daniel & Schwieder, Marcel & Pflugmacher, Dirk & Hostert, Patrick. (2021). Landsat time series reveal simultaneous expansion and intensification of irrigated dry season cropping in Southeastern Türkiye . Journal of Land Use Science. 16. 1-17. 10.1080/1747423X.2020.1858198.

²³⁵ Jordan Hashemite Charity Organization. (2020). Fact sheet on humanitarian aid and development projects. Retrieved from https://www.haed-jo.org/sites/default/files/resource_file/2020-04/1_haed-jo-en-fact-sheet_0.pdf

²³⁶ Ozkahraman, C. (2017). Water power: the domestic and geostrategic dimensions of Türkiye 's GAP Project. Conflict, Security & Development, 17, 411 - 428. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14678802.2017.1371988>.

Figure 29 Jordan Hydroponic Agriculture and Employment Development Project (source: ECO Consult²³⁷)

6	Mosul Dam ^{238,239}	Iraq	Water, Energy	<p>The Mosul Dam, located on the Tigris River approximately 60 kilometers north of Mosul, is Iraq’s largest dam and one of its most crucial infrastructure projects. Completed in 1986, the dam stands 113 meters high and stretches 3.4 kilometers across, creating a reservoir with a storage capacity of 11.1 billion cubic meters. It is a multipurpose dam designed for hydroelectric power generation, irrigation, and flood control. The dam has an installed capacity of 750 megawatts, providing substantial hydroelectric power for northern Iraq. In addition to power generation, the dam supports vast agricultural lands downstream by regulating water flow, which is crucial for irrigation.</p>	<p>The Mosul Dam contributes significantly to Iraq’s energy supply, generating power for approximately 1 million households. It plays a vital role in supporting agricultural production by irrigating hundreds of thousands of hectares of farmland. Additionally, the dam helps manage seasonal flooding along the Tigris River, protecting communities and infrastructure downstream. However, the dam faces major structural challenges due to its foundation, which is built on soluble gypsum, anhydrite, and marl, leading to ongoing risks of erosion and subsidence. Since its completion, the dam has required continuous grouting to stabilize its foundation and prevent failure. Emergency grouting efforts, particularly in 2016, helped avert a potential disaster, and ongoing international efforts continue to mitigate these risks</p>
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²³⁷ ECO Consult. (2020). Saydat Bani Kinana. HAED-Jo. <https://www.haed-jo.org/page/saydat-bani-kinana>

²³⁸ Vargas, J., Sawitzki, D., & Malyala, N. (2022). Mosul Dam: Challenges and Innovative Solutions. E3S Web of Conferences. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202234603025>.

²³⁹ Milillo, P., Bürgmann, R., Lundgren, P., Salzer, J., Perissin, D., Fielding, E., Biondi, F., & Milillo, G. (2016). Space geodetic monitoring of engineered structures: The ongoing destabilization of the Mosul dam, Iraq. Scientific Reports, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep37408>.

Figure 30 Mosul Dam

7	Wadi Al Arab Water Supply Project II ^{240,241}	Jordan	Water, Energy, Ecosystem	<p>The Wadi Al Arab Water Supply Project II, located in the northwest of Jordan (Figure 31), is a critical infrastructure initiative designed to alleviate water scarcity in the northern governorates, including Irbid, Ajloun, Jerash, and Mafraq. This project is crucial due to Jordan's severe water deficit issues and the increasing demands from population growth and the influx of refugees. The project's primary components include the construction of an intake facility on the King Abdullah Canal, a water treatment plant, and a transmission pipeline that delivers treated water to the Zabda Reservoir in Irbid</p>	<p>The Wadi Al Arab Water Supply Project II has significantly improved water supply and quality for approximately 1.1 million residents in the target regions. The project outputs an initial 10 million cubic meters of water annually, with expectations to increase to 30 million cubic meters at full capacity, covering 60% of the area's potable water needs. The comprehensive treatment facilities and advanced conveyance systems ensure the provision of high-quality water, crucial for both daily use and agricultural needs in these predominantly arid regions</p>

²⁴⁰ European Investment Bank. (2015). WADI AL ARAB WATER SYSTEM II PROJECT. European Investment Bank. Retrieved from <https://www.eib.org/en/projects/pipelines/all/20140150>

²⁴¹ CDM Smith. (2020). Wadi Arab II. CDM Smith. Retrieved from <https://www.cdmsmith.com/en/Client-Solutions/Projects/Wadi-Arab-II>

Figure 31 Wadi Al Arab Water Supply Project II

8	Al Khobar Desalination Plant, Saudi Arabia ^{242,243}	Saudi Arabia	Water, Energy	<p>The Al Khobar Desalination Plant, located on Saudi Arabia's east coast (Figure 32), is a crucial part of the country's efforts to address its acute water scarcity. The plant, developed by ACCIONA in collaboration with the Saline Water Conversion Corporation (SWCC), utilizes reverse osmosis (RO) technology to desalinate seawater. The project is divided into two phases: Al Khobar 1 and Al Khobar 2. Al Khobar 1, completed in 2020, has a capacity of producing 210,000 cubic meters of potable water per day. Al Khobar 2, one of the largest desalination plants globally, produces 630,000 cubic meters of water daily, serving a population of about 3 million people. The RO technology used at both plants is highly energy-efficient, emitting significantly fewer greenhouse gases compared to traditional thermal desalination</p>	<p>The Al Khobar Desalination Plant has greatly improved water security for the eastern region of Saudi Arabia. It provides potable water for the cities of Khobar, Dammam, and Dhahran, supporting local industries and households. The energy-efficient reverse osmosis process ensures that the plant meets water demand while minimizing environmental impacts. Moreover, the project has fostered job creation and skill development within the local community, particularly through the use of advanced technologies such as digital twin systems, which enhance operational efficiency. This plant plays a pivotal role in Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030, which aims to modernize the country's water infrastructure and reduce per capita water consumption by 43% by 2030</p>
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²⁴² Pradeep, A. (2021). Project profile: Al Khobar 1 SWRO desalination plant. ME Construction News. Retrieved from <https://meconstructionnews.com/46277/project-profile-al-khobar-1-swro-desalination-plant>

²⁴³ ACCIONA. (2021). SWRO Al Khobar II. ACCIONA. Retrieved from <https://www.aciona.com/projects/swro-al-khobar-ii/>

Figure 32 Al Khobar Desalination Plant (source: ACCOINA²⁴⁴)

9	Tabqa Dam and Hydropower Project ^{245,246}	Syria	Water, Energy	<p>The Tabqa Dam, situated on the Euphrates River near Al-Thawra in northern Syria, is a cornerstone of Syria's water and energy infrastructure. Completed in 1973, the dam is 60 meters tall and spans 4.5 kilometers across the river. It creates Lake Assad, Syria's largest artificial reservoir, with a storage capacity of 11.7 billion cubic meters. The dam's hydroelectric plant has an installed capacity of 880 megawatts, providing a substantial portion of northern Syria's electricity. Beyond energy production, the dam supports irrigation for over 640,000 hectares of agricultural land, essential for the region's food security, and helps regulate water flow to prevent seasonal floods along the Euphrates River</p>	<p>The Tabqa Dam remains crucial to Syria's electricity grid, especially for cities like Raqqa and Aleppo. Its irrigation support allows for productive farming in Syria's arid regions, contributing significantly to the nation's agricultural output. However, the ongoing Syrian conflict has disrupted the dam's operations multiple times, leading to maintenance challenges and temporary shutdowns. Control of the dam has shifted between various factions, causing occasional interruptions in electricity supply and water management. Despite these challenges, the dam continues to play a critical role in Syria's water-energy-food nexus, although reduced water flow from upstream in Türkiye and regional water shortages pose significant risks to its long-term sustainability</p>
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²⁴⁴ ACCIONA. (2020). ACCIONA completes the construction of the Al Khobar I desalination plant in Saudi Arabia. <https://www.acciona.com/updates/news/acciona-completes-construction-al-khobar-desalination-plant-saudi-arabia/>

²⁴⁵ Global Energy Monitor. (2020). Tabqa Dam hydroelectric plant. Global Energy Monitor. Retrieved from https://www.gem.wiki/Tabqa_Dam_hydroelectric_plant

²⁴⁶ European University Institute. (2021). EU-Türkiye relations: Towards a renewed and modernized partnership? European Commission. Retrieved from <https://cadmus.eui.eu/bitstream/handle/1814/72182/QM-02-21-984-EN-N.pdf?sequence=8>

Figure 33 Tabqa Dam (source: Zaman al-Wasl²⁴⁷)

				<p data-bbox="1433 1012 2009 1052">Figure 33 Tabqa Dam (source: Zaman al-Wasl²⁴⁷)</p>
10	Sundrop Farms in Port Augusta ²⁴⁸	Australia	Water, Energy, Food, Ecosystem	<p data-bbox="566 1075 1745 1312">Sundrop Farms in Port Augusta, South Australia (Figure 34), represents a groundbreaking approach to sustainable agriculture, utilizing advanced technologies to grow crops in arid regions using renewable resources. Founded with the construction of a pilot facility in 2009, Sundrop Farms has expanded to a 20-hectare site that integrates solar power, desalination, and hydroponics to produce high-quality fruits and vegetables without relying on soil, fossil fuels, or groundwater. This innovative system harnesses sunlight and seawater to meet all its energy and water needs, proving a model for sustainable agriculture that could be replicated globally</p> <p data-bbox="1745 1075 2902 1312">Sundrop Farms has achieved significant production capacity, yielding 10-15% of Australia's truss tomatoes. The facility, powered by a Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) system, is capable of generating fresh water and electricity while minimizing environmental impact. The solar thermal plant at Sundrop Farms produces heat, fresh water, and 1.5 MWe of electricity, contributing to the farm's sustainability goals. This model of farming not only provides a consistent supply of fresh produce but also demonstrates the potential for reducing agriculture's dependence on finite natural resources</p>

²⁴⁷ Zaman al-Wasl. (2017). Former Tabqa Dam engineer claims collapse is imminent. The Syrian Observer. https://syrianobserver.com/foreign-actors/former_tabqa_dam_engineer_claims_collapse_imminent.html

²⁴⁸ Sundrop Farms Pty Ltd. (2024). A fresh way of growing: Redefining sustainable greenhouse production of fresh fruits and vegetables. Sundrop Farms. Retrieved from <https://www.sundropfarms.com/>

Figure 34 Sundrop Farms in Port Augusta (source: Centuria²⁴⁹)

11	Al Baydha Project ²⁵⁰	Saudi Arabia	Food, Ecosystem	<p>The Al Baydha Project in Saudi Arabia (Figure 35), initiated in 2009, represents a groundbreaking approach to combat desertification and foster economic sustainability in a harsh desert environment. The project employs regenerative agriculture techniques to revitalize the arid landscapes near Mecca. By incorporating traditional water conservation methods alongside modern ecological practices like rainwater harvesting, rock terraces, and the planting of drought-resistant species, Al Baydha aims to transform degraded lands into fertile, productive territories</p>	<p>Al Baydha has achieved notable environmental and social successes. Ecologically, the project has significantly reduced erosion, restored native vegetation, and increased biodiversity, turning barren desert into savannah-like ecosystems. This restoration effort has helped stabilize the soil, improve water retention, and create habitats for local wildlife. Socially, the project has empowered the local Bedouin community by providing training and employment opportunities in sustainable farming techniques, thereby fostering economic resilience and food security. Additionally, the project has received recognition for its innovative approaches to sustainable land management and its role as a model for similar arid regions</p>
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Figure 35 Al Baydha Project (source: Strickler, D ²⁵¹)

²⁴⁹ Centuria Capital Group. (2023). Alternatives drive Centuria's FY23 growth. <https://centuria.com.au/news/alternatives-drive-centurias-fy23-growth/>

²⁵⁰ Kresh, M. (2020). The Al Baydha project: How regenerative agriculture revived green life in a Saudi Arabian desert. Green Prophet. Retrieved from <https://www.greenprophet.com/2020/08/the-al-baydha-project-how-regenerative-agriculture-revived-green-life-in-a-saudi-arabian-desert>

²⁵¹ Strickler, D. (2023). Designing for drought resilience. AgSpire. <https://agspire.com/designing-for-drought-resilience/>

1.8 Unsustainable Practices

This section addresses unsustainable practices, highlighting cases where the implementation of WEFE-related projects has led to unintended negative consequences, such as resource depletion, environmental degradation, or social inequity. In examining these challenges, a focus on the lessons learned from these experiences, emphasizing how future Nexus projects can avoid similar pitfalls and strive for more holistic and equitable solutions. Table 23 below highlights a number of unsustainable practices, illustrating the issues and lessons learnt.

Table 23 Unsustainable practices and lessons learnt

	Example	Country	Result	Lessons Learnt
1	Salinization of the soil of the agricultural lands due to inefficient irrigation systems, decreased flow in the Euphrates and Tigris, and inadequate drainage infrastructure.	Iraq	High levels of soil salinity have reduced agricultural productivity (affecting 70% of irrigated lands), making it difficult to grow crops like wheat and rice. Moreover, 30% of farmlands have been abandoned due to salinity, exacerbating food insecurity. ²⁵² .	The introduction of modern irrigation systems and proper drainage infrastructure is critical to reversing soil degradation and improving agricultural productivity. The establishment of a National Center for Agricultural Policy, the introduction of desalination technologies like Bio-Electro-remediation and Reverse electro-dialysis, should also be considered as potential solutions ²⁵³ .
2	The inequality of shared transboundary water resources among the riparian countries led to resource over-exploitation and increased potential for conflict over water ²⁵⁴ .	Iran, Iraq, Türkiye	Significant water and food insecurity due to weak planning, compounded by increasing demands from population growth and urbanization.	Cooperation between countries is essential for sustainable management of shared water resources, and integrated planning across water, energy, and food sectors can alleviate insecurity.
3	The Mesopotamian Marshes in southern Iraq have experienced severe drying and salinization due to natural factors like low rainfall and human interventions, including dam construction and deliberate draining ²⁵⁵ .	Iraq	This desiccation has led to significant ecological damage, threatening biodiversity and altering migration patterns of various species.	Coordinated water-sharing agreements with neighboring countries, combined with improved irrigation techniques to reduce salinity, are key to restoring the marshes. Adequate water resources are necessary to support the restoration of the marshes.
4	The agricultural sector in Syria has encountered major difficulties due to the lack of government support, insufficient investments, and the ongoing conflict. These challenges have resulted in reduced productivity, and an increased dependency on imports.	Syria	The ongoing conflict has caused extensive damage to agricultural infrastructure, leading to a notable drop in food production and agricultural output. These compounding issues pose a significant threat to long-term sustainability in semi-arid areas ²⁵⁶ .	There is an opportunity to enhance sustainability by diversifying cropping systems, particularly in regions with different water availability and climatic conditions. To overcome these challenges, it is crucial to implement effective policies that promote sustainable practices, invest in agricultural infrastructure, and support local farmers. Rebuilding the agricultural sector is vital for Syria's economic recovery and ensuring food security ²⁵⁷ .
5	Groundwater overexploitation in Iran has resulted in severe aquifer depletion, causing	Iran	The overexploitation of groundwater has led to severe consequences, including soil salinity,	To overcome this crisis, experts suggest developing a consistent and effective legal framework to regulate groundwater use. Additionally,

²⁵² Qureshi, Asad & Al-Falahi, Adnan. (2015). Extent, Characterization and Causes of Soil Salinity in Central and Southern Iraq and Possible Reclamation Strategies. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications*. Vol. 5, Issue 1(Part 1)..

²⁵³ Ahmed, A.N.A. & Ahmed, & Rashad, R.T.. (2022). WATER SALINIZATION IN IRAQ AND SOME SUGGESTED SOLUTIONS. *Water Conservation and Management*. 6. 137-145. 10.26480/wcm.02.2022.137.145.

²⁵⁴ Zarei, M. (2020). The water-energy-food nexus: A holistic approach for resource security in Iran, Iraq, and Türkiye . *Water-Energy Nexus*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wen.2020.05.004>.

²⁵⁵ Hussein, A., & Asal, A. A. (2023). Drying water and its impact on the vital system in the marshes of southern Iraq. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1129(1), 012032. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1129/1/012032>

²⁵⁶ Almohamed, S., & Sheikh, D. . (2019). Review of the Syrian Agriculture and Future Prospects for Reconstruction. *Jordan Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 15(2), 35–49. <https://doi.org/10.35516/jjas.v15i2.44v>

²⁵⁷ Hole, Frank. (2009). Drivers of Unsustainable Land Use in the Semi-Arid Khabur River Basin, Syria. *Geographical Research*. 47. 4 - 14. 10.1111/j.1745-5871.2008.00550.x.

	widespread environmental and socioeconomic impacts. This issue affects approximately 77% of the country's land area, with an estimated total groundwater depletion of ~74 km ³ between 2002-2015 ²⁵⁸ .		land subsidence, and aquifer destruction, particularly in central and northeast Iran. In regions like Fars province, the high demand for agricultural water has caused a rapid decline in the groundwater table ²⁵⁹ .	reducing the social and political costs of enforcing regulations and involving local communities in policy-making and implementation are crucial steps. Implementing sustainable groundwater management practices, promoting water conservation, and raising awareness about the importance of groundwater conservation can help mitigate the environmental and socioeconomic impacts of groundwater overexploitation in Iran ²⁶⁰ .
6	Türkiye 's energy sector is facing significant sustainability challenges, primarily due to a heavy reliance on imported fossil fuels. This dependency not only burdens the economy but also contributes to air pollution ²⁶¹ .	Türkiye	The rapid increase in energy demand and electricity consumption is leading to rising carbon dioxide emissions. In response to these challenges, renewable energy sources are viewed as a promising solution for sustainable energy development. Türkiye 's geographical advantages provide opportunities for the extensive use of various renewable energy sources.	Transitioning from fossil fuels to renewable energy is essential for Türkiye 's energy future. Implementing sustainable energy policies and enhancing the utilization of renewable energy sources are critical for achieving clean and sustainable energy development. By prioritizing these actions, Türkiye can mitigate environmental impacts and foster a more sustainable energy landscape ²⁶¹ .
7	Iran's energy sector is grappling with significant sustainability challenges, primarily due to its heavy dependence on fossil fuels and inefficient consumption practices. Major barriers to sustainability in Iran include an aging vehicle fleet, outdated manufacturing standards, and inefficient public transport systems ²⁶² .	Iran	This unsustainable energy supply and usage lead to various economic, social, and environmental repercussions.	Strategies for enhancing sustainability in Iran's energy sector involve: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renovating the passenger vehicle fleet. • Expanding subway systems to improve public transportation. • Encouraging private sector investment in public transport initiatives. Additionally, there is a growing momentum in developing renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and biogas, which is contributing to increased installed capacity and job creation within the sector ^{263,264} .

²⁵⁸ Ashraf, S., Nazemi, A. & AghaKouchak, A. Anthropogenic drought dominates groundwater depletion in Iran. *Sci Rep* 11, 9135 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-88522-y>

²⁵⁹ Motagh, M., T. R. Walter, M. A. Sharifi, E. Fielding, A. Schenk, J. Anderssohn, and J. Zschau (2008), Land subsidence in Iran caused by widespread water reservoir overexploitation, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 35, L16403, doi:10.1029/2008GL033814.

²⁶⁰ Nabavi, Ehsan. (2018). Failed policies, falling aquifers: Unpacking groundwater overabstraction in Iran. *Water Alternatives*. 11. 699-724.

²⁶¹ Kaygusuz, K., & Toklu, E. (2012). Energy issues and sustainable development in Turkey. *Journal of Engineering Research and Applied Science*, 1(1), 1-25. Retrieved from <https://www.journaleras.com/index.php/jeras/article/view/4>

²⁶² Rezaei, Maede. (2013). The Role of Renewable Energies in Sustainable Development: Case Study Iran. *Iranica Journal of Energy and Environment*. 4. 10.5829/idosi.ijee.2013.04.04.02.

²⁶³ Moradi, Afsaneh & Hejazi, Seyed Reza & Yadollahi, Jahangir. (2015). Sustainability in Iran's Road Transport Sector: Evaluating Strategies and Policies. 10.1007/978-3-319-14002-5_10. .

²⁶⁴ S. Mohsen, P., Pourfayaz, F., Shirmohamadi, R., Moosavi, S., & Khalilpoor, N. (2021). Potential, Current Status, and Applications of Renewable Energy in Energy Sector of Iran: A Review. *Renewable Energy Research and Applications*, 2(1), 25-49. doi: 10.22044/rera.2020.8841.1008

Policy, Legal Frameworks and Agreements Assessment in the Study Countries

1.9 Iran

Iran's varied approach to managing the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) nexus is distinguished by a diverse set of policies, regulations, and national strategies aimed at integrating the management of these critical resources. This section examines the current policies within the nexus, scrutinizes legislative frameworks, identifies existing policy gaps, and assesses potential avenues for increased cooperation both domestically and internationally. A detailed table (Table 24) lists the primary policies affecting the WEFE nexus in Iran, laying the foundation for an in-depth analysis in the following subsections. These analyses will look into the complicated relationships and interdependencies between water, energy, food, and ecosystem resources, highlighting the country's strategic efforts and challenges in achieving sustainable resource management.

Table 24 Policies, governance, legal frameworks - Iran

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
<i>Water sector</i>	
<p>Iran Water Law and Methods of Nationalization of Water - 31 August 1968</p>	<p>Issued by the Ministry of Water and power in 1968</p> <p>The Water Law aims to nationalize all internal water resources in Iran and designates the Ministry of Energy as the primary authority for managing and utilizing these resources. The law includes regulations on water consumption and official tariffs for each sector, as well as organizing the use of public and groundwater resources through special permits. It also focuses on ensuring water availability by controlling floods, desalinating saline water, and establishing an irrigation network. Additionally, the law prohibits pollution of water resources and mandates measures for sewage disposal. Violations of the law are subject to penalties.</p> <p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this strategy, there are some approaches relevant to all sectors in WEFE Nexus:</p> <p>Functions of the Law:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nationalization of Internal Water: Nationalizes all internal water resources and assigns the Ministry of Energy as the responsible authority. 2. Regulation of Water Consumption: Determines permissible water consumption for domestic, agricultural, and industrial sectors, and sets official tariffs. 3. Permits: Requires special authorization from the Ministry for the use of public and groundwater resources.

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<p>4. Ensuring Water Supply: Includes measures for flood control, desalination, groundwater extraction, and establishment of an irrigation network.</p> <p>5. Pollution Prevention: Prohibits water pollution and mandates measures for proper sewage disposal.</p> <p>Article 17: The Ministry of Water and Power shall be required to gradually determine and notify the amount of water use permit in each region, in considering the type of product, type of soil and the continental conditions as well as the information put at its disposal by the Ministry of Agriculture relating to water use for each type of agricultural products</p> <p>Revisions of the Water Law:</p> <p>The 1982 Water Law in Iran established the foundation for the management and allocation of the country's water resources after the revolution. Under this law, all water bodies, such as rivers and lakes, are declared public property, with the government assuming full responsibility for their management. The Ministry of Energy (MOE) plays a central role, overseeing water resource allocation for domestic, agricultural, and industrial uses through permits. It is also tasked with constructing large hydraulic projects, including dams and irrigation systems. Within the MOE, the Water Affairs Department coordinates planning, development, and conservation efforts through various subsidiary organizations. Additionally, other ministries, such as the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of Health and Medical Education, collaborate on water distribution, quality control, and agricultural water use²⁶⁵.</p> <p><u>Gaps in WEFE Nexus Consideration</u></p> <p>While the Agrarian Reform Law of Iran (1962) effectively addresses the redistribution of agricultural land to improve the socio-economic status of poor peasants, it would benefit from further elaboration to include detailed considerations of energy and environmental sectors</p>
<i>Agriculture sector</i>	
<p>Agrarian Reform Law of Iran (1962) قانون الاصلاح الزراعي</p>	<p>The Agrarian Reform Law of Iran (1962) is a law aimed at redistributing agricultural land from large feudal landlords to poor peasants and updating irrigation systems to better meet agricultural needs.</p> <p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to all sectors in water sector:</p>

²⁶⁵ UN-Water. (n.d.). Iran paper (version 2.1). Retrieved December 19, 2024, from https://www.ais.unwater.org/ais/pluginfile.php/356/mod_page/content/110/Iran_Paper%20Bonn%20%20version%202.1.pdf

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Redistribute land from large feudal landlords to poor rural peasants, aiming to improve their socio-economic status. 2. Shift responsibility for maintaining traditional water infrastructure, such as qanats, from large landlords to new small-scale farmers. 3. Improve water access by transitioning to modern water resources like deep wells in areas where traditional systems are inadequate. 4. Facilitate agricultural productivity for new farmers by providing access to better water systems and reducing the burden of infrastructure maintenance
<p>Law on plants protection (1966) قانون حماية النباتات (الامراض والمبيدات)</p>	<p>The Plant Protection Act in Iran focuses on regulating and overseeing the control of plant pests and diseases through the establishment of a Plant Protection Organization. Environmentally, the law aims to prevent pollution by regulating the import and distribution of chemicals like pesticides and plant hormones. Agriculturally, the law is designed to protect crops from pests and diseases and enhance agricultural productivity through effective control measures.</p> <p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to all sectors in the environmental sector.</p> <p>The functions of this law:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Crop Protection: Control and manage plant pests and diseases affecting agricultural crops. 2. Environmental Control: Regulate the use of chemicals to prevent environmental pollution. 3. Permit Regulation: Issue permits for the import and distribution of agricultural chemicals. 4. Compliance Monitoring: Ensure that companies and farmers adhere to environmental standards and technical guidelines. <p><u>Gaps in WEFE Nexus Consideration</u></p> <p>The Law on Plant Protection (1966) focuses on safeguarding plants from pests and diseases and enhancing regulations related to environmental protection. However, it would be beneficial to further elaborate the law to include detailed considerations of the water and energy sectors, as these aspects significantly impact the effectiveness of plant protection and the sustainability of agricultural production, along with the inclusion of organic farming and biological control agents.</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
<i>Energy sector</i>	
Ministry of energy-1983	<p>The Ministry of Energy was established on October 17, 1936, to provide electricity in Tehran. On May 20, 1943, its scope expanded to include water management. The ministry was renamed the Ministry of Water and Electricity on March 17, 1964. On February 17, 1975, it became the Ministry of Energy after parliamentary approval. Its responsibilities expanded on May 10, 1978, to include the construction and operation of nuclear power plants. Following the Iranian Revolution in 1979, some functions were transferred to the Ministry of Agriculture on July 12, 1980. On March 7, 1983, water management and the fair distribution of water resources became part of the Ministry of Energy's responsibilities.</p> <p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to all sectors in WEFE Nexus</p> <p>Functions of the ministry of energy:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Regulation and management of supply and demand for water, electricity, energy, and wastewater services. 2. Promotion of training, research, and technology in the water and electricity sectors. 3. Development of the goods and services market in the water and electricity industry. 4. Preservation of natural resources. 5. Environmental protection. 6. Promotion of public health and welfare. 7. Achieving self-sufficiency and sustainable development for the country <p>Some approaches relevant to renewable energy:</p> <p>Operating under the Ministry of Energy, the Statute of the Renewable Energy Organization of Iran regulates the establishment and operations of the Iranian Renewable Energy Organization (IREO). The main objective of the Organization is to increase the use of renewable energy and improve energy efficiency through research and development, education, consultancy, technical and financial support, and capacity building. The IREO is structured with a General Assembly, a Board of Directors, an Executive Manager, and an Inspector. The statute consists of 29 articles,</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	divided into five chapters: General Provisions and Funding, Activities and Duties, Structure, Financial Statements, and Miscellaneous Provisions ²⁶⁶ .
<i>Environment sector</i>	
<p>The Air Pollution Prevention Law (1995) قانون منع تلوث الهواء (1995)</p>	<p>The Air Pollution Prevention Law (1995) is the fundamental legislation in Iran that regulates how to manage air pollution.</p> <p>functions of the Air Pollution Prevention Law (1995):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define emission limits: Establish limits for emissions from vehicles and factories. • Monitor vehicles: Prohibit the use of vehicles that emit pollution beyond the allowable limits. • Standards for new factories: Impose standards on new factories and workshops to reduce air pollution. • Define clean air standards: Assign the Environmental Protection Agency responsibility for setting clean air standards and pollutant standards for factories. • Address regional crises: Direct workshops to consider regional environmental crisis <p><u>Gaps in WEFE Nexus Consideration</u></p> <p>While the Air Pollution Prevention Law (1995) effectively addresses air pollution by setting emission limits and regulating vehicle and factory emissions, it would benefit from further elaboration to include detailed considerations of the agricultural sector and the integration of renewable energy sources.</p>
<p>Clean Air Law (2017)</p>	<p>Clean Air Law (2017)</p> <p>The Clean Air Law of 2017 is a legislative framework aimed at controlling and reducing air and noise pollution in Iran. It includes a set of regulations to monitor emissions from vehicles and industries, ensuring a healthier environment. The law emphasizes the transition to renewable energy sources and promotes environmental sustainability through policies like increasing green spaces in industrial zones.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of Air and Noise Pollution: The law sets limits on emissions from vehicles and industrial activities. It requires mandatory annual technical inspections for vehicles to control pollution levels. • Promotion of Renewable Energy and Environmental Precautions: The Ministry of Energy is tasked with increasing the share of

²⁶⁶ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (n.d.). *Statute of the Renewable Energy Organization of Iran* (LEX-FAOC164938). FAOLEX. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/c/LEX-FAOC164938>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<p>renewable energy to meet 30% of the country’s growing electricity demand. The law also mandates that new industrial units dedicate at least 10% of their area to green spaces and prohibits the burning of various waste types in public spaces.</p> <p>Gaps in WEFE Nexus Consideration</p> <p>While the Clean Air Law (2017) effectively addresses air and noise pollution by regulating emissions from vehicles and industries, it could be further enhanced by incorporating considerations for the Water, Energy, Food, and Environment (WEFE) Nexus. Specifically, the law could benefit from a more detailed focus on the agricultural sector and its integration with air quality management. Additionally, expanding on the role of renewable energy sources and their impact on air quality and environmental sustainability would strengthen the law's alignment with broader sustainable development goals</p>
<i>Laws and policies cover all sectors of the WEFE Nexus</i>	
Waste Management Law (2004)	<p><i>The Waste Management Law (2004) consists of 23 articles aimed at optimizing waste management practices and minimizing their harmful environmental impact. The law focuses on protecting the environment through provisions related to the collection, sorting, recycling, and disposal of waste. Key elements include:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Setting standards for recycled materials and products in collaboration with the Ministry of Health and the Standard Institute.</i> • <i>Delegating waste collection and disposal duties to the private sector in specific regions.</i> • <i>Identifying appropriate waste disposal areas in cooperation with the Ministry of Agriculture.</i> • <i>Prohibiting the mixing of hospital or medical waste with household waste.</i> • <i>Ensuring compliance with the Basel Convention for the trans-boundary transport of waste.</i>
Iran’s Third National Communication – December 2017	<p>National Greenhouse Gas Mitigation Policies</p> <p>Energy sector</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mitigation Scenarios at agricultural sector <p>Water pumps fuel switching of Agricultural wells: Reducing gas oil consumption by replacing existing diesel engines with electric submersible pumps in 217,000 agricultural wells</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mitigation Scenarios at Power generation sector <p>1. Installation of 6,000 MW wind and 18,700 MW hydro power plants by 2025. 2013 capacities were 98 MW and 10266 MW, respectively.</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<p>2. Raising share of efficient combined cycle power plants with thermal efficiency of around 45% in power generation mix from 27.3% in 2015 to 54.2% in 2025. This is done via either upgrading the current open cycle gas turbine with steam cycle or installing new combined cycle power plants.</p> <p>3. Increasing the share of natural gas in power plants fuel mix</p> <p>Oil and gas activity:</p> <p>1. Recovery of flared gases in offshore and onshore oil extraction facilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vulnerability and Adaptation <p>Water Resources:</p> <p>1. Trying to achieve healthy community with welfare, food security, equal opportunities, proper income distribution and benefited from favorable environment</p> <p>2. The water sector has a special role in sustainable development, food security, and people’s health. Therefore, it is critical to enhance the optimal utilization of water resources in each basin considering the capacity of their ecosystems and situation of their climate</p> <p>3. Increasing the economic efficiency of water use and improving water productivity in all sectors.</p> <p>4. Determining the value of water (including its intrinsic, economic, security, political and environmental values) in the context of sustainable development guidelines and appropriate applicable pricing policies in the country.</p> <p>Agriculture sector:</p> <p>Capacity Building Strategies for Adaptation of Agriculture Sector to Mitigate Adverse Effects of Climate Change:</p> <p>1. Saline-water resources (surface and underground), treated wastewater, agricultural drainage waters, and rainwater harvesting</p> <p>2. Irrigation management should consider specific crop water requirements at local levels and climatic conditions.</p>
Fifth Social, Economic and Cultural Development Plan 2011-2015	<p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this plan, there are some approaches relevant to all sectors in WEFE Nexus</p> <p>The Fifth Social, Economic, and Cultural Development Plan (2011-2015) is a comprehensive strategy aimed at fostering sustainable growth in Iran by improving food security, supporting the agricultural sector, and</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<p>developing infrastructure. The plan consists of nine chapters covering various areas such as culture, science, social affairs, and administration. Key components of the plan include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing support for the agricultural sector and developing slaughterhouses. • Supporting livestock production and combating diseases. • Enhancing research and technology in agriculture. • Improving irrigation efficiency and achieving self-sufficiency in essential food production. • Protecting the environment and natural resources by replacing fossil fuels with renewable energy sources. • Enhancing livelihoods in rural areas through improved services, infrastructure, education, and job creation.
The Five-Year National Development Plan	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>Iran's Five-Year National Development Plans are strategic frameworks encompass a range of sectors, including infrastructure, industry, and environment, with each iteration focusing on addressing pressing national challenges while promoting sustainable growth.</p> <p>Below is a summary of the most related environmental legal clauses in the seventh Five-Year National Development Plan that will be issued in 2023.</p> <p>Part 4, Clause T, Article 33: The Ministry of Jihad of Agriculture must cover the costs for water and soil operations, including the reconstruction and modernization of irrigation systems in agricultural lands.</p> <p>Clause D of Article 38: The Ministry of Economy is required to collect a tax from the value of water-rich agricultural and food products exported, with the funds allocated for watershed projects, cultivation pattern improvements, and smart meter installation for agricultural wells.</p> <p>Clause P, Article 40: Mechanisms to ensure the sustainability of underground water usage in critical plains must be established. The Ministry of Energy is tasked with installing counters to manage over-extraction of water resources.</p> <p>Referring to the country's fifth five-year plan (2010-2015), the Iranian government sought to boost the use of renewable energy resources, but it fell short of its target of 5,000 MW of renewable energy by 2050. Iran plans to increase the share of renewable energy to 32% by 2050, which will contribute to improving air quality in major cities and achieving energy security, independence, and future climate goals.</p>

1.9.1 Assessment of Current Policies and Governance Structures

The current policies and legal frameworks in Iran demonstrate a concerted effort to align national strategies and legal measures with the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus, although this integration is not always explicitly mentioned. The Iran Water Law (1968), for instance, encompasses comprehensive management and preservation strategies that indirectly support the WEFE Nexus by emphasizing sustainable water management, pollution prevention, and the establishment of controlled irrigation systems. Similarly, the Agrarian Reform Law (1962) and the Plant Protection Law (1966) contribute to the food and ecosystem components by improving land distribution and agricultural productivity while ensuring environmental safety in chemical usage. These laws, along with strategic national communications and development plans, such as the Third National Communication on Climate Change (2017) and the Fifth Social Economic and Cultural Development Plan, propose holistic approaches that cover multiple aspects of the WEFE Nexus, including sustainable agriculture practices, renewable energy promotion, and water resource management. These integrated approaches are critical for fostering sustainable development and addressing interconnected challenges across sectors.

However, gaps remain in the explicit integration of the WEFE Nexus within Iran's governance and legal frameworks. While sector-specific laws such as the Air Pollution Prevention Law (1995) and various energy and water management policies address individual elements of the WEFE Nexus, they often lack comprehensive provisions that bridge the interdependencies between water, energy, food, and ecosystems. For example, although the Ministry of Energy is pivotal in managing both energy and water resources, there is limited evidence of coordinated efforts that consider the simultaneous impacts on food security and ecosystem health, which are essential components of the WEFE Nexus. The absence of explicit nexus-oriented goals and measures in some of these policies may hinder the effectiveness of integrated resource management and reduce the potential for synergistic benefits across sectors, underscoring the need for more cohesive policy frameworks that holistically address the interconnected nature of these critical resources.

1.9.2 Analysis of Legal Frameworks and Agreements

- **Legal Frameworks:** Iran's legal framework provides detailed regulations for managing resources but often in isolation without a cohesive nexus-oriented approach.
- **Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements:** Iran participates in international environmental agreements, which could be leveraged more effectively to promote nexus integration and cooperation on transboundary resource management issues.

1.9.3 Identification of Gaps

Key areas for improvement in Iran's WEFE nexus management include:

- **Explicit Nexus Integration:** While individual laws address specific resources, there is a notable lack of integrated policy frameworks that explicitly link water, energy, food, and ecosystems. This can be done by establishing a dedicated inter-ministerial body that ensures alignment between ministries.
- **Implementation and Coordination:** Discrepancies between policy intentions and on-the-ground implementations highlight the need for better coordination and enforcement mechanisms.
- **Modernization and Adaptation:** Updating some older laws and better aligning them with contemporary environmental and technological challenges could enhance the efficacy of nexus management. This includes the integration of programs that adapt to climate change.

1.9.4 Potential for Cooperation

Opportunities for enhanced cooperation in Iran focus on:

- **National Policy Integration:** Strengthening the interconnections between different sectoral policies at the national level to promote more holistic management of nexus resources.
- **Regional Collaboration:** Increased participation in transboundary water management and energy exchange programs could improve regional stability and sustainability, benefiting all countries involved in shared resource management.

1.10 Iraq

Iraq's strategic engagement with the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) nexus is reflected in a number of legislative measures, regulatory frameworks, and policy initiatives aimed at optimizing resource management and promoting sustainable development. This section defines Iraq's current policies, examines the legal frameworks and agreements, identifies gaps in these structures, and evaluates opportunities for regional and international cooperation. The following table (Table 25) outlines Iraq's key policies across the nexus, setting the framework for the detailed analyses in the following subsections. These evaluations will look into how Iraq manages the complex interconnections between water, energy, food, and ecosystems, highlighting the country's challenges and opportunities for achieving integrated resource management and sustainability goals.

Table 25 Policies, governance, legal frameworks - Iraq

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
Water	
<i>Law No. 50 of 2008 – Ministry of Water Resources Law</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The Ministry of Water Resources Law No. 50 of 2008 in Iraq was established to effectively and sustainably manage the country's water resources. Since its inception, several amendments have been made to the law to improve the legal framework and update policies in line with the country's evolving needs and new environmental and technological challenges. These amendments include enhancing the ministry's role in monitoring and regulating water consumption, developing irrigation systems, and improving water infrastructure.</p> <p>Despite the law extensive framework, but it does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to the water in the environmental and agriculture sectors; One of the law goals is to preserving surface and groundwater from pollution, giving priority to the environmental aspect, and reviving and sustaining marshes and other water bodies.</p> <p><u>Article 3 – The Ministry seeks to achieve its objectives as follows:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulating water distribution, preventing flood dangers, and controlling torrents and river basins.

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting studies on irrigation, reclamation, dams and groundwater projects. • Management, operation and maintenance of dams, reclamation, irrigation, drainage and groundwater projects.
<i>Irrigation Law No. 83 of 2017</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The Irrigation Law regulates the use and management of water resources in agricultural lands with the aim of improving irrigation efficiency and preserving these resources.</p> <p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to water in the environment and agricultural sector:</p> <p><u>Article 4:</u> The locations and extensions of irrigation facilities are determined and coordinated with the competent authorities to ensure that they do not have a negative impact on the environment.</p> <p><u>Article 5:</u> Addresses issues of water resource maintenance and bears its costs to beneficiaries, which includes farmers and affects agriculture.</p> <p><u>Article 7:</u> Prevents the use of water for purposes other than those for which it was designated, which ensures the efficient use of water in agriculture and preserves water resources.</p>
<i>Iraq Country Water Resource Assistance Strategy - 2016</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The report, developed in collaboration with Iraq's Ministry of Water Resources, Ministry of Planning and Development Cooperation, assesses current water management practices, identifies challenges in resource management, and prioritizes investment and technical assistance for rehabilitating deteriorating hydraulic infrastructure.</p> <p>Hydropower: new hydropower capacity is planned that would double hydropower output. Where the National Water Master Plan will examine alternative flow options, and a review the scope for new hydraulic and hydropower facilities.</p>
<i>Regulation of national limits for the use of treated wastewater in agricultural irrigation – No. (3) of 2012</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>Regulation No. (3) of 2012 in Iraq establishes a framework for using treated wastewater in agricultural irrigation. It outlines standards and guidelines to ensure that treated wastewater is safe and effective for agricultural use. The regulation aims to promote sustainable water use while protecting public health and the environment.</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<p>Despite the law extensive framework, but it does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to the water in the environmental and agriculture sectors;</p> <p>The regulation aims to maximize the utilization of treated water, considered a non-conventional water source, by establishing criteria to ensure safe utilization of treated wastewater in agricultural irrigation. It also defines appropriate methods and standards for treating wastewater and reusing it in agricultural irrigation.</p>
<i>Iraq Vision 2030</i> -	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>Iraq Vision 2030, developed by the Ministry of Planning, serves as a strategic roadmap for building a thriving and equitable nation. It focuses on leveraging Iraq's economic strengths to promote sustainability. The vision includes five key areas, includes the environmental sustainability, aligning with UN sustainable development goals.</p> <p>Goal (5-1): Reduce environment pollution and greenhouse emissions. Tackling environmental problems can be achieved through drafting laws according to increasing the reliance on renewable and clean energy sources.</p> <p>Goal (5-2): Efficient use of water resources. The need to increase the efficiency of water resources use is crucial in light of the continuous decrease in the water available for home, agricultural and industrial uses and to prevent wasting more water.</p> <p><u>Target Achieving Tools:</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve the irrigation and drainage systems. 2. Develop an integrated water management system. <p>Goal (5-4): Develop the consumption and production patterns to achieve environmental sustainability. This goal is crucial for sustainable agriculture. This aligns with the NEXUS WEFE framework by integrating efficient water, energy, and food management while preserving ecosystems. Key strategies include advanced irrigation, soil health enhancement, and climate-resilient practices.</p> <p>Gaps: The document's goals lack a focus on specific energy efficiency measures and the transition to renewable energy. There is also a need for a more integrated approach to managing water, energy, and food resources together. Addressing these gaps would strengthen the implementation of WEFE NEXUS in the Vision 2030 objectives.</p>
<i>The National Report for</i>	<u>Document Description</u>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
<i>Sustainable Development in Iraq - 2012</i>	<p>The 2012 National Report for Sustainable Development in Iraq, prepared by the Ministry of Planning, outlines Iraq's sustainable development initiatives, including measures to combat desertification. These efforts integrate with the WEFE Nexus by promoting sustainable land management and conserving water resources, aiming for resilience across water, environment, and food sectors.</p> <p>Combat Desertification Measures:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establishing desert oases to get the benefit of the western desert in achieving food security. 2. Increasing green cover in desert areas through natural pastor stations. 3. Al-Hammad basin project and water collection, which aims at: developing water resources to combat desertification and preserve environmental balance in the area and using rain water through erecting small dams and sand dunes.
<i>Energy</i>	
<i>Ministry of Electricity Law No. 53 of 2017</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The Ministry of Electricity Law No. 53 of 2017 in Iraq establishes the legal framework for the development and regulation of the electricity sector. This law aims to modernize the electricity infrastructure, promote private sector investment, especially in renewable energy. It outlines the responsibilities of the Ministry of Electricity in planning, operation, and maintenance of the national grid.</p> <p>This law includes several strategies related to the environmental and energy sectors. One of its objectives is to support and promote the use of renewable energy across different fields and to develop local industries related to these technologies.</p> <p><u>Article 9 of Chapter Four stipulates</u> that the Ministry of Electricity shall, for the purpose of investment in the electricity sector, focus on encouraging the private sector to invest in constructing stations that operate on renewable energy, while also providing the necessary incentives.</p>
<i>Law No. 4 of 2018 regarding the Iraqi National Oil Company Law</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The law defines the powers and responsibilities of the Iraqi National Oil Company, and includes several aspects such as community development and environmental protection. The law addresses the environmental, social and economic dimensions of the company's activities.</p> <p>Despite the law extensive framework, but it does not explicitly integrate the WEFE Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to the energy, agriculture and environmental sectors.</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<p>Key Articles Related to Energy, Agriculture, and the Environment:</p> <p><u>Article 8:</u></p> <p>Clause 9: Establish environmental protection controls and work to stop pollution by developing the alternative energy sources sector.</p> <p>Clause 10: Develop plans to qualify the private sector for the purpose of developing various energy sectors.</p> <p><u>Article 18:</u></p> <p>Clause 5: Directs the company to ensure that all lands it controls are used productively. These lands can be designated for the company's operational needs, agricultural projects, light manufacturing industries, services, tourism, or recreational purposes.</p> <p>Clause 6: Permits the company to aid in the advancement of the agricultural, industrial, and service sectors across Iraq to benefit all citizens.</p>
<i>Food</i>	
<p><i>Instructions for the use of treated sludge in agriculture No.1 of 2016</i></p>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The Instructions for the Use of Treated Sludge in Agriculture aim to regulate the use of treated sludge, which is the result of wastewater treatment, as agricultural fertilizer.</p> <p>The regulations in these instructions show the interconnection between several important aspects:</p> <p><u>Article 1:</u> describes wastewater and sludge as part of the water management system, linking water management and treatment.</p> <p><u>Articles 2 and 4:</u> specify the standards for treating and using sludge to ensure that it does not have a negative impact on the environment, reflecting the importance of preserving soil and water quality.</p> <p><u>Article 6:</u> includes examining soil and sludge to ensure that they do not affect groundwater and soil, linking the environment and public health.</p> <p><u>Articles 7 and 8:</u> specify the use of sludge in agriculture only if it is compatible with environmental standards, ensuring that food is not contaminated and agricultural production is increased safely.</p>
<p><i>Modern Agricultural Villages Law No. (59) of 2012</i></p>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The Modern Agricultural Villages Law No. (59) of 2012 in Iraq establishes a framework for developing and promoting modern agricultural villages. The law enhances agricultural productivity by allocating land, ensuring access to water resources, and providing necessary support to farmers. It also emphasizes the</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<p>adoption of advanced irrigation systems and modern agricultural practices to improve efficiency and sustainability in rural farming communities.</p> <p>The law aims to regulate the establishment of modern agricultural villages that contribute to achieving food security, increasing green spaces, combating desertification, and improving the environment.</p> <p>The objectives of the law are achieved through the Ministry's commitment to allocating agricultural lands, coordinating with relevant authorities to ensure the provision of adequate water resources, and extending necessary support to beneficiaries. Additionally, the law mandates the use of modern, advanced irrigation systems.</p>
<i>Ecosystem</i>	
<p><i>Law No. (27) of 2009 Environmental Protection and Improvement Law</i></p>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The law seeks to safeguard and enhance the environment by addressing and mitigating existing or potential damage, while conserving natural resources and biodiversity to promote sustainable development. The law also fosters international and regional cooperation in environmental protection.</p> <p>The law adopts a NEXUS approach by integrating efforts to protect water from pollution, preserve land, maintain biodiversity, and prevent environmental contamination from oil and natural gas exploration and extraction activities.</p> <p><u>Through the following:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Maintain the quality of water resources by stipulate special laws and specifications about: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Discharge of domestic, industrial, service or agricultural liquid waste. ● Connecting or draining sewage to rainwater drainage networks. ● Throwing waste into water resources. ● The use of toxic materials and explosives in hunting aquatic animals. ● Discharge of liquid waste related to petroleum materials into internal surface waters or Iraqi marine areas. ➤ In order to protect the land, special laws and specifications apply to the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Preventing any activity that directly or indirectly leads to damage to the soil in a way that affects its production capabilities and the food chain, except in accordance with applicable legislation. ● Commitment to the basic designs of urban areas and protecting lands from urban sprawl.

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Protecting biodiversity through laws preventing the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmful to rare, medicinal, aromatic, and wild plants. • Cutting down old trees (30 years and older) in public areas is prohibited except with permission.
<p><i>Nationally Determined Contributions of Iraq - 2021</i></p>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The 2021 Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) of Iraq, prepared by the Ministry of Environment and UNDP, outlines adaptation and mitigation measures across various sectors. It includes strategies for energy, water resources, agriculture, and natural systems and forests, aimed at addressing climate change impacts and promoting sustainability.</p> <p><u>Adaptation and mitigation measures categorized by sector:</u></p> <p><u>Water Resources Sector:</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Utilizing renewable energy sources to power desalination plants for seawater desalination. 2. Enhancing the efficiency of irrigation through the adoption of advanced techniques and exploring alternative water sources. <p><u>Agriculture sector:</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Managing the cultivation of methane-intensive crops and reducing their water consumption. 2. Integrating renewable energy sources for operating irrigation systems and adopting high-efficiency irrigation methods in agriculture. 3. Establishing a framework for preserving forests, expanding forest cover, and establishing green zones to mitigate CO2 emissions. <p><u>Natural systems and forests:</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Restoring forests, expanding their coverage, and implementing sustainable management practices to bolster their environmental protection role and carbon sequestration. 2. Establishing oases within desert and arid ecosystems to safeguard biodiversity against the impacts of climate change. <p><u>Energy sector</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Implementing nature-based solutions by planting vegetation around energy production facilities.

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Enhancing infrastructure such as airports and transportation hubs by integrating modern, eco-friendly modes of transportation like electric trains. 3. Investing in and advancing petroleum industries to promote resource conservation and emissions reduction. 4. Utilizing hydropower as a clean energy source. 5. Implementing advanced, sustainable, and eco-friendly public transportation systems. 6. Harnessing methane produced from landfills for electricity generation. 7. Generating electricity and heat through waste treatment processes.
<i>Environmental Determinants Instructions for Project Establishment and Safety Monitoring No. 3 of 2011</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The Environmental Determinants Instructions for Project Establishment and Safety Monitoring No. 3 of 2011 were issued in accordance with the Environment and Environmental Protection and Improvement Laws. These instructions categorize projects based on their environmental impact into three groups and mandate site-specific and environmental requirements. The requirements include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementing a system for treating liquid industrial waste to lower water pollutant levels, thus protecting the environment and conserving water resources in Iraq. • Providing containers for collecting solid waste and transporting it to designated sanitary landfill sites. • In certain projects, establishing belts of evergreen trees. • Promoting the use of solid waste from animal husbandry projects as fertilizer. • Utilizing clean fuels in various production processes, combustion activities, and gas treatment.
<i>National Development Plan (NDP) 2018 - 2022</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The National Development Plan (NDP) 2018-2022 outlines Iraq’s strategic approach to economic and social advancement. It focuses on diversifying the economy beyond oil, enhancing infrastructure, and improving public services. The plan also emphasizes strengthening governance, supporting private sector growth, and promoting sustainability.</p> <p>Although the strategy does not explicitly integrate the WEFE NEXUS, it includes relevant approaches in the following sustainable development goals in different sectors:</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<p><u>Agriculture and Water Resources Sector</u></p> <p>Sustainable Development Goals:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enhance Agriculture: Expand and improve agricultural land and productivity using modern irrigation methods. Rehabilitate irrigation areas from 2,094 thousand dunums in 2018 to 5,292 thousand dunums by 2022. 2. Secure Water for Agriculture: Increase irrigation efficiency and reduce water waste, while boosting storage capacity. 3. Ensure Sustainable Water Resources: Negotiate with upstream countries, revitalize marshes, and improve irrigation efficiency from 35% in 2015 to 60% by 2022. <p><u>Energy Sector</u></p> <p>A. Oil and Gas:</p> <p>Environmental Protection: Reduce CO2 emissions, adhere to international standards, and implement eco-friendly technologies with a robust environmental monitoring system.</p> <p>B. Electricity:</p> <p>Reduce Environmental Impact:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use gas instead of liquid fuel to cut CO2 emissions by 19,433 thousand tons annually. 2. Convert to combined-cycle gas stations to reduce CO2 emissions by 8,150 thousand tons annually. 3. Invest in renewable energy, targeting 4.2% from solar power.

1.10.1 Assessment of Current Policies and Governance Structures

Iraq's policies and legal frameworks demonstrate a strong orientation towards addressing components of the WEFE Nexus, albeit often in a segmented fashion rather than through an integrated approach. The Ministry of Water Resources Law and the Irrigation Law highlight substantial efforts to manage and sustain water resources with an implicit impact on agriculture and ecosystems. The focus on improving irrigation systems underlines the interconnectedness of water and food security, essential for the agricultural productivity of the country. Similarly, the energy sector reforms, especially the push towards renewable energy, align with environmental sustainability goals that indirectly support the water and food sectors by reducing pollution and promoting cleaner production methods.

However, the explicit integration of the WEFE Nexus is lacking, as most policies and regulations address the nexus components separately without a unified framework. For example, while the Ministry of Electricity promotes renewable energy, the broader implications for water conservation

and food production—critical under the nexus framework—are not thoroughly explored. Furthermore, the strategic plans, such as Iraq Vision 2030 and the National Report for Sustainable Development, while ambitious, reveal gaps in fully integrating energy efficiency measures and a cohesive strategy that simultaneously manages water, energy, and food resources in a changing climate. Addressing these gaps by fostering policy coherence and integrating nexus thinking into all relevant sectors could enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of Iraq’s development initiatives.

1.10.2 Analysis of Legal Frameworks and Agreements

- **Legal Frameworks:** Iraq has enacted numerous laws that impact the WEFE sectors. Notably, environmental laws like the Environmental Protection and Improvement Law focus on conserving natural resources and promoting sustainable development.
- **Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements:** Iraq engages in various agreements aimed at environmental sustainability and resource management, although specific agreements directly addressing the integrated management of the WEFE sectors are less common.

1.10.3 Identification of Gaps

Several gaps are evident in Iraq’s approach to managing the WEFE nexus:

- **Explicit Nexus Integration:** Few policies explicitly address the interconnections between water, energy, food, and ecosystems, which could enhance overall resource efficiency and sustainability.
- **Policy and Implementation Discrepancies:** There is a noticeable gap between policy formulation and actual implementation, often due to lack of coordination among various governmental bodies and unclear mechanisms for enforcement.
- **Technological and Knowledge Gaps:** There is a need for advanced technologies and knowledge sharing (for data management) to effectively implement the principles of the WEFE nexus, especially in areas like renewable energy integration in water and agricultural sectors.

1.10.4 Potential for Cooperation

Iraq has substantial potential for enhanced cooperation both nationally and regionally:

- **National Integration:** Strengthening intra-governmental collaboration could foster integrated nexus management, linking policies across the WEFE sectors more coherently.
- **Regional Collaboration:** Enhanced cooperation with neighboring countries could improve transboundary water management, shared energy resources, and food security initiatives, fostering regional stability and sustainable development.

1.11 Syria

Syria’s involvement in the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) nexus reflects a comprehensive set of policies and legislative frameworks aimed at managing and optimizing the interdependent resources required for sustainable development. This section describes Syria’s current legislative environment, examines the effectiveness of these frameworks in addressing nexus principles, identifies key gaps in policy integration, and assesses the potential for increased cooperation both within the country and regionally. The following table (Table 26) provides a detailed account of the key policies influencing the WEFE nexus in Syria, which serves as the foundation for the in-depth analyses that follow, emphasizing the interplay between governance, resource management, and sustainable development strategies across the nexus sectors.

Table 26 Policies, governance, legal frameworks - Syria

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
Water Sector	
<p><i>Water Legislation Law No. 31 of 2005</i></p>	<p>Water Legislation Law No. 31 of 2005 aims to regulate the management and protection of water resources in Syria. The law provides key definitions related to the High-Water Committee, the Ministry of Irrigation, protected areas for water sources, and various types of water, including surface, groundwater, and non-traditional water. It outlines the rights to public water, how to register and confirm these rights, and sets conditions to protect water resources from pollution and depletion. The law emphasizes the development of infrastructure and the regulation of water use for purposes such as drinking, agriculture, and industry.</p> <p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to the environmental and agriculture sectors:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Chapter 5: Government water networks <p>The chapter stipulates that the exploitation and maintenance of water sources and networks are carried out according to the instructions of the relevant ministry. It specifies that lands benefiting from irrigation networks can use the network's water according to designated distribution schedules and prohibits the use of wastewater and agricultural drainage for irrigation without a prior license based on the quantity and quality of the water.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Chapter 6: Well and pumping licenses. <p>Article 25: The Ministry, upon request from the entity seeking the license, shall grant a license to drill one or more wells and provide technical assistance, all within the available water resources in each basin, provided that modern irrigation methods are used for agricultural purposes and water use is optimized for other purposes.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Chapter 9: Prospecting <p>Article 44: Remove debris from the excavation site and neighboring land and compensate for any damage resulting from excavation activities.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Chapter 11: General Provisions <p>Article 50: Public water is preserved from pollution through cooperation and coordination between the ministry, other ministries, and public entities in accordance with current laws and regulations.</p> <p>Article 52: Well owners are required to use advanced irrigation techniques according to the principles and decisions set by the High-Water Committee.</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<p><u>Gaps in WEFE Nexus Consideration</u></p> <p>While Law No. 31 of 2005 effectively addresses the management and protection of water resources, further elaborated to include additional details on the interconnections with the energy sector. The law primarily focuses on the administrative and legal framework for water use and conservation but requires more comprehensive integration with the energy sector to ensure a thorough and effective approach to resource management.</p>
<p><i>Legislative Decree No. 90 related to the General Authority for Water Resources</i></p> <p><i>المرسوم التشريعي (90) بشأن الهيئة العامة للموارد المائية (بدل هيئة الري)</i></p>	<p>The Legislative Decree No. 90 establishes the General Authority for Water Resources, responsible for managing, developing, and protecting water resources in Syria. It outlines the authority's organizational structure, duties, and financial management, and it replaces previous irrigation management bodies with a focus on comprehensive water resource management.</p> <p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to the agriculture sector:</p> <p>Chapter 4: The Authority is responsible for the following tasks:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop mechanisms for the utilization of water resources to ensure their protection from pollution in all water basins, in coordination with relevant ministries. 2. Study and design irrigation projects and water facilities, establish engineering standards for their study, implementation, and supervision, and oversee their operation. <p><u>Gaps in WEFE Nexus Consideration</u></p> <p>While Legislative Decree No. 90 effectively outlines the management and protection of water resources, it needs to be further elaborated to include additional details on the interconnections with the energy sector and environmental considerations.</p>
Agriculture Sector	
<p><i>Agricultural Reform Law No. 161 of 1958</i></p> <p><i>قانون الإصلاح الزراعي رقم 161 لسنة 1958</i></p>	<p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to the water sector:</p> <p>Law No. 161 of 1958 on Agricultural Reform specifies ownership limits for agricultural land based on its type and irrigation source. It outlines different areas for irrigated lands, rainfed lands with olive and pistachio trees, and non-irrigated rainfed lands. The law includes conditions for each type of land, setting restrictions on the amount of land an individual can own, considering factors like the age of trees in planted areas and rainfall rates in rainfed lands.</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<p>It defines irrigated lands based on the availability of a stable water source, including groundwater and surface water.</p> <p><u>Gaps in WEFE Nexus Consideration</u></p> <p>While Law No. 161 of 1958 on Agricultural Reform primarily addresses land distribution and the development of the agricultural sector, it needs to be further elaborated to include additional details on these interconnections to ensure a more comprehensive and effective approach to managing and developing agricultural lands.</p>
<p><i>Law No. 56 of 2004 regarding the Regulation of Agricultural Relations</i></p> <p>قانون رقم (56) لسنة 2004 في شأن تنظيم العلاقات الزراعية</p>	<p>The law aimed at organizing relationships between various parties in the agricultural sector, including farmers, agricultural producers, and government entities</p> <p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to the environment sector:</p> <p>Article 92: defines types of agricultural land based on water usage: rainfed land relies solely on rainfall, irrigated land uses flowing or groundwater, vineyards include fruit-bearing trees, and forest lands cover areas with trees, shrubs, and herbs.</p> <p>Article 126: The minister, after consulting with the Ministries of Local Administration, Environment, Health, Agriculture and Agrarian Reform, and the Social Insurance Institution, sets the rules for preventive oversight of agricultural institutions, pest control materials, and the methods used in handling and transferring agricultural products to ensure they do not pose a threat to health and occupational safety.</p> <p><u>Gaps in WEFE Nexus Consideration</u></p> <p>While Law No. 161 of 1958 on Agricultural Reform primarily addresses land distribution and the development of the agricultural sector, it needs to be further elaborated to include additional details on how to integrate agriculture sector with the energy sector and environmental considerations.</p>
<p><i>Legislative Decree No.29 of 2012 on Agricultural Land Reclamation.</i></p>	<p>The Decree, consisting of 55 articles, regulates agricultural land reclamation in Syria. Part I outlines the rules for reclamation and specifies that the Minister of Irrigation, in coordination with the Minister of Agriculture and Agrarian Reform and after consulting the General Union of Farmers, can declare certain lands for reclamation as being of public benefit. It also sets restrictions on land alterations, halts agricultural activities during reclamation, and clarifies that no compensation is provided for damaged plantations or installations.</p> <p>Part II establishes committees for distributing reclaimed irrigated land and specifies that land ownership cannot exceed 16 hectares, with excess land reverting to the state. Part III focuses on the investment of reclaimed land,</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	prohibiting changes to its features and setting water usage limits in consultation with the Ministry. Parts IV and V cover sanctions and general provisions related to the reclamation process.
<i>Energy sector</i>	
<p><i>Law No. 32 of 2010 on electricity</i> قانون رقم (32) لسنة 2010 بشأن الكهرباء</p>	<p>The law aims to provide electricity to meet the needs of society and the national economy, allow public, joint, and private sectors (including national, local, Arab, and foreign entities) to invest in generation and distribution, and support and encourage the use of renewable energy in various fields and the localization of its industries.</p> <p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to the environmental sector:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Chapter 2: Ministry tasks <p>Article 3: Enhancing energy efficiency and promoting renewable energy.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Chapter 4: Sector activities <p>Article 11: Ratifying agreements related to generation projects to be implemented by investors, and agreements concerning the rehabilitation and development of the operation of existing power plants.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Chapter 6: renewable energy <p>Article 29/A: Collaborating with the National Center for Energy Research to conduct technical, economic, and environmental studies for electricity generation projects using renewable energy sources, in cooperation with relevant domestic and international entities.</p> <p>Article 29/B: Implementing, operating and investing in electricity generation projects using renewable energies</p> <p><u>Gaps in WEFE Nexus Consideration</u></p> <p>While Law No. 32 of 2010 on electricity effectively regulates and manages the electricity sector, it requires further elaboration to include additional details on the interconnections with environmental and agricultural considerations</p>
<p><i>Law No. (23) of 2021 on the Establishment of the Fund for Supporting the Use of Renewable Energies and</i></p>	<p>This law establishes a fund aimed at supporting the use of renewable energy sources and enhancing energy efficiency. It outlines the fund's objectives, management structure, sources of financing, and operational procedures for supporting renewable energy projects and improving energy efficiency.</p> <p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to all WEFE nexus sectors:</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
<p><i>Improving Energy Efficiency</i></p> <p>قانون رقم (23) لسنة 2021 بشأن إنشاء صندوق دعم استخدام الطاقات المتجددة وتحسين كفاءة الطاقة</p>	<p>Chapter 3: The objectives of the fund</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage energy consumers to use renewable energy sources and work on improving energy efficiency. • Increase the contribution of renewable energy sources to the targeted percentages. • Reduce the consumption of fuel and electricity used in major sectors (residential, industrial, agricultural, commercial, and service sectors, etc.). • Decrease harmful environmental emissions and limit climate change. • Contribute to raising public awareness about the importance of renewable energy and spreading the culture of its use and its role in sustaining energy resources. • Contribute to the transfer and localization of renewable energy technologies and energy-efficient equipment.
<p><i>Energy Conservation Law No. (3) of 2009</i></p> <p>قانون الحفاظ على الطاقة رقم (3) لسنة 2009</p>	<p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to environment sector:</p> <p>This law aims to disseminate and apply the concepts of energy conservation, which include rationalizing energy consumption, preserving it and raising the efficiency of its use in all areas that have a permanent impact on the rates of energy production and consumption. It also works to spread the use of renewable energies with its various applications.</p> <p><u>Gaps in WEFE Nexus Consideration</u></p> <p>While Law No. 03 on Energy Conservation effectively promotes energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources, it needs to be further elaborated to include additional details on the interconnections with water and agricultural considerations to ensure a more comprehensive approach to sustainable resource management.</p>
<p><i>Decision on Feed-in Tariffs for Renewable Energy Electricity Purchase Prices, amended by Decision No. /1113/ of 2020</i></p> <p>قرار تعرفه التغذية لأسعار شراء كهرباء</p>	<p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to environment sector:</p> <p>The decision on feed-in tariffs for determining the purchase prices of electricity produced from renewable energy aims to encourage investment in renewable energy projects for small and medium-sized enterprises that can be connected to the distribution network. The decision sets purchase prices that are generally considered rewarding for investors, providing good financial returns compared to the cost of fuel oil needed to produce the same amount of electricity.</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
<p>الطاقة المتجددة المعدل بالقرار رقم /1113/ لسنة 2020</p>	<p><u>Gaps in WEFE Nexus Consideration</u></p> <p>While the decision on feed-in tariffs for determining the purchase prices of electricity produced from renewable energy aims to encourage investment and provide financial incentives, it needs to be further elaborated to include additional details on the interconnections with water and agricultural considerations.</p>
<p>Renewable Energy in Syria until the Year 2030</p> <p>الطاقة المتجددة في سورية حتى عام 2030</p>	<p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this plan, there are some approaches relevant to all WEFE Nexus sectors:</p> <p>Measures under Implementation to Encourage the Use of Renewable Energy:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Coordinating with relevant authorities to establish incentives and facilities to encourage industrialists to use renewable energy as part of their consumption. 2. Preparing a legislative draft for renewable energy by an expanded committee with participation from all stakeholders, aimed at organizing renewable energy activities and projects by encouraging and motivating electricity consumers and investors to generate energy from renewable sources. 3. Providing a specialized laboratory to test photovoltaic panels imported from abroad to ensure their quality and compliance with approved standard specifications. 4. Following up on specialized training courses in cooperation with the Engineers Syndicate to qualify engineering personnel in the field of renewable energy and energy efficiency projects. <p>• Policies and Measures Necessary to Implement the Renewable Energy Plan</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Intensify the drinking water pumping program using renewable energy, secure funding from grants and aids, and establish a binding cooperation plan between the ministries of electricity, water resources, local administration, and the environment. 2. Developing legislation to enable the sale of electricity from private renewable energy projects to various sectors and consumers. 3. Giving priority to the establishment of renewable energy projects to feed the productive sectors (industry, agriculture, services, etc.), both public and private.

Environment sector

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
<p><i>Law No.12 of 2012 for the Ministry of Environment for State Affairs</i></p> <p><i>قانون رقم (12) لسنة 2012 بشأن وزارة البيئة لشؤون الدولة</i></p>	<p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this law, there are some approaches relevant to all sectors in WEFE Nexus:</p> <p>1. Chapter 2: Ministry objectives</p> <p>Article 2: This law aims to establish principles for environmental safety, protect the environment from pollution, achieve environmental development, and define the tasks of the Ministry in cooperation with relevant authorities to ensure the implementation of related laws and regulations.</p> <p>2. Chapter 3: Ministry tasks</p> <p>Article 3/1: Establish the necessary foundations and procedures for environmental impact assessment in cooperation and coordination with relevant authorities for new development activities, including infrastructure, industrial, agricultural, or service projects that pose a threat to the environment due to their size, nature, or pollutant emissions.</p> <p>Article 3/2: Preparing legislation, regulations, and studies to preserve the environment in all its elements, protect it systematically, and move towards a green economy in cooperation with relevant authorities</p> <p>Relevant Articles:</p> <p>Article 3/16: Establishing the foundations for creating national parks, gardens, and environmental streets, as well as the principles for natural reserves and their specifications, in cooperation with the Ministry of Agriculture and Agrarian Reform and relevant authorities.</p> <p>3. Chapter 4: Developing curricula and new environmental specializations in higher education stages.</p> <p>Article 4/1: Establishing environmental standards and requirements for the use of renewable and alternative energy technologies.</p> <p>Article 4/6: Participating in the protection of the coastline and marine environment from pollution.</p> <p>Article 4/7: Studying the causes of soil erosion, desertification, and all factors leading to land and groundwater pollution and the contamination of natural resources and proposing solutions.</p> <p>Article 4/10: Collaborating with the Ministry of Local Administration to develop methods for solid municipal waste management through reviewing environmental impact assessment studies.</p> <p>Article 4/15: Approving emergency plans to address natural disasters.</p>
<p><i>Desertification Monitoring and</i></p>	<p>The "Desertification Monitoring and Mitigation" project in Jebel al-Bishri aims to utilize remote sensing technology and land rehabilitation techniques to</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
<p><i>Mitigation Program and Project in the Syrian Badia – Jebel Bishri (March 1994 - December 2006)</i></p> <p>برنامج ومشروع مراقبة التصحر والتخفيف من آثاره في البادية السورية – جبل بيشري (آذار 1994 - كانون الأول 2006)</p>	<p>combat desertification. The project focuses on improving the economic and social conditions of local communities, training national personnel, and enhancing collaboration between ACSAD and national institutions, with funding from ACSAD, the Ministry of Agriculture and Agrarian Reform, and the German Technical Cooperation Agency (GTZ).</p> <p>Gaps in WEFE Nexus Consideration</p> <p>While the "Desertification Monitoring and Mitigation" project in Jebel al-Bishri effectively addresses desertification issues, it requires further elaboration to include additional details on the interconnections with water management and energy considerations to ensure a more integrated approach to the WEFE Nexus.</p>
<p><i>Laws and policies cover all sectors of the WEFE Nexus</i></p>	
<p><i>Syrian Arab Republic Nationally Determined Contributions Under Paris Agreement on Climate – 2018</i></p> <p>الجمهورية العربية السورية المحددة وطنياً بموجب اتفاق باريس بشأن المناخ 2018 –</p>	<p>The Syrian Arab Republic's 2018 NDCs under the Paris Agreement outline sector-specific strategies for emission reduction and climate adaptation. Key policies include enhancing renewable energy in the energy sector, managing forests and agricultural waste, and promoting sustainable land use. Adaptation and mitigation measures focus on improving water resource management and combating land degradation and desertification.</p> <p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this strategy, there are some approaches relevant to all sectors in WEFE Nexus:</p> <p>➤ Policies and strategies that contribute to reducing emissions by sector:</p> <p>Energy Sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulations and policies have been adopted, in which take into account the environmental aspects and increase the contribution of renewable energy, as well as its role to improves supply security by reducing dependence on fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in the generation sector. • Conversion of sanitary landfill gases into energy (and utilization of biogas). <p>Forests, lands and agricultural sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage and manufacture agricultural waste and safe recycling of residues instead of burning them and taking advantage of solid waste and liquid residues in the production of alternative energy by establishing modern plants. • Increase the production of forest plantations and forest area in the Syrian Arab Republic, so that contributing to enhance the role of forests in carbon sequestration.

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting renewable energy projects for agricultural uses. ➤ Adaptation Mitigation Measures by Sector: <p><u>Water resources management</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water scarcity adaptation in the agricultural sector could include: • Raising the efficiency of irrigation water use, support water harvesting projects, using highly efficient irrigation methods, and providing actual quantities of water needed by plants, as well as using supplementary irrigation to irrigate rain crops during droughts. • Improvement of the current agricultural practices (use of crops with low water needs, drought resistant crops). <p><u>Combating Land Degradation and Desertification</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achieving land degradation neutrality and improving management practices, particularly in the agriculture and forestry sectors. • Developing studies and methods for identifying and controlling dust storms in affected or threatened areas through the use of green belts and barriers, as well as studying suitable plant species to mitigate the effects of long-term dust storms.
<p><i>The national plan for new and renewable energies in Syria- January 2010</i></p> <p><i>الخطة الوطنية للطاقة الجديدة والمتجددة في سورية – كانون الثاني 2010</i></p>	<p>Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. However, within this strategy, there are some approaches relevant to all sectors in WEFE Nexus:</p> <p>The primary goal of NAAP process is to identify priority measures to adapt to climate change and climate variability and develop them into project-based activities that can address urgent needs for adapting to the adverse impacts of climate change in Syria.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify challenges hindering adaptation to climate change. 2. Identify national constraints on implementing activities related to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change. 3. Integrate global environmental management commitments into national policies <p>The INC (Initial National Communication) Strategy is designed based on the following themes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop sustainable institutional coordination mechanisms. 2. Develop clear and systematic integration of the UNFCCC concepts in the national policy and legislation.

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<p>3. Sustainable development of agricultural and water resources.</p> <p>NAAP Includes the following projects:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Integrated Agricultural Production: Enhancing integrated agricultural practices. 2. Water Conservation and Rational Use: Preserving water resources and using them efficiently, including modern irrigation. 3. Drought Forecasting and Monitoring Systems: Developing and implementing information systems for drought forecasting and monitoring to improve preparedness. 4. Improving the Investment Environment in Agriculture: Developing the investment environment for agriculture and agribusiness. <p>Agricultural and Water Research and Extension: Developing research programs and expanding knowledge in agriculture and water management.</p>

1.11.1 Assessment of Current Policies and Governance Structures

Syrian policies demonstrate a foundational approach to integrating elements of the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus, although this is often implicit rather than systematically enforced. For instance, the Water Legislation Law No. 31 of 2005 and Legislative Decree No. 90 establish robust frameworks for water resource management that support both agricultural productivity and ecosystem sustainability. These legislations ensure that water use is regulated not only to preserve environmental quality but also to enhance agricultural outputs, which are directly linked to water availability. Similarly, energy laws such as Law No. 32 of 2010 and Law No. 23 of 2021 promote renewable energy, which indirectly supports water and food security by reducing dependency on non-renewable resources that can have adverse environmental impacts. These laws collectively embody a shift towards a more sustainable and integrated approach, aligning with some aspects of the WEFE Nexus by addressing the interdependencies between water management, energy efficiency, and agricultural productivity.

Despite the presence of several laws and regulations that indirectly support the WEFE Nexus, there is a significant gap in explicit integration and coordination among these sectors within Syria's policy framework. Many of the policies focus on sector-specific outcomes without a comprehensive strategy that bridges all elements of the WEFE Nexus. For example, while the Agricultural Reform Law and the Law on Regulating Agricultural Relations provide detailed regulations for land use and agricultural practices, they lack clear linkages to energy policies and water management strategies that could enhance overall resource efficiency and sustainability. Additionally, although the Syrian Arab Republic's NDCs under the Paris Agreement outline climate adaptation and emission reduction strategies, they do not provide a cohesive plan that explicitly integrates water, energy, and food security in a way that would fully realize the potential of the WEFE Nexus. This lack of integrated planning and coordination may hinder the effective implementation of Nexus-oriented actions, limiting the ability to achieve sustainable development goals comprehensively.

1.11.2 Analysis of Legal Frameworks and Agreements

- **Legal Frameworks:** Syrian laws provide structured approaches to managing individual sectors but often lack explicit directives for integrating these sectors within a cohesive WEFE framework.
- **Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements:** Syria’s participation in international agreements, such as its Nationally Determined Contributions under the Paris Agreement, showcases an intent to align sectoral policies with global climate goals, but more focused efforts are required to fully realize nexus synergies.

1.11.3 Identification of Gaps

Key gaps in Syria's approach include:

- **Explicit Nexus Integration:** Most Syrian laws address sectoral issues in isolation, with limited provisions for the interconnected management of water, energy, food, and ecosystems.
- **Policy Implementation and Enforcement:** There is a noticeable discrepancy between policy formulation and its practical application, with many ambitious legal frameworks falling short in implementation due to various constraints, including political and economic challenges.
- **Modernization of Laws:** Several older laws require updates to incorporate modern technological advances and contemporary environmental challenges into their frameworks.

1.11.4 Potential for Cooperation

Opportunities for enhancing cooperation include:

- **Strengthening National Coordination:** Developing integrated management strategies that span all nexus sectors could facilitate more efficient resource use and sustainable development.
- **Enhancing Regional Collaboration:** Increased participation in transboundary water management and energy exchange programs could improve regional stability and sustainability, benefiting all countries involved in shared resource management.

1.12 Türkiye

Türkiye 's approach to the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) nexus is based on a wide range of policies, legal frameworks, and strategic initiatives that reflect the country's commitment to sustainable development across multiple sectors. This section provides an overview of existing policies and governance structures, analyzes relevant legal frameworks and agreements, identifies gaps in current implementations, and investigates the potential for increased collaboration. A detailed table (Table 27) outlines key policies relevant to the WEFE nexus, laying the groundwork for further analysis in the following subsections. These analyses aim to highlight Türkiye 's strategies and challenges in integrating and managing the interdependence of water, energy, food, and ecosystem resources, while also providing insights into both national and international collaborations.

Table 27 Policies, governance, legal frameworks - Türkiye

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<i>Water</i>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
<i>Law 831 on Water –1926</i>	<p><u>Document Description:</u> In 1926, Türkiye enacted a key Water Law outlining the management, provision, and maintenance of water resources. This legislation specified the roles of local government bodies, such as municipalities and village councils, in overseeing water supply and sanitation.</p> <p><u>Alignment with WEFE Nexus Principles</u> The law promotes sustainable water management, aligning with the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus principles. It emphasizes stakeholder involvement, including local communities and authorities, to ensure effective resource management. Supplementary Article 7 exemplifies how legal frameworks can support the WEFE Nexus by protecting water quality and promoting integrated management practices, crucial for environmental sustainability and public health.</p> <p><u>Gaps and Limitations</u> While the law effectively addresses water management, it does not explicitly explore the broader interconnections with energy and food resources central to the WEFE Nexus could be enhanced or elaborated further. Its primary focus is on the administrative and legal aspects of water provision and maintenance.</p>
<i>Regulation on water allocation No. 30974 of 2019</i>	<p><u>Document Description:</u> The Water Allocation Regulation regulates the use of water resources, and sets priorities for water allocation among different sectors.</p> <p><u>Alignment with WEFE Nexus Principles</u> Despite the extensive framework of the regulation, but it does not explicitly integrate the WEFE Nexus. However, there are some approaches relevant to the water in the energy and agriculture sectors;</p> <p><u>Article 7:</u> The priority order of water resource use: a) Drinking water and domestic use. b) Environmental use. c) Agricultural irrigation and aquaculture. ç) Energy production and industrial water needs. d) Commercial, tourist, recreational, mining, transportation, and other needs.</p> <p>Water allocation priorities are determined between basic needs, agriculture, industry, and energy production. And the importance of balancing the various uses of water in the environment, agriculture and energy sectors.</p>
<i>Water Efficiency Strategy Document and Action Plan in the Framework</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u> By the republic of Türkiye ministry of agriculture and forestry, the document aims to improve water efficiency across sectors to adapt to climate change. It integrates stakeholder input and emphasizes urban, agricultural, and industrial water use. Despite its extensive framework, the action plan does</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
<i>of Adaptation to the Changing Climate (2023 - 2033)</i>	<p>not explicitly integrate WEFE Nexus. However, there are some approaches relevant to the water in the energy and agriculture sectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture Water Use Efficiency <p>The strategies aim to boost agricultural water use efficiency to 60% by 2030 and 65% by 2050. Key measures include enhancing irrigation organizations through legal and technical studies, promoting sustainable practices, and integrating advanced monitoring and technology. They also involve real-time irrigation assessments, expanding rainwater harvesting, reusing irrigation runoff and treated wastewater, and increasing farmer training. Also, integrating the Nexus WEFE approach in this strategy by using renewable energy sources to support modern irrigation systems and improve overall efficiency.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Efficiency Components that Affect All Sectors <p>Aim: Mainstreaming Water Efficiency Practices Affecting All Sectors. Strategies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensuring the integration of drinking water, wastewater, treatment and solid waste facilities along with renewable energy projects. 2. Promoting examples of “integrated urban water management” and “water sensitive urban design” at the city scale.
<i>The Irrigation Unions Law No. 27882 of 2011</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The Irrigation unions Law regulates the establishment and management of irrigation associations in Türkiye , and provides a regulatory framework for irrigation and water resource management processes.</p> <p>Regarding the concept of “WEFE Nexus”, the law itself does not specifically focus on this concept, but through the regulations on financial and human resource management, it can be said that it contributes to improving water and energy management as Article 12 deals with the penalties related to water use violations, which affects the effective management of water resources and indirectly affects energy use in irrigation systems.</p> <p>The law does not directly address the link between biosecurity, environment, water and energy, but it lays the foundations that can indirectly support the integration of these elements by improving resource management.</p>
<i>Climate Change Adaptation Strategy and Action Plan 2024-2030</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The Turkish Climate Change Adaptation Strategy and Action Plan 2024-2030 provides a comprehensive approach to addressing climate change by enhancing resilience across various sectors.</p> <p>Although the strategy does not explicitly integrate the WEFE NEXUS, it includes relevant approaches:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Emphasizes improving water efficiency and sustainable management, including efficient irrigation and water recycling.

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Highlights enhancing energy efficiency in water systems by incorporating renewable energy to reduce fossil fuel dependence and greenhouse gas emissions. 3. Focuses on adapting farming practices for water and soil conservation, promoting drought-resistant crops, and optimizing irrigation. 4. Includes measures to maintain food security through climate-resilient crops and improved agricultural practices to adapt to changing weather and water conditions.
<i>Energy</i>	
<p><i>The Energy Efficiency law - Law No. 5627 of 2007</i></p>	<p><u>Document Description:</u> The Energy Efficiency Law of Türkiye (Law No. 5627), adopted on April 18, 2007, aims to enhance energy efficiency, reduce waste, lower energy costs, and protect the environment. It covers principles and procedures for improving energy efficiency in industries, buildings, power plants, and transportation.</p> <p><u>WEFE Nexus and Energy Efficiency Law</u> While the Energy Efficiency Law does not explicitly mention the WEFE Nexus, it does intersect with some of its principles, particularly in the areas of energy and environmental protection.</p> <p><u>Relevant Articles:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Article 1: The law aims to protect the environment, which aligns with the ecosystem component of the WEFE Nexus by promoting energy efficiency to reduce environmental impact. ➤ Article 2: The inclusion of renewable energy sources suggests a consideration of sustainable practices, indirectly supporting the WEFE Nexus's goals of integrated resource management. <p><u>Gaps in WEFE Nexus Consideration</u> Despite intersections, the Energy Efficiency Law does not fully address the interdependencies of the WEFE Nexus. The law does not mention energy efficiency on water sector, nor does it consider the implications of energy efficiency on agriculture and food production.</p>
<p><i>Law on utilization of renewable energy sources for electricity generation No. 25819 of 2005</i></p>	<p><u>Document Description:</u> The law regulates the use of renewable energy sources for the production of electrical energy, and aims to promote the use of these sources in a reliable and economical manner, with a focus on increasing the diversity of sources, reducing emissions and protecting the environment.</p> <p>The Law does not fully address the interdependencies of the WEFE Nexus. However, within this law, Energy regulations are intertwined with laws related to water, environment and agriculture.</p> <p><u>Article 7:</u> geological and hydropower must be used to meet energy needs in areas with sufficient geological resources.</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<p>Article 8: Projects that use renewable energy sources to meet agricultural needs are exempted from certain fees to encourage the sustainable use of renewable energy in this sector.</p>
<p><i>Law NO. 6094 Amending the renewable energy law - 2011</i></p>	<p>Document Description: Law No. 6094 amends the Renewable Energy Law by raising guaranteed prices, offering domestic production incentives, and expanding purchase obligations. It also introduces a centralized program for energy purchases and prioritizes renewable energy connections.</p> <p>Alignment with WEFE Nexus Principles While not explicitly addressing the WEFE Nexus, the law's focus on renewable energy, efficiency, and environmental protection aligns with sustainability goals. However, it does not directly connect to the interrelationships of water, energy, food, and ecosystems within the Nexus framework.</p>
<p><i>Regulation on increasing efficiency in the use of energy resources and energy – No. 27035 of 2008</i></p>	<p>Document Description: The Regulation on Increasing Efficiency in the Use of Energy Resources and Energy, issued by the Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources, sets out principles and procedures to enhance energy efficiency. Its objective is to ensure the efficient use of energy, reduce energy waste, lower the economic burden of energy costs, and protect the environment.</p> <p>Alignment with WEFE Nexus Principles Article 28 - (2): Prompts the studies for using the waste heat of thermal power plants primarily agricultural, water products, cold air warehouse and freshwater production sectors. Article 30 – (6): that emphasizing prioritize the projects in the below-listed fields:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Increasing the performance of biofuels produced from local agricultural crops. b) Techniques for producing biofuel and synthetic fuels from biomass resources. c) Hydrogen generation techniques using renewable energy resources such as hydro, wind, solar and geothermal energy. <p>In addition to Promote the use of alternative energy in various applications which supports the WEFE Nexus by reducing emissions and environmental impact, alternative energy solutions help manage resource use more efficiently and sustainably.</p>
<p><i>Law on utilization of renewable energy sources for the purpose of generating electrical</i></p>	<p>Document Description: This law aims to promote the use of renewable energy sources for electricity generation. Its objectives include enhancing the security, economic efficiency, and quality of renewable energy use, diversifying energy sources, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, managing waste products, protecting the environment, and fostering related industries supporting the development and implementation of renewable energy projects.</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
<i>energy – No. 5346 of 2005</i>	<p><u>Alignment with WEFE Nexus Principles</u></p> <p>By advancing renewable energy use, the law supports the WEFE Nexus by addressing the interconnections between water, energy, food, and ecosystems. Renewable energy reduces reliance on fossil fuels, lowering greenhouse gas emissions and mitigating environmental impact. This contributes to improved ecosystem health and supports sustainable development by minimizing the negative effects on water and land resources, ultimately benefiting all aspects of the Nexus.</p>
<i>Türkiye National Energy Plan - 2022</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The Türkiye National Energy Plan, by the republic of Türkiye ministry of energy and natural resources, includes five chapters: Key Indicators, Sectoral Activity, Policy Preferences, Results of Net-Zero Emission Restrictions, and Forecasts for 2035–2053.</p> <p><u>Policy Preferences - Renewable Energy</u></p> <p>The share of intermittent renewable energy sources such as wind and solar in total electricity generation is planned to be increased taking into account Türkiye’s current flexibility opportunities and renewable energy potential, and the potential in the future.</p> <p>In 2035, the installed capacity will increase to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 29.6 GW (24.6 GW onshore, 5 GW offshore) in wind power; • 52.9 GW in solar power. <p>For other renewable energy sources, the installed capacity will increase to 35.1 GW in hydroelectric power plants and 5.1 GW in geothermal and biomass power plants.</p>
<i>Food</i>	
<i>Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry 2024-2028.</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry 2024-2028 outlines the vision and goals for advancing Türkiye 's agricultural and forestry sectors over the next four years.</p> <p>Although the document does not explicitly integrate the WEFE NEXUS, it incorporates strategies related to the agriculture sector with various WEFE NEXUS elements.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The plan emphasizes improving irrigation practices and water management in agriculture. And encouraging practices that preserve water resources while maintaining agricultural productivity. • Encourages the adoption of energy-efficient technologies and practices in agricultural operations. This involves integrating renewable energy sources and improving energy use in farming processes.

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focuses on improving food production systems to ensure food security while minimizing environmental impacts. This includes adopting sustainable farming practices that reduce the carbon footprint of agriculture. • Implements measures to minimize food waste throughout the supply chain, from production to consumption.
<p><i>Towards Sustainable food Systems: National Pathway of Türkiye - 2021</i></p>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The republic of Türkiye ministry of agriculture and forestry outlines Türkiye 's strategic initiatives for achieving sustainable agriculture and food security. It focuses on integrating economic growth with environmental sustainability, aiming to address challenges like climate change and population growth. Despite its extensive framework, the national action tracks did not explicitly integrate WEFE Nexus. However, there are some approaches relevant to the water, environment and energy in the agriculture sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action Track (1): Shift to Sustainable Consumption Pattern The action plan promotes sustainability by converting inedible food into animal feed and reducing food loss. These strategies align with the WEFE Nexus by conserving water and energy, minimizing waste, and supporting ecosystem health, thereby ensuring efficient resource use. • Action Track (2): Boost Nature Positive Production at Sufficient Scale The action track includes measures that aligns directly with the WEFE Nexus include expanding irrigated areas and improving water efficiency, adopting energy-efficient irrigation methods, supporting energy efficiency projects in agriculture by encouraging the renewal of tractors and combine harvesters with more energy efficient versions., and limiting land use impacts on climate change. These strategies enhance resource management and sustainability by optimizing water and energy use while supporting ecosystem health. • Action Track (3): Build Resilience to Vulnerabilities, Shocks & Stresses The action builds resilience by diversifying forest products, afforesting areas, and encouraging agricultural forestry. It also emphasizes sustainable soil and water management, efficient water use in agriculture, and reducing agricultural greenhouse gas emissions, all contributing to environmental resilience
<p><i>The Agriculture Law No. 5488 of 2006</i></p>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The Agriculture Law No. 5488 aims to regulate and guide agricultural policy support and achieve sustainability in this sector. The law deals with financial support to farmers, and focused on providing agricultural support through quality and health standards, and using an integrated management system.</p> <p>The law does not directly address the concept of WEFE NEXUS, as it does not indicate a direct link between biosecurity, environment, water, and energy.</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
	However, through its general application, the law indirectly contributes to achieving agro-environmental sustainability that can overlap with other dimensions of WEFE NEXUS.
<i>Ecosystem</i>	
<i>Environment Law – law No. 2872 of 1983</i>	<p><u>Document Description:</u> The Environment Law in Türkiye was published in 1983 and updated in 2006, aims to protect and sustain the environment through sustainable development principles. The law mandates that all individuals and organizations adhere to environmental protection measures and collaborate with relevant authorities to prevent and mitigate environmental degradation. It includes provisions for environmental impact assessments, waste management, and the establishment of high-level environmental oversight bodies.</p> <p><u>Gaps and Limitations</u> Despite its extensive framework, the law does not explicitly integrate the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus, which highlights the interconnectedness of these resources and their environmental effects. While the law covers individual aspects of environmental protection, it lacks a unified approach to managing their complex interactions.</p>
<i>The Zero Waste Regulation No. 30829 of 2019</i>	<p><u>Document Description:</u> The Zero Waste Law promotes environmental sustainability by setting criteria for waste management and requiring various places to obtain zero waste certificates in four levels: basic, silver, gold, and platinum. Although it does not explicitly integrate the WEFE Nexus, the law enhances environmental protection by reducing waste in landfills and incinerators, thereby minimizing pollution. By encouraging recycling, it efficiently uses natural resources and conserves energy. Additionally, the law improves water quality by preventing waste from contaminating water bodies, thus protecting groundwater and surface water from pollution.</p>
<i>The Biosecurity Law No. 5977 of 2010</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u> Biosecurity Law No. 5977 is a Turkish legislation that aims to regulate the use of genetically modified organisms (GMO) and their products to ensure the protection of human, animal and plant health, the environment and biodiversity. The law defines the responsibilities and obligations related to the use of GMOs.</p> <p>Regarding the concept of WEFE Nexus (Water, Energy, Food and Environment), the law does not specifically address the link between biosecurity and the four elements of this concept. However, the laws related to biosafety indirectly affect the environment, water and energy resources by carefully regulating the use of GMOs and their environmental impacts.</p>
<i>Climate Change Mitigation</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u> The Turkish Climate Change Mitigation Strategy and Action Plan 2024-2030 outlines a comprehensive approach to reducing greenhouse gas emissions</p>

Related Policy/ Regulation/ Strategy	Relevance to Nexus
<i>Strategy and Action Plan 2024-2030</i>	<p>and addressing climate change. It focuses on: Promoting Low-Carbon Technologies, Enhancing Energy Efficiency, Supporting Sustainable Practices</p> <p>Although the strategy does not explicitly address the WEFE NEXUS, it includes relevant measures in the following areas:</p> <p><u>Water-Energy Nexus:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotes the use of renewable energy in water management to lower greenhouse gas emissions. • Encourages technologies that reduce energy consumption for water treatment and distribution. <p><u>Water-Food-Ecosystem Nexus:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support practices that enhance carbon sequestration and reduce emissions, such as precision farming and improved irrigation. • Optimize resource use, reduce waste, and improve sustainability in food systems by integrating water-efficient and low-carbon practices.
<i>Updated First Nationally Determined Contribution of Republic of Türkiye - 2023</i>	<p><u>Document Description</u></p> <p>The Updated NDC of Türkiye outlines the country’s updated climate goals and actions to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 2030, aligning with the Paris Agreement. It focuses on enhancing climate resilience and adopting low-carbon technologies across various sectors.</p> <p>Although the Updated NDC of Türkiye dose not explicitly integrate the WEFE NEXUS, it incorporates various NEXUS approaches to address climate change effectively. For the Water-Agriculture Nexus, the strategy promotes improved water use efficiency in agriculture and emphasizes integrated water management to support sustainable farming. In terms of the Energy-Agriculture Nexus, the plan encourages the adoption of energy-saving technologies in agricultural practices and supports the integration of renewable energy sources into farming operations. Regarding the Food-Agriculture Nexus, the focus is on sustainable production methods that aim to reduce emissions and enhance food security, alongside efforts to minimize food waste throughout the supply chain.</p>

1.12.1 Assessment of Current Policies and Governance Structures

Türkiye ’s policies demonstrate an evolving framework that aligns with elements of the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus, although the integration across these elements is not always explicit. Water management laws and regulations establish a solid foundation for sustainable water use, directly supporting both agricultural productivity and ecosystem sustainability. Energy policies promote efficiency and renewable energy use, which indirectly support water and food security by reducing the environmental impact of energy production. Food sector strategies focus on improving agricultural practices and enhancing water management, reflecting a direct link to water conservation and energy efficiency.

Despite these strengths, Türkiye 's policy frameworks exhibit gaps in explicit integration and coordination among the sectors involved in the WEFE Nexus. The strategies and laws tend to address water, energy, and food security in isolation, without a comprehensive strategy that bridges all elements of the Nexus. For instance, while there are extensive measures for water efficiency and renewable energy, the potential synergies between these sectors—such as using renewable energy for water treatment and irrigation—are not fully leveraged. Enhancing policy coherence and adopting an integrated nexus approach would allow Türkiye to more effectively manage its natural resources, ensuring sustainability and resilience in the face of environmental and socio-economic challenges. This could involve revising existing laws and policies to explicitly incorporate nexus thinking, promoting cross-sectoral collaboration, and developing comprehensive strategies that address the interdependencies between water, energy, food, and ecosystems.

1.12.2 Analysis of Legal Frameworks and Agreements

- **Legal Frameworks:** Türkiye has established robust legal foundations that influence the WEFE sectors, including specific laws aimed at water conservation, energy efficiency, sustainable agriculture, and ecosystem protection.
- **Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements:** While the document does not provide detailed descriptions of specific agreements, Türkiye 's involvement in international climate commitments, such as the Updated First Nationally Determined Contribution (2023), demonstrates a commitment to integrating environmental sustainability in its policies, which could be enhanced through more explicit WEFE nexus integration.

1.12.3 Identification of Gaps

Türkiye displays comprehensive sectoral policies but exhibits some gaps in nexus integration:

- **Explicit Nexus Integration:** Most policies address individual sectors with indirect references to nexus principles rather than a cohesive, integrated approach that explicitly connects water, energy, food, and ecosystems.
- **Inter-sectoral Coordination:** There is room for improvement in coordination among different governmental bodies to ensure that policies are not only complementary but also synergistically managed to maximize the nexus benefits.
- **Policy Modernization:** Some laws, like the very old Water Law of 1926, although amended, might need further updates to align with contemporary nexus challenges and technological advancements.

1.12.4 Potential for Cooperation

The potential for enhanced cooperation in Türkiye can be explored through:

- **National Policy Integration:** Strengthening the framework for interlinking policies at the national level to promote a more integrated approach to the WEFE nexus.
- **Regional and International Collaboration:** Increased participation in transboundary water management and energy exchange programs could improve regional stability and sustainability, benefiting all countries involved in shared resource management.

Suggested Transboundary WEFE Projects

This chapter outlines proposals for various WEFE (Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem) projects to be implemented across the study countries—Türkiye, Iran, Iraq, and Syria. These pilot projects are designed to be both scalable and sustainable, with a focus on their socio-economic impact and potential for regional cooperation and trust building. Each project proposal includes an assessment of its scalability, sustainability, and replicability, and evaluates its contributions to regional socio-economic development and trust building.

1.13 Small-Scale WEFE Projects

Project 1: Smart Irrigation Systems for Small-Scale Farms

Project Description

This project proposes the implementation of smart irrigation systems for small-scale farms in rural areas. By using sensor technology and automated water management systems, farmers can optimize water usage, reducing wastage and increasing crop yields. The smart irrigation system will monitor soil moisture, weather conditions, and crop water needs, ensuring efficient water delivery with minimal human intervention.

Scalability

The system can be easily scaled to larger farms or integrated with additional smart agricultural technologies like nutrient monitoring systems. This project serves as a model for regions that want to modernize their agricultural practices sustainably.

Sustainability

The project promotes water conservation and energy efficiency by optimizing irrigation processes, making it a key contributor to sustainable agriculture. It also reduces the reliance on manual irrigation, saving labor and water resources, and ensuring long-term food security in water-scarce regions.

Replicability

Smart irrigation systems can be replicated in various regions, particularly those that struggle with water scarcity and inefficient irrigation methods. The technology can also be adapted to different climates and agricultural practices.

Socio-Economic Impact & Trust Building

The introduction of smart irrigation will enhance agricultural productivity and income for small-scale farmers, boosting local economies. It will also reduce water-related conflicts by ensuring efficient and equitable water use across farms, promoting trust and cooperation among farmers.

Project 2: Solar-Powered Water Pumps for Remote Agricultural Areas

Project Description

This project focuses on deploying solar-powered water pumps in remote agricultural areas, replacing diesel-powered pumps or manual irrigation methods that require intensive labor. Solar-powered pumps use renewable energy to provide reliable and affordable irrigation water, particularly in rural areas that are off the grid.

Scalability

The solar pump network can be expanded to cover more regions, helping farmers irrigate larger areas of land. The system can be upgraded with battery storage, ensuring water availability even during periods of low sunlight.

Sustainability

By utilizing solar power, this project reduces reliance on fossil fuels, lowering carbon emissions and operational expenses. The use of renewable energy ensures the project's long-term viability, making it environmentally and economically sustainable.

Replicability

Solar-powered water pump systems are highly replicable and can be implemented in other regions facing similar energy and water challenges. The technology can also be adapted for other purposes, such as livestock watering or community water supply systems.

Socio-Economic Impact & Trust Building

The project will improve water access, enhance agricultural productivity, and create jobs in the renewable energy sector. By providing a reliable, clean energy-powered water solution, the project will improve the livelihoods of rural communities and foster collaboration among different regions over shared resources.

1.14 Medium-Scale WEFE Projects

Project 1: Establishing a NEXUS Governance Framework and Policy Coordination

Project Description

This project aims to develop and implement a WEFE (Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem) NEXUS governance framework for each country independently utilizing a unified approach between the BPME countries. The focus will be on creating a coordinated policy mechanism and governance framework that addresses the shared management of water, energy, and agricultural resources while preserving ecosystems in each country. This includes drafting a legal document that defines the WEFE Nexus approach for the country introduces joint policies and KPIs between the sectors in order to make the WEFE Nexus approach more applicable and more sustainable for the country.

Scalability

The governance frameworks within each country can be connected together by establishing a multi-country coordination body between the BPME countries, and creating joint monitoring systems for shared resource especially in shared river basins. This transboundary WEFE Nexus coordination body can also be utilized to share knowledge and experiences and lessons learnt across the countries. The governance framework can be expanded to include additional sectors beyond water, energy, food, and ecosystems, such as health and disaster management.

Sustainability

By formalizing cooperative governance over shared resources, the project ensures long-term sustainability in the management of water, energy, and food. It encourages integrated natural resource management while also promoting the preservation of the environment and regional stability.

Replicability

The governance model can be replicated in other regions facing similar challenges with shared water and energy resources. It provides a model for transboundary cooperation that can be implemented globally.

Socio-Economic Impact & Trust Building

This project promotes regional cooperation by developing clear, transparent, and equitable resource policies. A coordinated governance optimizes resource use, reduces conflict, and

promotes trust, along with improving socioeconomic conditions by providing better access to shared resources.

Project 2: Floating Photovoltaic (PV) System for Water Bodies and Agricultural Use

Project Description

This project proposes the installation of floating photovoltaic (PV) solar energy systems on various water bodies, such as ponds, lakes, and reservoirs. Floating PV panels harness the potential of these water surfaces to generate solar power, reducing the need for land-based installations while helping to conserve water by minimizing evaporation. In agricultural contexts, floating PV systems can provide clean energy for farms, supporting irrigation and other farm operations. The integration of solar power with water management enhances renewable energy generation and contributes to sustainable agricultural practices and water conservation.

Scalability

Floating PV systems are adaptable to a wide range of water bodies, from small ponds to large reservoirs, making them highly scalable. Farmers can deploy smaller-scale systems in farm ponds and irrigation reservoirs, while larger installations can be implemented in lakes and lagoons to increase renewable energy production. The technology's flexibility allows it to be adopted in various regions, supporting both agricultural and energy needs.

Sustainability

The project promotes the use of solar energy, reducing reliance on fossil fuels and supporting a clean energy transition. By minimizing water evaporation, it contributes to water conservation, particularly in regions experiencing water stress. For farmers, this helps ensure water availability for irrigation, improving crop resilience in dry climates.

Replicability

Floating PV systems are easily replicable across regions, particularly in areas with plenty of sunshine but limited space for traditional solar installations. This technology can be used in a variety of climates, making it appropriate for both urban and rural settings, including agriculture-focused areas where water bodies can serve multiple functions.

Socio-Economic Impact & Trust Building

The project will generate job opportunities in the renewable energy and agricultural sectors, thus increasing access to reliable, sustainable electricity. It provides farmers with a cost-effective energy solution, lowering operational costs and increasing productivity. The project can encourage collaboration in transboundary regions by sharing renewable energy benefits and water management strategies, as well as promoting regional cooperation and trust through mutual responsibility for resource management.

Conclusions

The Baseline Study on the Status of the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem Nexus in Iran, Iraq, Syria, and Türkiye reveals varying degrees of integration and recognition of the interconnectedness of water, energy, food, and ecosystem management across these nations. Each country demonstrates unique approaches and levels of engagement with the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus approach. Iran's legal and policy frameworks primarily emphasize water and agricultural management, with evolving considerations for energy efficiency and ecosystem sustainability. However, these policies often lack explicit mechanisms for fully integrating the Nexus concept, focusing instead on sector-specific outcomes without a comprehensive strategy to bridge all elements of the WEFE Nexus.

Main conclusions can be summarized in the following:

Iran, through the Ministry of Energy, has adopted an integrated approach to water and energy management, promoting a strong Water-Energy Nexus with combined targets for projects that address both sectors simultaneously. As for the agricultural and environmental sectors, there appears to be some shortage in policies that integrate the principles of Nexus. Also, it was noticed that the Nexus level of awareness is medium to high. While there is room to enhance integration, current efforts provide a strong foundation to build a more comprehensive nexus strategy that bridges sector-specific outcomes.

It was also observed that several local experts and governmental representatives did not feel free to contribute and share information related to the Nexus in Iran. In terms of the projects, it has been noticed that there is a strength in the major water energy nexus projects such as dams that utilize hydropower and provide water resources. In contrast, there appears to be a need for projects integrating water efficiency and agricultural sector such as smart water agriculture, projects that relate to energy efficiency in all sectors, or projects that focus on utilizing additional non-renewable sources in water and agriculture sectors.

In Iraq, the management of water, energy, food, and environment is handled by separate ministries with separate goals and KPIs, which often leads to challenges in implementing integrated Nexus-based projects. Political unrest has hindered progress, affecting WEFE Nexus initiatives and limiting coordinated action across sectors. Transboundary water issues also create an additional level of complexity, causing severe WEFE-related challenges, ranging from severe reduction in water share available for agriculture to irreversible ecological damage in some areas such as the Mesopotamian Marshlands in the South.

It is important to address the severe inherited obstacles caused by the political conflict first. However, despite these obstacles, there are notable opportunities for innovative WEFE Nexus projects, such as solar-powered agricultural systems and solar desalination. Notable efforts, although not currently sufficient, are underway to adapt water, energy, and food strategies to address climate change and resource challenges. While the understanding of nexus principles is present, further steps toward explicit cross-sectoral integration would strengthen cohesive resource management and maximize benefits. The awareness of the WEFE Nexus concept in Iraq, from our observations, appears to be at a medium level, highlighting the need for an integrated policy development and capacity building to address these pressing issues effectively.

In Syria, the management of water, energy, food, and environmental resources is carried out by separate ministries (each with separate goals), resulting in limited integration of WEFE Nexus principles. While there are individual cases that demonstrate some WEFE Nexus-based approaches, based on our observations, the overall level of awareness seems to be low. The country's legislative framework includes valuable laws addressing water management and efficiency, energy efficiency, and sustainable agricultural laws, that are addressed separately. By exploring opportunities for greater synergy and interconnected management in the WEFE sectors, Syria could unlock significant potential for sustainable and efficient resource use.

It is observed that years of conflict have not only disrupted governance and coordination but also led to a significant lack of literature and data on WEFE Nexus-related topics and initiatives. This has created a pressing need for comprehensive projects and strategies across all WEFE sectors, highlighting the urgency of addressing gaps in water, energy, food, and environmental management to support recovery and sustainable development.

In Türkiye, the water, energy, food, and environmental sectors are well-developed, supported by robust infrastructure and a strong technological foundation. While WEFE Nexus awareness appears to be high, there appears to be no clear common understanding what the term WEFE Nexus really means and how exactly it should be implemented. Türkiye demonstrates significant progress in integrating renewable energy policies with water and agricultural management, emphasizing resource efficiency and sustainability.

However, to fully capitalize on the interdependencies among sectors, the development of a more cohesive and explicit WEFE Nexus framework would be advantageous. Such a framework could enhance cross-sectoral coordination and optimize resource use. Türkiye has considerable potential for implementing innovative WEFE Nexus projects, including precision agriculture powered by IoT (Internet of Things) systems to optimize water use and efficiency, and large-scale renewable energy solutions such as floating solar farms and agro-voltaic systems. These cutting-edge initiatives could further strengthen resource efficiency and promote sustainable development.

The study underscores the need for enhanced policy coherence and cross-sectoral planning to optimize the WEFE Nexus in Iran, Iraq, Syria, and Türkiye. Developing comprehensive strategies that explicitly incorporate nexus thinking can promote sustainability and resilience. This requires robust governance frameworks, increased cooperation, and the engagement of multiple stakeholders to facilitate the transition towards integrated nexus management. By fostering a deeper understanding and implementation of the WEFE Nexus, these countries can better manage their resources, ensuring sustainable development and greater environmental, economic, and social stability.

Appendices

Appendix A: Stakeholder Engagement

Appendix B: Stockholder engagement form

Appendix A : Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder Mapping

A thorough examination and assessment were conducted to map out and analyze the main stakeholder groups involved in WEFE governance. This analysis delved into the different levels at which stakeholders operate and their specific contributions to shaping decisions and implementing related initiatives. The objective is to systematically recognize, classify, and evaluate stakeholders engaged in managing resources within targeted areas. This process seeks to comprehend each stakeholder's functions, impacts, interests, and expectations, thereby offering a comprehensive overview of the landscape of WEFE decision-making. The resultant insights will facilitate more informed, inclusive, and strategic decision-making in WEFE resource planning and management.

Table 28 below outlines the primary stakeholders identified in each country, highlighting their roles, significance, and methods of involvement.

In all four countries, key stakeholders were identified and carefully chosen based on their expertise and willingness to participate. Subsequently, the stakeholder engagement process utilized various approaches to collect input and encourage discussion. These methods included:

1. Questionnaires: Structured surveys were distributed to stakeholders (number and analysis) to gather information on their viewpoints, concerns, and recommendations regarding sectoral management and governance.
2. Interviews: In-depth, one-on-one online interviews were conducted with stakeholders to gain deeper insights into their roles, experiences, and expectations. This approach allowed for the exploration of complex issues and the collection of detailed feedback.
3. Phone Calls and Emails: Additional communication channels, such as phone calls and emails, were utilized to sustain ongoing engagement, clarify information, and promptly address any emerging issues.

The questions were crafted to collect input on WEFE Nexus challenges, constraints, and opportunities, as well as to pinpoint collaboration and coordination requirements. This also facilitated the identification of stakeholder motivations, interactions, and roles in decision-making processes across various levels. These inquiries yielded insights that will guide strategic interventions and priorities for sustainable WEFE Nexus management in the region.

Table 28 Stakeholder mapping table

Country	Institution	Category	Key Responsibilities
Iran	Ministry of Energy	Governmental	Energy supply, water services, wastewater services, electricity
	Ministry of Agriculture Jihad	Governmental	Agricultural products, food security
	Department of Environment	Governmental	Safeguarding the environment, management of wildlife and fisheries
	Universities and Research Centers and NGOs	Academia	Conducting research and providing technical expertise
Iraq	Ministry of Water Resources	Governmental	Water resource management, maintenance of irrigation canals
	Ministry of Electricity	Governmental	Electricity supply
	Ministry of Agriculture	Governmental	Manage public and private agriculture
	Ministry of Environment	Governmental	Management of environment and environmental resources, collecting environmental licenses
	Universities and Research Centers and NGOs	Academia	Conducting research and providing technical expertise
Syria	Ministry of Water Resources	Governmental	Water resource management
	Ministry of Agriculture	Governmental	All agricultural affairs
	Ministry of State for Environmental Affairs	Governmental	Management of environment and environmental resources
	Ministry of Electricity	Governmental	Electricity supply
	Universities and Research Centers and NGOs	Academia	Conducting research and providing technical expertise
Tkiye	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry	Governmental	Protecting agriculture and water resources, ensure sustainable production, ensure sufficient food
	Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources	Governmental	Management of energy supply and natural resources
	Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change	Governmental	Management of environment public works, urban planning, combating climate change
	Universities and Research Centers and NGOs	Academia	Conducting research and providing technical expertise

Stakeholder Views

The following section includes an initial summary of stakeholder’s views. A more thorough section shall be presented in the final report.

Iran

Survey Results and Data Analysis

This section presents the key findings from the survey conducted as part of the WEFE Nexus Project in Iran. The analysis aims to summarize the main trends.

Participation Details: Number of Survey Respondents and Online Meeting Attendees

Type of Participation	Number of Participants
Survey Respondents	6
Online Meeting Participants	0
Total	6

Note: We requested those who filled out the form to participate in an online meeting, but they declined. Additionally, some participants chose not to disclose their names or the organizations they are affiliated with.

Participating Entities: The interviews and data collection were conducted online with a diverse group of entities, including:

- Water and Wastewater Authorization - 1 person
- Iran Water Resources Management Co. - 1 person
- Australian National Centre for the Public Awareness of Science; The Australian National University - 1 person
- Gazestan Company - 1 person

Summary of Stakeholder Input:

The following sections will present the questions included in the survey along with the responses collected from the participants

1. Based on the responses gathered from experts and stakeholders in Iran regarding the challenges related to sustainable development in the water, energy, and food sectors (WEFE), a set of key priorities and challenges has been identified. These insights aim to highlight the areas requiring special focus to enhance sustainable development and improve resource management in the country.
 - **Overexploitation of Resources:**
This challenge was ranked the highest in most responses, receiving scores ranging from **8 to 10**. It highlights significant concerns about the unsustainable use of water and natural resources, leading to increased pressure on these limited assets and putting them at risk of depletion.
 - **Governance and Institutional Weaknesses:**
Scoring between **8 and 10**, this issue points to considerable gaps in policies and governance that hinder effective resource management. The need for regulatory reforms and stronger institutional frameworks was emphasized to improve coordination across sectors.
 - **Lack of Integrated Planning:**
Ranked between **6 and 9**, this challenge stresses the importance of enhancing planning and

coordination between sectors to achieve comprehensive and sustainable development. The lack of integration is seen as reducing the effectiveness of resource management and exacerbating overuse.

- **Climate Change Impacts:**

This issue received moderate to high rankings, between **6 and 8**, reflecting growing awareness of the negative impacts of climate change on natural resources and infrastructure. The need to address these effects is seen as critical for long-term sustainability.

- **Energy and Food Security Risks:**

These challenges were rated between **5 and 7**, expressing concerns about the ability to secure sufficient resources for energy and food in the face of environmental and economic pressures.

- **Infrastructure Deficits and Socioeconomic Disparities:**

While these challenges received moderate scores, there is a clear need to improve infrastructure and address social inequalities to ensure more comprehensive sustainability in resource use.

2. Based on the responses regarding the effectiveness of sectoral strategies and policies in promoting the development and continuous improvement of the Water, Energy, Agriculture, and Environmental sectors (WEFE) in your Iran, the following insights were gathered:

Overall Ranking of Sectors

- **Water Sector:**

- Rankings: **2, 2, 2, 2** (Average: 2)

The water sector consistently received low scores, indicating a perception of inadequate strategies and policies to promote effective development and improvement.

- **Energy Sector:**

- Rankings: **3, 3, 4** (Average: 3.33)

The energy sector scored higher compared to the water sector, with a slight improvement in perceived effectiveness. However, the rankings indicate that there is still room for significant enhancements.

- **Agriculture Sector:**

- Rankings: **2, 1, 3, 2** (Average: 2)

This sector received mixed reviews, with the lowest score of **1** indicating serious concerns about the effectiveness of current strategies and policies in driving development.

- **Environmental Sector:**

- Rankings: **2, 4, 1, 2** (Average: 2.25)

The environmental sector showed variability in scores, with one response reflecting a higher level of effectiveness (**4**), while other responses indicated dissatisfaction, leading to an overall low average.

Good Practices and Success Stories

Based on the provided information about sectoral nexus projects, the good practices and success stories can be summarized as follows:

- **Research Project:**

Sectors: Water and Agriculture

Location: Alborz Province, Iran

Status: Completed

Summary:

A research project was conducted in Alborz Province focusing on the nexus between the water and agriculture sectors. This project aims to enhance the sustainability of water resources through improved agricultural practices, contributing to waste reduction and increased efficiency. The success of this project highlights the importance of linking these two sectors to improve food security and resource management.

- **Implementation Project:**

Sectors: Water and Energy Management

Location: Not specified (no country details provided)

Status: In Progress

Summary:

This dual management project aims for the simultaneous management of water and electricity. It involves implementing innovative strategies to ensure that water and electricity flows operate in harmony, enhancing resource use efficiency. This project serves as a good example of how integrating these two sectors can achieve sustainable development.

Suggested Initiatives

Based on the experts' responses, the proposed projects include integrated management of water and agricultural resources, enhancing energy efficiency in agriculture, and ecosystem restoration. These projects aim to address challenges and promote sectoral integration for sustainable development.

- **Integrated Water and Agriculture Resource Management Project**

- **Objective:** Improve the sustainability of water use in agriculture and reduce waste.
- **Activities:**
 - Develop smart irrigation systems that rely on remote sensing technologies.
 - Train farmers on sustainable agricultural practices.
 - Establish partnerships with local authorities to distribute modern agricultural technologies.

- **Energy Efficiency Enhancement Project in Agriculture**
 - **Objective:** Reduce reliance on non-renewable energy sources and increase energy efficiency in the agricultural sector.
 - **Activities:**
 - Install solar energy systems in farms.
 - Provide technical support to farmers in implementing renewable energy technologies.
 - Develop agricultural models that effectively utilize renewable energy.
- **Policy and Institutional Framework Development Project**
 - **Objective:** Enhance governance and institutional capacity in managing natural resources.
 - **Activities:**
 - Develop integrated national policy strategies for water, agriculture, and energy resources.
 - Conduct workshops with decision-makers and local communities to identify gaps in current policies.
 - Improve coordination among stakeholders to achieve sustainable development goals.

Iraq

Survey Results and Data Analysis

This section presents the key findings from the survey conducted as part of the WEFE Nexus Project in Iran. The analysis aims to summarize the main trends.

Participation Details: Number of Survey Respondents and Online Meeting Attendees

Type of Participation	Number of Participants
Survey Respondents	6
Online Meeting Participants	0
Phone calls	2
Total	6

Note: We requested those who filled out the form to participate in an online meeting, but they declined and refused to record the phone calls. Additionally, some participants chose not to disclose their names or the organizations they are affiliated with.

Participating Entities: The interviews and data collection were conducted online with a diverse group of entities, including:

- Ministry of Water Resources - 3 person
- Anbar Agriculture Directorate - 1 person
- Al-Qasim Green University / College of Engineering - 1 person
- University of Garmian - 1 person

Summary of Stakeholder Input

The following section will present the questions included in the survey along with the responses collected from the participants.

1. Based on the responses gathered from experts and stakeholders in Iraq regarding the challenges related to sustainable development in the water, energy, and food sectors (WEFE), a set of key priorities and challenges has been identified. These insights aim to highlight the areas requiring special focus to enhance sustainable development and improve resource management in the country.

- **Overexploitation of Resources:**

This challenge received the highest ratings in most responses, with scores ranging from 8 to 10. This indicates significant concerns regarding the unsustainable use of water and natural resources, leading to increased pressure on these limited assets and putting them at risk of depletion.

- **Governance and Institutional Weaknesses:**

Scores ranged between 8 and 10, indicating considerable gaps in policies and governance that hinder effective resource management. There is a strong emphasis on the need for regulatory reforms and stronger institutional frameworks to improve coordination across sectors.

- **Lack of Integrated Planning:**

Rated between 6 and 9, this challenge underscores the importance of enhancing planning and coordination between sectors to achieve comprehensive and sustainable development. The lack of integration is perceived as diminishing the effectiveness of resource management and exacerbating overuse.

- **Climate Change Impacts:**

This issue received moderate to high ratings, ranging from 6 to 8, reflecting growing awareness of the negative effects of climate change on natural resources and infrastructure. Addressing these impacts is viewed as critical for long-term sustainability.

- **Food and Energy Security Risks:**

These challenges were rated between 5 and 7, expressing concerns about the ability to secure sufficient resources for energy and food amidst environmental and economic pressures.

- **Infrastructure Deficits and Socioeconomic Disparities:**

While these challenges received moderate scores, there is a clear need to improve infrastructure and address social inequalities to ensure more comprehensive sustainability in resource use.

2. Based on the responses regarding the effectiveness of sectoral strategies and policies in promoting the development and continuous improvement of the Water, Energy, Agriculture, and Environmental sectors (WEFE) in your Iran, the following insights were gathered:

Overall Ranking of Sectors

- **Water Sector:**

- **Rankings:** 3, 3, 3, 1 (Average: 2.5)

The water sector received mixed scores, indicating concerns about the effectiveness of current strategies and policies for managing this sector.

- **Energy Sector:**

- **Rankings:** 4, 3, 4, 2 (Average: 3.25)

The energy sector scored higher compared to water and agriculture sectors, suggesting a good level of effectiveness, although some improvements are still needed.

- **Agriculture Sector:**

- **Rankings:** 4, 2, 2, 2 (Average: 2.5)

This sector received varied ratings, with lower scores indicating concerns regarding the current strategies in promoting agricultural development.

- **Environmental Sector:**

- **Rankings:** 1, 1, 3, 1 (Average: 1.5)

The environmental sector received the lowest ratings, reflecting significant concerns about the effectiveness of policies and strategies in environmental protection and sustainability

Good Practices and Success Stories

Based on the provided information about sectoral nexus projects, the good practices and success stories can be summarized as follows:

- **Planting 5 million Trees and Palm Trees in Iraq**

Sectors Involved: Agriculture, Water Resources, Environment

Status: Active

Feedback: This initiative addresses critical issues like desertification and climate change while enhancing biodiversity. Its multifaceted approach effectively integrates environmental sustainability with agricultural development and water resource management.

- **Energy Support and Emissions Reduction**

Sectors Involved: Electricity, Oil, Environment, Agriculture, Water Resources

Status: Active

Feedback: The project's focus on environmental protection and energy efficiency highlights the importance of renewable energy utilization. By rationalizing energy consumption, it promotes sustainable practices across various sectors.

- **Alternative Energy Project**

Sectors Involved: Water Resources, Agriculture

Status: Proposal

Feedback: This project emphasizes the potential of alternative energy sources to enhance agricultural productivity and water management. Further development and implementation could significantly benefit both sectors.

- **Renewable Energy Project**

Sectors Involved: Environment, Agriculture

Status: Proposal

Feedback: Focusing on renewable energy within agricultural practices is crucial for sustainable development. This project aligns well with global efforts to reduce carbon footprints and promote eco-friendly solutions.

3. Based on participants' views regarding the presence of a governance framework for the WEFE Nexus in Iraq, it appears that the country does not yet have a comprehensive framework to manage the interconnected sectors of water, energy, food, and the environment in an integrated and sustainable manner. Participants highlighted that current policies address each sector separately, with a lack of effective coordination between ministries and relevant authorities. However, there is optimism about the potential for developing this framework in the future through joint efforts between government entities and research centers.

Suggested Initiatives

Based on the experts' responses, the proposed projects include integrated management of water and agricultural resources, enhancing energy efficiency in agriculture, and ecosystem restoration.

These projects aim to address challenges and promote sectoral integration for sustainable development.

- **Sustainable Irrigation and Renewable Energy for Agriculture**

Sectors Involved: Water, Energy, Agriculture

Description: This project proposes using renewable energy sources, such as solar or wind, to power irrigation systems in Iraq's central and southern agricultural regions. By integrating solar-powered pumps and drip irrigation, farmers can reduce water wastage while using clean energy.

Objective: To enhance agricultural productivity by providing a reliable and sustainable water supply powered by renewable energy.

Impact: Increased agricultural output, reduced reliance on fossil fuels, improved water-use efficiency, and climate change resilience.

- **Water Desalination Using Solar Energy for Coastal Regions**

Sectors Involved: Water, Energy, Ecosystem

Description: In Iraq's coastal areas or regions with saline groundwater, this project would focus on building solar-powered desalination plants to supply fresh water for both agriculture and domestic use. Solar energy would be harnessed to desalinate seawater or saline groundwater, ensuring a sustainable freshwater supply.

Objective: To provide sustainable solutions for freshwater scarcity in Iraq's southern regions.

Impact: A reliable freshwater supply for agriculture, reduction in the strain on groundwater resources, and protection of ecosystems.

- **Wastewater Treatment for Irrigation and Energy Generation**

Sectors Involved: Water, Energy, Agriculture, Ecosystem

Description: This initiative would treat wastewater from urban areas using energy-efficient methods, such as anaerobic digestion, which generates biogas. The treated wastewater would then be used for irrigating crops in nearby agricultural areas.

Objective: To reuse water sustainably for agriculture while generating energy from wastewater treatment.

Impact: Reduced pressure on freshwater resources, sustainable waste management, and increased energy production from renewable sources.

- **Integrated Nexus Data and Analytics Platform**

Sectors Involved: Water, Energy, Food, Ecosystem (Cross-Sectoral)

Description: Establishing a digital platform using advanced data analytics and remote sensing technologies to track and model interactions between water, energy, food, and ecosystem resources. This would help policymakers understand how changes in one sector (e.g., water for energy production) affect the other sectors and where intervention is needed.

Objective: To provide a comprehensive, real-time decision-making tool for integrated resource management across Iraq's sectors.

Impact: Improved coordination across sectors, optimized resource management, early detection of potential crises, and informed policy development.

- **Agroforestry and Ecosystem Restoration in Desert Areas**

Sectors Involved: Agriculture, Ecosystem, Water, Energy

Description: This project would promote planting drought-resistant trees and crops using treated wastewater and renewable energy-powered irrigation in desert and semi-arid regions of Iraq. The initiative would focus on restoring ecosystems, reducing desertification, and creating new agricultural opportunities.

Objective: To combat desertification, restore ecosystems, and create a sustainable agricultural model in arid areas.

Impact: Increased green cover, enhanced carbon sequestration, improved soil health, and sustainable livelihoods for rural communities.

- **Energy Efficient Aquaculture Systems**

Sectors Involved: Water, Energy, Food, Ecosystem

Description: Developing energy-efficient aquaculture systems using solar-powered water circulation and aeration to boost fish production. This initiative would aim to reduce the reliance on traditional, energy-intensive aquaculture methods while preserving water quality.

Objective: To provide a sustainable solution for increasing fish production without depleting water resources or causing ecosystem degradation.

Impact: Boosted food production, improved water-use efficiency, lower energy consumption, and healthier ecosystems.

- **Smart Agriculture Using Remote Sensing for Water and Crop Management**

Sectors Involved: Water, Agriculture, Energy

Description: This project would employ remote sensing technologies to monitor soil moisture, crop health, and water levels in reservoirs, allowing farmers to optimize irrigation and crop management practices. It could also track how much water energy production is used and its impact on agriculture.

Objective: To improve agricultural efficiency and reduce water waste by using precise, data-driven methods.

Impact: Enhanced agricultural productivity, reduced water waste, optimized energy usage, and minimized ecosystem impact.

Syria

Survey Results and Data Analysis

This section presents the key findings from the survey conducted as part of the WEFE Nexus Project in Syria. The analysis aims to summarize the main trends.

Participation Details: Number of Survey Respondents and Online Meeting Attendees

Type of Participation	Number of Participants
Survey Respondents	4
Online Meeting Participants	0
Total	4

Note: We requested those who filled out the form to participate in an online meeting, but they declined.

Participating Entities: The interviews and data collection were conducted online with a diverse group of participants. Additionally, some participants chose not to disclose their names or the organizations they are affiliated with.

- World Vision International- 1 person
- Independent consultant - 1 person

Summary of Stakeholder Input

The following sections will present the questions included in the survey along with the responses collected from the participants

1. Based on the responses gathered from experts and stakeholders in Syria regarding the challenges related to sustainable development in the water, energy, and food sectors (WEFE), a set of key priorities and challenges has been identified. These insights aim to highlight the areas requiring special focus to enhance sustainable development and improve resource management in the country.
 - **Infrastructure Deficiencies:**

This challenge ranked the highest in several responses, receiving scores of 10 in multiple instances. It highlights major concerns about the inadequacy of infrastructure to support sustainable development. Addressing these deficiencies is critical for improving the management of water, energy, food, and environmental resources.

- **Overexploitation of Water Resources:**

Consistently ranked between 5 and 8, the overuse of both groundwater and surface water resources poses a significant threat. This reflects the need for more sustainable practices to protect and preserve these limited resources, preventing long-term depletion.

- **Pollution and Contamination:**

Scoring between 2 and 7, pollution remains a pressing issue. The contamination of water, air, and soil continues to hinder sectoral development, highlighting the importance of stronger environmental protection measures to combat pollution.

- **Governance and Institutional Weaknesses:**

With rankings ranging from 6 to 9, this challenge indicates that weak governance structures and policy gaps significantly hinder resource management. Strengthening institutions and improving policy frameworks are essential to enhance coordination and accountability across sectors.

- **Lack of Integrated Planning:**

Ranked between 4 and 8, the absence of coordinated planning across sectors is seen as a major issue. This lack of integration results in ineffective management of resources, further complicating efforts to address environmental and economic challenges.

- **Socioeconomic Disparities:**

Socioeconomic inequalities were rated between 7 and 9. These disparities hinder equitable access to resources and exacerbate vulnerabilities in marginalized communities, making it a critical issue to address for overall sustainability.

- **Climate Change Impacts:**

This challenge received rankings between 2 and 6, reflecting growing awareness of the negative consequences of climate change on water resources, agriculture, and infrastructure. Mitigation and adaptation efforts are increasingly recognized as necessary for ensuring long-term resilience.

- **Reliance on Non-Renewable Energy Sources:**

With scores between 7 and 8, the reliance on non-renewable energy is seen as a significant challenge. This underscores the need for transitioning to renewable energy sources to reduce environmental impacts and support sustainable development.

- **Food Security:**

Ranked between 4 and 8, concerns about food security persist due to environmental degradation and resource constraints. Ensuring a stable and sufficient food supply is critical, particularly in the face of increasing demand and climate pressures.

2. Based on the responses regarding the effectiveness of sectoral strategies and policies in promoting the development and continuous improvement of the Water, Energy, Agriculture, and Environmental sectors (WEFE) in your Iran, the following insights were gathered:

- **Water Sector:**

- Rankings: 4, 3, 3, 4 (Average: 3.5)

The water sector generally received positive scores, indicating a perception of relatively effective strategies and policies for development. However, there's still room for improvement, especially in addressing existing challenges.

- **Energy Sector:**

- Rankings: 2, 4, 2, 5 (Average: 3.25)

The energy sector displayed mixed reviews, with scores ranging from 2 to 5. While some responses reflect confidence in current strategies, others highlight concerns about effectiveness, suggesting the need for further enhancements.

- **Agriculture Sector:**

- Rankings: 3, 5, 2, 5 (Average: 3.75)

The agriculture sector received relatively higher scores, particularly in the second and fourth responses, indicating general satisfaction with its strategies and policies. Nonetheless, variability in ratings suggests that certain areas still require attention.

- **Environmental Sector:**

- Rankings: 1, 2, 2, 3 (Average: 2)

The environmental sector consistently received low scores, reflecting significant concerns about its effectiveness. This underscores the need for urgent reforms to enhance policies and strategies for better integration and impact.

Good Practices and Success Stories

Based on the provided information about sectoral nexus projects, the good practices and success stories can be summarized as follows:

- **Research Project:**

Sectors: Water and Agriculture

Location: Alborz Province, Iran

Status: Completed

Summary:

A research project was conducted in Alborz Province focusing on the nexus between the water and agriculture sectors. This project aims to enhance the sustainability of water resources through improved agricultural practices, contributing to waste reduction and increased efficiency. The success of this project highlights the importance of linking these two sectors to improve food security and resource management.

- **Implementation Project:**

Sectors: Water and Energy Management

Location: Not specified (no country details provided)

Status: In Progress

Summary:

This dual management project aims for the simultaneous management of water and electricity. It involves implementing innovative strategies to ensure that water and electricity flows operate in harmony, enhancing resource use efficiency. This project serves as a good example of how integrating these two sectors can achieve sustainable development.

3. Based on expert opinions regarding the governance framework, the ongoing conflicts in Syria have resulted in a fragmented governance landscape, with no comprehensive nationwide framework for the Water-Energy-Food-Environment (WEFE) Nexus. While discussions on WEFE-related initiatives may occur in various forums, there are currently no concrete initiatives being

implemented on the ground. This highlights a significant gap between theoretical frameworks and practical applications in resource management.

Suggested Initiatives

Based on the experts' responses, the proposed projects include integrated management of water and agricultural resources, enhancing energy efficiency in agriculture, and ecosystem restoration. These projects aim to address challenges and promote sectoral integration for sustainable development.

- **Integrated Water and Energy Resource Management Project:**

Sectors Involved: Water and Energy

Description: Develop a system for integrated management of water and energy resources that includes establishing renewable energy plants to support agricultural irrigation systems, enhancing the efficiency of water and energy use in agriculture.

- **Sustainable Agriculture Technology Improvement Project:**

Sectors Involved: Agriculture and Water

Description: Implement programs to train farmers on sustainable agricultural practices focusing on efficient water usage, such as soil-less farming or precision agriculture. Renewable energy technologies could be employed to power irrigation systems.

- **Climate Change Adaptation Project:**

Sectors Involved: Water and Agriculture

Description: Develop climate adaptation strategies that include establishing desalination plants and distributing the water to farmers in drought-prone areas, using renewable energy to operate these plants.

- **Water and Sanitation Infrastructure Improvement Project:**

Sectors Involved: Water and Agriculture

Description: Develop sustainable water and sanitation infrastructure that includes treatment technologies and the reuse of wastewater for agricultural purposes, enhancing water security and reducing pressure on freshwater sources.

- **Research and Development Project:**

Sectors Involved: Water, Energy, and Food

Description: Conduct research to assess the impact of renewable energy use on crop productivity and water efficiency. This could include case studies and pilot projects in local communities.

Türkiye

Survey Results and Data Analysis

This section presents the key findings from the survey conducted as part of the WEFE Nexus Project in Türkiye. The analysis aims to summarize the main trends.

Participation Details: Number of Survey Respondents and Online Meeting Attendees

Type of Participation	Number of Participants
Survey Respondents	6
Online Meeting Participants	0
Total	6

Note: We requested those who filled out the form to participate in an online meeting, but they declined.

Participating Entities: The interviews and data collection were conducted online with a diverse group of participants. Additionally, some participants chose not to disclose their names or the organizations they are affiliated with.

- International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) - 1 person
- Kırşehir Ahi Evran University - 1 person
- Texas A&M University - 1 person

Summary of Stakeholder Input

The following sections will present the questions included in the survey along with the responses collected from the participants

1. Based on the responses gathered from experts and stakeholders in Türkiye regarding the challenges related to sustainable development in the water, energy, and food sectors (WEFE), a set of key priorities and challenges has been identified. These insights aim to highlight the areas requiring special focus to enhance sustainable development and improve resource management in the country.

- **Overexploitation of Resources:**

Ranked consistently between 7 and 9, this challenge underscores the unsustainable use of water resources, both groundwater and surface water. It points to the urgent need for better management practices to conserve these critical resources and avoid long-term depletion.

- **Pollution and Contamination:**

With rankings ranging from 2 to 8, pollution remains a serious concern for sectoral development. The contamination of water resources is a widespread issue, and addressing this requires robust environmental protection strategies to ensure cleaner, safer water.

- **Lack of Integrated Planning:**

Ranked between 7 and 8, this challenge highlights the absence of coordinated planning across sectors. Better integration is necessary to develop sustainable solutions that address the interconnectedness of water, energy, food, and environmental systems.

- **Climate Change Impacts:**

Consistently ranked between 7 and 9, the effects of climate change are a growing concern. The sector's vulnerability to climate variability emphasizes the need for adaptive measures to mitigate the risks posed by climate-induced water shortages and other disruptions.

- **Socioeconomic Disparities:**

Ranked between 6 and 10, socioeconomic inequalities strongly impact access to water and other resources. Addressing these disparities is crucial to ensuring equitable and sustainable development across different regions.

- **Governance and Institutional Weaknesses:**

Rankings between 5 and 7 reflect concerns about the effectiveness of governance and institutional structures. Strengthening regulatory frameworks and ensuring better policy implementation are key to improving resource management and sectoral sustainability.

- **Infrastructure Deficits:**

Ranked between 5 and 7, the lack of sufficient infrastructure continues to hinder the efficient use and management of water resources. Investment in modernizing and expanding infrastructure is essential to support sustainable growth in the water sector.

2. Based on the responses regarding the effectiveness of sectoral strategies and policies in promoting the development and continuous improvement of the Water, Energy, Agriculture, and Environmental sectors (WEFE) in your Türkiye, the following insights were gathered:

- **Water Sector:**

Rankings: 3, 5, 4 (Average: 4) The water sector appears to be moderately successful across the responses. The highest ranking (5) reflects that some respondents view water management strategies as effective, while the lower scores indicate areas for improvement.

- **Energy Sector:**

Rankings: 4, 4, 2 (Average: 3.33) The energy sector demonstrates varying levels of success. While two respondents rated it highly (4), one rated it lower (2), suggesting that, although policies are somewhat effective, there is room for improvement, particularly in areas of efficiency and sustainability.

- **Agriculture Sector:**

Rankings: 2, 5, 1 (Average: 2.67) The agriculture sector received more mixed feedback. One high score (5) indicates successful initiatives, but the lower rankings (2, 1) highlight concerns over the effectiveness of current strategies, possibly due to challenges in resource management or integration with other sectors.

- **Environmental Sector:**

Rankings: 1, 4, 3 (Average: 2.67) This sector shows a wide range of opinions. One respondent rated it very low (1), suggesting dissatisfaction with environmental strategies, while others offered more moderate scores. This reflects a need to strengthen environmental policies to better align with sustainable development goals.

Good Practices and Success Stories

Based on the provided information about sectoral nexus projects, the good practices and success stories can be summarized as follows:

- **Strategic Planning of Natural Resources: Dynamic Modelling of Water, Energy, and Food (WEF) Nexus for The Gediz Basin- Türkiye**

Countries Involved: Türkiye and USA

Status: Completed

Summary: This project focused on the strategic planning of natural resources in the Gediz Basin through dynamic modeling of the water, energy, and food nexus, demonstrating effective cross-country collaboration between Türkiye and the USA.

- **Dynamic Modeling of Water, Energy, and Food Nexus in the Central Kızılırmak Basin**

Countries Involved: Türkiye and USA

Status: Completed

Summary: A successful collaborative initiative between Türkiye and the USA, applying dynamic modeling to optimize the interconnected management of water, energy, and food resources in the Kızılırmak Basin.

Suggested Initiatives

Based on the experts' responses, the proposed projects include integrated management of water and agricultural resources, enhancing energy efficiency in agriculture, and ecosystem restoration. These projects aim to address challenges and promote sectoral integration for sustainable development.

- **Water and Energy Resource Management Improvement Project**

Sectors Involved: Water and Energy

Description: Establish an integrated system for improving the management of water and energy resources in Türkiye, focusing on upgrading infrastructure to reduce losses and increase resource use efficiency. The project will involve investment in new technologies, such as smart systems for monitoring water flow and energy usage.

- **Water Pollution Mitigation Project**

Sectors Involved: Water and Environment

Description: Develop effective strategies to combat water pollution, including the establishment of wastewater treatment plants and the improvement of water quality in rivers and lakes. The project aims to protect water resources from pollution and enhance the quality of life in local communities.

- **Sustainable Agriculture Project**

Sectors Involved: Agriculture and Water

Description: Implement sustainable agricultural practices to improve water use in farming, such as drip irrigation systems and the cultivation of drought-resistant crops. The project focuses on enhancing agricultural productivity while reducing pressure on water resources.

- **Integrated Planning Enhancement Project**

Sectors Involved: Water, Energy, and Agriculture

Description: Develop a framework for integrated planning across sectors to ensure efficient and balanced resource use. The project will include workshops and training sessions for planning officials in various fields to promote cooperation and coordination.

- **Renewable Energy in Agriculture Project**

Sectors Involved: Energy and Agriculture

Description: Utilize renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind energy, to power irrigation systems and agricultural facilities. The project aims to improve energy efficiency in the agricultural sector and reduce reliance on fossil fuels.

Appendix B : Stakeholder Engagement Form

Baseline Study on the Status of the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus in Middle Eastern Countries

Name: _____

Institution: _____

Country: _____

Date: _____

Objective of this form

The objective of this form is to gather stakeholder input relevant to the main research goals of this project. The sheet has several questions aimed at collecting and integrating feedback from stakeholders from each of the target countries. Please fill in the form to the best of your knowledge and we would be happy to arrange an interview to discuss the form afterwards.

Please email filled form to zayadeenleen8@gmail.com.

Project Background.

The Blue Peace Middle East (BPME) initiative, part of the Islamic Network on Water Resources Development and Management (INWRDAM) WEFE Nexus Hub, seeks to promote peace and sustainable development in the Middle East by leveraging water resources. The initiative aims to improve water, energy, and food security, as well as ecosystem resilience, through regional knowledge sharing and project implementation. This effort is part of the initiative, and aims to engage with key stakeholders, to conduct a WEFE Baseline Study across Iran, Iraq, Syria, and Türkiye . This study will analyze interactions among water, energy, food, ecosystems, and climate change, identifying knowledge gaps and opportunities for stronger intersectoral linkages. The project aims to offer data-driven strategies and recommendations to improve regional cooperation and promote sustainable resource management and resilience.

1 What are the current sustainability challenges facing sectoral development in your country? Rank from 1 to 10, where 1 is the least important and 10 is most.

Ranking (1-10)	WEFE Sectors
	Overexploitation of ground and surface water resources
	Pollution and contamination
	Lack of integrated planning
	Climate change impacts
	Infrastructure deficiencies
	Socioeconomic disparities
	Reliance on non-renewable energy sources
	Governance and institutional weaknesses (Policy and regulatory gaps)
	Food security

2 Sectorial strategies and policies have an important role in leading the development and continuous improvement of WEFE sectors through proper planning, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation. Are the sectoral strategies and policies in your country successful in promoting the effective development and continuous improvement of each of the WEFE sectors?

Sector	Rank from 1-5 (where 1 is the lowest and 5 is the highest)
Water sector	
Energy sector	
Agriculture sector	
Environmental sector	

3 WEFE nexus mapping. Do you know of any Good Practices and success stories of Nexus projects or initiatives between 2 or more sectors?

Type of project	Which sectors	Status

4 In your country do you have a governance framework for WEFE Nexus?

5-Any lessons learnt from previous WEFE Nexus initiatives or projects